

Eu-ARTECH

CHARISMA

IPERION CH

“Success stories”

a preliminary compilation – 10.05.2019

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Notice:

The following definitions are used herein at point 5:

Academic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to academic advances, across and within disciplines, including significant advances in understanding, methods, theory and application (this could be scientific, but could also be in other disciplines related to heritage science eg advances in understanding the materials and structure of an object contributing to historical research questions)

Economic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to the economy. (e.g. the commercialisation of the instrument developed)

Societal impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to society, especially to preservation of CH – e.g. by introducing a new method of conservation, adopted by the community or commonly adopted new facts (knowledge) about the object of art

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Examinations of violins made by Antonio Stradivari, Giuseppe Guarneri ‘del Gesu’, Lorenzo Storioni in Museum of Violin in Cremona with NMR Mouse – MOLAB 2018

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry
- other – describe:

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Portable MRI inspects frescoes, paintings, violins and mummies

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE
- other:

comments:

(e.g. the history of the development: first idea during ..., prototype during, mature design)

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The NMR-MOUSE is a commercial product of Magritek holding and is being produced by Magritek GmbH in Aachen. Magritek GmbH is directed by Federico Casanova and Juan Perlo, who developed the instrument in the EU-ARTECH project. The company has expanded since and leads the world market in producing tabletop NMR spectrometers for chemical analysis.

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

8. Person to be contacted for details (sent by Markus Küppers)

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TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: 2016: Effects of ageing on the wood and varnish of violins and violas & 2018: Non-invasive Examination of Stratigraphic System in violins

Project proposal acronym: 2016: AshNMR & 2018:

Date of realization: 26. – 30 Sept. 2016 & 7.-12- Oct. 2018

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Dr. Colin Harrison & Dr. Marco Malagodi

Project leader institution: Ashmolean Museum, Oxford, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) NYU, Abu Dhabi; Museo del Violino Cremona.

Field of specialization of the user group: Scientist, Conservator.....

General description of the TNA activity

The stiffness of the wood is one important parameter that defines the sound quality of a violin. The stratigraphy of the backplanes of master violins by the master luthiers from Cremona was mapped by portable Magnetic Resonance Imaging with the NMR-MOUSE to learn in how far and to what extent the elasticity of the wood has been modified through surface treatment and age.

Major results of the access

We found evidence of surface treatments that changed the elastic properties of the violin back planes in layers up to half a millimetre. This was more often found on the outer than on the inner surface suggesting the use of an invisible primer that stiffened the surface layer. At this time, it remains unclear if the inner surfaces were treated at the time of making or later at a time of restoration.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? The results from the first study at the Ashmolean Museum were so exciting that a second study was conducted at the Museo del Violino in Cremona.

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how:

NOW – why: The results are very recent. The dissemination in terms of publications are in progress. Preliminary accounts have been given in talks and posters at conferences.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The NMR-MOUSE functioned as a tool to non-invasively analyze the wood density and the molecular dynamics according to material elasticity by acquiring depth profiles of the hydrogen density and the NMR relaxation time T2. An assumption of a correlation of the age with the wood density could be refuted. In agreement with the literature, we confirmed that highly homogeneous wood was used that exhibits uniform density not only across the plane of the back plate but also throughout all

depths of the wood.

Highly informative NMR relaxation time distributions were measured as a function of depth across the back planes of the violins, revealing areas of enhanced and attenuated wood elasticity. These variations occurred sometimes at unexpected locations within the wood, indicating that they are not completely attributable to a treatment with varnish or primer. Instead, any progression towards attenuated mobility may indicate also damage that has occurred not only on the surfaces, but sometimes below the surface or in the center of the maple plates. The Stradivari violin Cremonese has shown a consistent structure on the outside and the inside at different spots, that matches that of the other violins only at the outer surface. It may report an uncommon fabrication technique, the marks of history, or some past restoration work.

Bernhard Blümich and Christian Rehorn from RWTH Aachen University adjusting the compact magnetic resonance imaging sensor to measure a depth profile through the back of the Cremonese Violin by Stradivari. Copyright Claudia Invernizzi, Museo del Violino, Cremona.

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Examinations of violins made by Antonio Stradivari, Giuseppe Guarneri ‘del Gesu’, Lorenzo Storioni in Museum of Violin in Cremona with OCT – MOLAB 2018

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry
- other – describe:

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) – NO

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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surname: Targowski

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TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal:

Effects of ageing on the wood and varnish of violins and violas & 2018: Non-invasive Examination of Stratigraphic System in violins

Project proposal acronym: thickNESS

Date of realization: 2-7.07.2018 – OCT; ...

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Marco Malagodi

Project leader institution: University of Pavia, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) Museum of Violin in Cremona, University of Parma, Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule (RWTH) Aachen, Germany

Field of specialization of the user group: scientists & conservators

General description of the TNA activity

to assess non-invasively the accurate thickness measure and appearance, condition and properties of varnishes in ancient violins. The data collected validate and improve the recently-developed methodology which allowed to non-invasively investigate how and to what extent varnish thickness vary on the surface by combining UV-induced fluorescence (UVIFL) photography and reflection FT-IR spectroscopy.

This action can be considered as a “success story” because of the importance of the object and results leading to publications

Major results of the access

1. “A micro-tomographic insight into the coating systems of historical bowed string instruments” by Fiocco G., Rovetta T., Invernizzi C.(), Albano M., Malagodi M., Licchelli M., Re A., Lo Giudice A., Lanzafame G.N., Zanini F., Iwanicka M., Targowski P., Gulmini M. - submitted to *Coatings*
2. “Non-invasive mobile technology to study the stratigraphy of ancient Cremonese violins: OCT, NMR-MOUSE and reflection FT-IR spectroscopy” by Invernizzi et al – submitted for TECHNART 2019 conference and a paper in *Microchemical Journal*

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? ...not known to us..

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: writing of publications

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

“OCT provided information about number and thickness of varnish and preparation layers, as well as detecting dispersed particles acting as fillers or colorants; FT-IR spectroscopy identified the chemical composition of the layered materials [2]; and the NMR-MOUSE investigated the wood density and elasticity, revealing wood treatments at the inner and outer surfaces of the plates. The gathered results add a further valuable contribution to the knowledge of the ancient processes adopted in the Cremonese violin making workshops during the considered period and subsequent restoration efforts.” - CI

Examination of "Principe Doria" violin made by Guarneri del Gesù in 1734, Violin Museum in Cremona (Laboratorio Arvedi di Diagnostica Non-Invasiva, CISRIC, Università degli Studi di Pavia, IT), from the left: Magdalena Iwanicka, Nicolaus Copernicus Univ. Torun PL and Claudia Invernizzi, Laboratorio... © P. Targowski

Examination of "Principe Doria" violin made by Guarneri del Gesù in 1734, Violin Museum in Cremona (Laboratorio Arvedi di Diagnostica Non-Invasiva, CISRIC, Università degli Studi di Pavia IT), from the left: Claudia Invernizzi and Giacomo Fiocco from this laboratory, Magdalena Iwanicka, Nicolaus Copernicus Univ. Torun, PL, © P. Targowski

Examination of 17th century paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London with DHSPI III- MOLAB 2018

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry
- other – describe:

3. Tentative **punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

NDT structural Diagnosis: The DHSPI III hybrid geometry provides non contact high resolution defect detection with digital capturing ease. DHSPI detects in micrometer resolution all typical subsurface/bulk defects that impact on the surface. Hidden cracks and detachments, voids and weakened areas invisible to other advanced imaging tools become traceable from surface. Raw data manipulation algorithms offer multi-tasking tools usable to generate accurate **defect documentation topography**, defects with exact coordinates, surface morphology , 3D surface mapping. Post-processing tools are employed to most applications of DHSPI . Example: serve to generate a coded “signature” conducting to the verification of originality procedures, e.g. **Originality assessment** before and after travel.

Risk priority map: Defect topography map is direct visual qualitative result from pre-processing recording, while risk priority map is quantitative result after post-processing. The structural condition is prioritised according to the impact of defects on precious surface to carry out necessary remedial interventions. Additionally it is visualised the defect micro-structure in 2D and 3D. The defects or defected areas are located, sized in 1:1 scale and deformation is measured to be marked as μm per area (mm^2 cm^2 related to the severity of defect impact on surface signifying the risk of permanent damage.

Preventive conservation: Monitoring environmental and microclimate impact of interior/exterior surfaces. Decorative artifacts, furniture, frescoes and wall paintings in historical buildings and monuments deteriorate constantly in response to the environment. DHSPI III can operate automatically in long term measurements to perform monitoring of surface reactions due to natural fluctuations of RH/T. Suits for on-field measurement requirements and can operate in moderate harsh out of laboratory conditions, e.g. Monuments and Churches environmental impact

Direct monitoring of materials, fragile surfaces are recorded in respond to natural climate conditions allowing to evaluate microclimate safety.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTE
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

http://popularizacija.ifs.hr/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/LaserLab_NL_07-2018_web.pdf

Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI) is a non-destructive optical technique which can be used to investigate deformation, deterioration and fracture mechanisms in cultural heritage objects. In the context of the European IPERION CH MOLAB project, Laserlab-Europe partner IESL-FORTH has developed DHSPI-II, a portable custom-made prototype, which has already been used to monitor wooden objects and to examine 17th century paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London. In DHSPI two coherent beams from the same laser form a holographic interferogram of the speckle patterns – spatial variations in the observed light intensity of the light reflected from a rough surface – on a CCD detector. A computer processes the phase changes in the reflected beam, which are caused by changes in the shape and position of the surface and the underlying material, revealing any changes in the surface as well as the internal structure. The laser beams employed in the DHSPI-II are highly divergent, allowing imaging of the whole or extended parts of the surface (full field). This also guarantees safety for the operator as well as the object, because in this power density regime the laser radiation does not interact with the surface. The technique enables detection of the location, shape and size of invisible defects, as well as their changes over time. As such, it allows monitoring of structural changes resulting from varying environmental and climatic conditions, conservation treatments, aging, and transportation or handling. The DHSPI-II instrument is a 15 kg light-weight portable system, comprising an optical head of 30x20 cm and a PC driven control unit. It has been developed at the holography laboratory of IESL-FORTH, and funded through several national and EU projects related to artworks diagnostics. In a preliminary preventive conservation experiment, DHSPI was employed to monitor in real time the response of complex materials and objects to fluctuations in relative humidity and temperature. Analysis has focused on the assessment of the dynamics of dimensional changes in cultural heritage objects made of hygroscopic materials. Oak and pine with sizes of 2 x 2 cm, and of varying thicknesses from 1 mm to 1 cm, were monitored while relative humidity was varied between 45% and 65% at different rates. The data of this work in progress suggests that wood sensors could be suitable for future assessment of environmental changes in collections. In addition, scaffold access between February and April 2018 enabled the recording of The Apotheosis of King James I and The Wise Rule of King James I, two ceiling paintings produced by Peter Paul Rubens and installed at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London in 1636. The assessment by the DHSPI-II instrument was part of a multidisciplinary effort to carry out a first ever full and systematic technical conservation survey, to determine how the paintings were created, how they have changed over the years, as well as to establish an accurate record of the present condition of the paintings to inform on approaches to future possible conservation interventions. Vivi Tornari A.Nevin, M. Andrianakis, V. Tornari, Towards understanding the impact of environmental changes on cultural heritage through the real time monitoring of dimensional change in wood sensors with Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry, to be published in Applied Surface Science List

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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The title TNA proposal: Banqueting House Whitehall Rubens Ceiling Paintings Technical Conservation Research

Project proposal acronym: RUBENS-TCR-BHW

Date of realization: MARCH 2018

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Constantina Vlachou – Mogire

Project leader institution: Historical Royal Palaces , other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable)

Field of specialization of the user group: Archaeologist - Project manager of HRP.....

General description of the TNA activity

The nine ceiling paintings painted by Peter Paul Rubens and his studio were installed at the Whitehall Banqueting House in 1636. This set of painting is one of the largest (243 m²) and most complex works by the master surviving in-situ for almost 400 years. Since their creation, the paintings have been removed at least five times and treated about nine times. These interventions included removing the canvases from their original stretchers and marouflaging them onto plywood boards at the beginning of the 20th c., cutting, removal, and evacuation of the panels during World War II a major restoration campaign after the war and two subsequent treatments. Historic Royal Palaces' current Banqueting House Whitehall conservation and re-presentation project provided a rare opportunity to carry out a first-ever full and systematic technical conservation survey of the Rubens ceiling paintings. The purpose of this scientific long-term research project is twofold: a) to understand Rubens' technique for creating these nine paintings and study their current state of preservation, b) to record evidence of previous interventions and their impact on the condition of the works today as composites of original materials with restoration structures and surface alterations.

Major results of the access

DHSPI supported the evaluation of possible delaminations between the painting canvas and the substrate layer as well as understanding the formation of cracks over the plywood panel joints.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how:

NOW – why:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The findings will help uncover details for the production of these magnificent paintings and provide scientific evidence on the current condition and stability of the paint layers and the coatings which is

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

paramount to the planning of any future conservation campaign. It is anticipated that the outcomes of this research will be widely communicated through conference presentations, academic peer-reviewed papers, online platforms, and the press.

DHSPI-SIRT ceiling facing OVH setup and image with example of deformation

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Examination of 17th century paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London with OCT – MOLAB 2018

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links
it was a note at NCU web site

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Rubens Technical Conservation Research, Banqueting House Whitehall

Project proposal acronym: RUBENS TCR BHW

Date of realization: 12-17.03.2018 – OCT; ...

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Constantina Vlachou-Mogire

Project leader institution: Historic Royal Palaces Conservation and Collections Care Department, Hampton Court Palace, Surrey KT8 9AU, UK

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Field of specialization of the user group: scientists & conservators

General description of the TNA activity

The OCT intervention was aimed at:

1. to identify thickness and structure of varnishes, detect delaminations and retouchings/overpaintings of former restorations campaigns

This action can be considered as a “success story” because of the importance of the object and results leading to 2 articles (one submitted to Studies in Conservation after presentation at LACONA 12 conference and one general (all groups) in preparation for Microchemical Journal).

Major results of the access

1. oral presentation at LACONA 12 conference: “Non-invasive survey of pre-restoration condition of the ceiling paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Banqueting House Whitehall, London, by means of Optical Coherence Tomography” by Magdalena Iwanicka, Constantina Vlachou-Mogire, Lucia Pereira-Pardo, Marcin Sylwestrzak, Piotr Targowski
2. paper submitted to Studies in Conservation: “Non-invasive survey of pre-restoration condition of the two ceiling paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Banqueting House Whitehall, London, by means of Optical Coherence Tomography” by Magdalena Iwanicka, Constantina Vlachou-Mogire, Lucia Pereira-Pardo, Marcin Sylwestrzak, Magdalena Kowalska, Piotr Targowski
3. planned oral presentation at TECHNART 2019: “Banqueting House Whitehall Rubens ceiling paintings non-invasive analysis” by Constantina Vlachou-Mogire et al, further for publication in Microchemical Journal

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? ...not known to us..

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: participation in the writing and editing of publications

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

“Historic Royal Palaces’ current Banqueting House Whitehall conservation and re-presentation project provided a rare opportunity to carry out a first ever full and systematic technical conservation survey to determine how the paintings were created, how they have changed over the years and establish an accurate record of the present condition of the paintings to inform on approaches to future possible conservation interventions. Scaffold access between February and April 2018 enabled among other activities the present technical survey, conducted with MOLAB portable in-situ multitechnique trans-national access service under the H2020 IPERION CH project.” C V-M

Examination of *The Apotheosis of James I* with OCT at Banqueting House Whitehall, London from the left: Lucia Pereira-Pardo, Historic Royal Palaces Conservation and Collections Care Department UK; Magdalena Iwanicka, N. Copernicus Univ. Torun, PL; © P. Targowski

Transportation of the OCT instrument to the working site on scaffolds, Banqueting House Whitehall, London, © P. Targowski

Examination of “The vase with Sunflowers” by Vincent Van Gogh in the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam with OCT – MOLAB 2016

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

a film was shot by the team appointed by the Van Gogh Museum – the result is unknown for me – contact please the Museum

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Piotr

surname: Targowski

institution: N. Copernicus University, Torun, PL

e-mail: ptarg@fizyka.umk.pl contact phone: + 48 56 611 3206

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal:

Systematic investigation of ‘Sunflowers’ by Vincent van Gogh: focus on the alteration of chrome yellow paints mixed with other pigments

Project proposal acronym: SUNMIX

Date of realization: 7-13.03.2106

Information about the user:

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Project leader name: Koen Janssens

Project leader institution: University of Antwerp , other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam

Field of specialization of the user group: scientists & conservators

General description of the TNA activity

The intervention was aimed at two targets:

2. to identify the type of chrome yellow and their association with other pigments in different parts of the painting
3. to identify varnishes used and to carry out cleaning tests for the varnish removal and to monitor these via a combination of mid- and near-FITR measurements and OCT. Since, both the presence of synthetic and natural resin-based varnishes are suspected to be present, this will be helpful to determine the appropriate protocol/sequence of removal steps.

This action can be considered as a “success story” because of the importance of the object and results leading to a book (in preparation).

Major results of the access

A book will be published in 2019 comprising major results of this intervention. As for the varnishes it was possible to identify the structure and composition of coatings.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? ...not known to us..

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: participation in the writing and editing of the book

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The book, comprising the results of the action is a common effort of van Gogh Museum, University of Amsterdam, Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands. National Gallery in London, University of Perugia, CNR Italy, University of Antwerp, N. Copernicus University in Torun. It will summarise the state of the knowledge of the structure of the painting and a state of preservation.

Van Gogh’s Sunflowers illuminated: Art meets Science (provisional title)

Tentative Table of contents:

1. Introduction
2. The Sunflowers in Art Historical Context
3. Technical investigation of the Sunflowers in the National Gallery, London (the first study)
4. Van Gogh’s Materials and Working Methods
5. Colour Changes and Chemical Alteration: a Focus on Chrome Yellows and Geranium Lake
6. Conservation: from Past to Future
7. Surface Layers
8. Techniques of Examination and Analyses

Examination of *Vase with Sunflowers* with OCT at Van Gogh Museum, from the left: prof. Ella Hendrix, Univ. of Amsterdam, dr Magdalena Iwanicka, n. Copernicus Univ. Torun, PL, © P. Targowski

Examination of “Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen” and “View of the sea at Scheveningen” by Vincent van Gogh in the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam with OCT – MOLAB 2018

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

a Polish national Tv network TVN produced an interview with NCU team on OCT including this intervention:

<https://dziendobry.tvn.pl/wideo,2064,n/arcydziela-sztuki-pod-lupa-polskich-konserwatorow,277526.html> emitted nationwide Oct. 28, 2018

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Piotr

surname: Targowski

institution: N. Copernicus University, Torun, PL

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TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Van Gogh Returns

Project proposal acronym: VGR

Date of realization: 13-18.05.2018 NCU;

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Kathrin Pilz

Project leader institution: Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam

Field of specialization of the user group: scientists & conservators

General description of the TNA activity

The intervention was aimed at examination of varnishes and patinas prior to conservation incl. tests of removal

This action can be considered as a “success story” because of the importance of the object and interesting story behind: both pictures were stolen from VGM in 2002 retrieved by Italian Guardia di Finanza from mafia in Napoli in 2016 and returned to VGM

Major results of the access

Reports given the museum, potential for a publication - tbd

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? ...not known to us..

- did the user participate in the dissemination of the results?

YES –

NO – why: no time for interaction yet but possible common publication in the future .

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Results of MOLAB intervention were used for planning of restoration

Detailed OCT results for *View of the sea at Scheveningen*

1. In most of the examined spots there are 1 layer of varnish with an overall thickness varying from ca 7 to 40 microns. In some areas two varnish layers were found on the surface .
2. Under the upper varnish layer (or layers) there is a semi-transparent/non-transparent layer of patina (the use of the term “patina” is based on the knowledge of the painting’s history).
3. A transparent layer (of up to ca 30 µm thickness) is visible in most of the OCT tomograms under the patina (in areas where the patina is thin enough to transmit IR radiation).
4. Paint layer of the signature is lying on a transparent layer (probably varnish) and not directly on the paint layer. It is probably covered with a very thin layer of an uppermost varnish.
5. Dark sharp lines visible on the surface are concave and filled with patina and upper varnish.
6. In the area of a streak resulting probably from some past dripping of solvent all the semi-transparent layers were removed and bare paint layer is exposed.
7. In the sky area no difference was found in the structure of layers between glossy and matte areas.

Detailed OCT results for *Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen*

1. In most of the examined spots, in the areas of paint dating from the first painting campaign there are 2 layers of varnish with an overall thickness varying from 10 to over 100 microns.
2. In some areas a transparent material is visible in a form of lumps either under thin paint layer or under a single layer of varnish. Moreover, on the paint dating from the first campaign, the bottom varnish tends to have a form of round-shaped isles. It was not found on top of the paint coming from the second campaign. It is therefore very probable that this brownish transparent material is in fact localised between the first and second paint.

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

3. Generally, on the paint regarded as dating from the second painting campaign the varnish is thinner, and, in most cases, there is only one layer of varnish. However, in some spots there seem to be two transparent layers on a paint regarded as coming from the second campaign.
4. In an area of sample collection two varnish layers were found (upper – thin: 10-11 μm , bottom – thick: 33-43 μm).
5. Paint protrusions are opaque to OCT radiation. In spots no. 7 and 31 protruding paint is probably not covered with varnish.
6. In result of cleaning tests the isles of bottom varnish proved to be less soluble than the upper varnish and thus were left exposed. Maps and models of the surface, derived from OCT data, show how the topography of the surface changed in result of cleaning (especially evident in spot#27).
7. A paint loss is filled with a semi-transparent material.

Examination of *View of the sea at Scheveningen* with OCT at Van Gogh Museum, from the left: Saskia Van Oudheusden, dr Kathrin Pilz – both Van Gogh Museum, dr Magdalena Iwanicka, Nicolaus Copernicus Univ. Torun, PL, © P. Targowski

Examination of *View of the sea at Scheveningen* with OCT at Van Gogh Museum, from the left: dr Magdalena Iwanicka, Nicolaus Copernicus Univ. Torun and Saskia Van Oudheusden, Van Gogh Museum, © P. Targowski

Non-invasive in situ study of the polychromy of the Pórtico de la Gloria in Santiago de Compostela Cathedral – MOLAB 2010

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

Read the following definitions before going ahead

Academic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to academic advances, across and within disciplines, including significant advances in understanding, methods, theory and application (this could be scientific, but could also be in other disciplines related to heritage science eg advances in understanding the materials and structure of an object contributing to historical research questions)

Economic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to the economy. (e.g. the commercialisation of the instrument developed)

Societal impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to society, especially to preservation of CH – e.g. by introducing a new method of conservation, adopted by the community or commonly adopted new facts (knowledge) about the object of art

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Yes

Links in document attached (2)

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Laborde Marqueze

surname: Ana

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

institution: Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España, Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte
e-mail: ana.laborde@cultura.gob.es contact phone: + 34 915504515/+34 615274885

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Scientific studies in the Pórtico de la Gloria Project, Catedral de Santiago de Compostela

Project proposal acronym:

Date of realization: June 2010

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Ana Laborde Marqueze

Project leader institution: Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España, Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte

Field of specialization of the user group: scientist, conservator

Working team of the Molab that worked in Santiago:

Costanza MILIANI researcher CNR-ISTM (scientific coordination of the project)

Brunetto Brunetti Professor Department of Chemistry

Aldo Romani researcher Department of Chemistry

Francesca Rosi Contract researcher Department of Chemistry

Chiara Anselmi researcher at contract Department of Chemistry

Anna Amat Contract researcher Department of Chemistry

Brenda Doherty CNR-ISTM contract researcher

David Buti PhD student

Paola Rocchi Laboratory Technician CNR-ISTM

e-mail: miliani@thch.unipg.it, tel.: +390755855639, fax: +390755855606.

Major results of the access

Encrustations and superficial deposits

As for the state of preservation all the porch is characterized by diffuse alterations based on plaster and oxalates that macroscopically are observed respectively as white deposition and dark patinas. Sulphates and Oxalates are always present, though not visible to the eye, in all the measuring points, even those related to deep gaps in which the supporting stone emerges.

In some points of the Pillar stature there are areas of sub-efflorescence of Calcium sulfate, visible in the images to the video microscope precisely in the phase of Rupture of the external pictorial layer for the crystallization pressure. Is believed to so that the problems of color fall in the areas of the complexion are due to the crystallization under the pictorial layer of calcium sulfate that fails to migrate

Outside because of the hydrophobicity of the lipid layer.

On the other hand the presence of diffuse gore-based chalk, show that the sulfate It also comes from water perbreakfasts on the outside surface. Of similar Origin only the calcite concretions of neo-formation, mainly present on the left side of the Porch. Finally in all the surface, with thickenings in the Pillar of the Evangelists, Chlorides are widespread, while only in many places are there also the presence of Nitrates.

Organic Binders

The outer layer of faces, attributable to the intervention of Crispin de Evelino that in 1651 he had the task of intervening on the only parts of the complexion of an unspecified number of Figures, it is made with lipid binder, white-headed, cinnabar and probably red ochre. They also observe signs of protein-type material that can also suggest the use of fat tempera even though it is not possible to

exclude successive maintenance. The pictorial layer shows the typical chippings of the binder painting and the formation of lead carboxylates, the result of the saponification reaction between the free fatty acids of the lipid binder and the basic carbonate of lead of the white. In all the statues analysed the outer layer shows, in a more or less clear depending on the state of preservation, the features discussed above.

In the statues of the Central Tympanum and Epistle Pillar present in the Incarnate more or less intense wax signals, evident not only in the S64 statue for which the protective and documented intervention (1969, San Martin and Lamas Chamoso).

FTIR reflectance spectroscopy does not allow to recognize whether it is beeswax or microcrystalline due to the presence of lipid binder. The analysis of the internal incarnate layer, probably original and visible through the gaps in the speech of Crispin de Evelino, was more difficult because of the bad state of preservation and possible contamination of the materials of the next drafting. However, it is clear that the increase in signals due to the protein component and the persistence of the biacca signals. Chalk is always present for which, however, being generally very widespread on the surface of the polychrome, it is not possible to determine whether it is original material or alteration.

A sampling of the layer of incarnate underlying the intervention of Crispin de Evelino, if analyzed with GC-MS technique or ELISA will be able to identify the nature of the protein binder and determine whether it is egg, casein or animal glue.

In many statues of the tympanum, especially in correspondence of the robes and the black lettering of the parchments, synthetic resins have been identified, corresponding to the intervention of consolidation of 1992-1993.

Metal Decorations

The Polychrome presents widespread residues of metallic decorations, the most common are those above pictorial layers at lapis lazuli in correspondence of the garments and are characterised by gold and lipid binder residues. Gold decorations were also traced in hair and beards. The particularities compared to this situation compositional are described below.

In some areas of brown color of the mantle of the statue S6 (Angel with Crown of Thorns) they are observed in XRF signals of gold and silver, suggesting the presence of a different metal decoration from previous ones. In all the points the silver is present always with gold.

The statue 159 is characterised by the presence of residues of the decoration technique at Brocade applied. In These areas we observe the presence of high levels of wax, residues of gold and tin, traces of lapis lazuli and lipid material. (follow the attached document) *To be continued in attached document (1)*

Policromia

Red-All The red Crosshatches analysed highlighted the presence of mercury

To the XRF analysis, identification for the use of cinnabar. The same pigment, mixed with wax,

It was used to realize the blood in the side and in the stigmata of Christ

Pantokrator. UV-vis fluorescence Measures allowed to exclude the presence of

Residues of red lacquers, in all the points analysed. The Available Techniques do not

They allow the identification of lead oxides in the presence of white, so if you

Want to check for the presence of minium, litharge or massive, we recommend performing analysis

Micro-Raman or XRD. Finally, there are widespread residues of the intervention of

Painted with ochre of red colour which is rich in iron oxides and Kaolin.

Yellow-There are widespread residues of the repainting carried out with

Yellow ochre which is rich in iron oxides and kaolin. Possible

Evidences of a yellow lead and tin have emerged in the vegetation-type decorations of the

Evangelist Pillar.

Blue-All well-preserved blue and vivid color (for example see the robe of S8-

Angel holding the column) are made up of lapis lazuli and Biacca. Traces of

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Natural overseas are often found in correspondence of the decorations in gold. ALL Blue of Green color are based on blue and white, see for example the Residues of color in the robe of the Pantocrator. It would be interesting to understand the succession of the interventions to azurite and lapis lazuli, which is the pigment used in Polychromatic original Romanic?

It is suggested that the execution of a section Stratigraphic at the Evangelist statue Pillar S161. In the mantle of this Statue The Azurite is predominant in the clearest and innermost areas of the mantle folds, While the lapis lazuli in darker areas. This recurrence suggests the presence of two distinct interventions rather than the use of azurite as a preparatory layer of Lapis lazuli.

Blacks--The blacks of the pupils were analyzed with systematicity, obtaining in the most Part of the cases indications of the use of black smoke with the prevalence of protein binder. Exceptions Are Some statues of the central Gable, in the lower part (S2-St. Mark, S3-Saint Luke, S6-Angel with crown of thorns, S7-Two Angels, S11-Angel with nails and Which have high levels of copper. In Addition, the statue S13-Angel with whips Where organic black is black with protein-binding bones.

Changes in Polychrome

Many areas of the polychrome of the Portico have evident alterations of green color That showed a different nature to the non-invasive analysis.

The Capitals 53, 54, 55 (Gospel Pillar) are characterised by a severe alteration of Green color affecting both areas representing vegetation and robes Men. Surfaces are strongly altered in the morphology to suggest That the green material is largely the result of a crystallization process Secondary. The XRF analyses highlighted the presence of high levels of copper and Chlorine, suggesting that the green alteration is made up of copper chlorides type Atacamite/Paratacamite. The FTIR analyses highlighted the presence of high Quantities of nitrates, oxalates and sulphates, which may also have contributed to degradation.

So the original pigment that underwent the alteration had to be copper-based. The FTIR analyses have highlighted in many places both the vegetation and the robes Presence of residues of azurite, which is evidently the original pigment that has undergone The alteration.

The colour of the vegetation, which was to be green, was most likely obtained By mixing bludrite with a yellow lead and tin, since in the altered areas of Vegetation Elemental Analysis XRF evidence the presence, abnormal and not found in Other areas, of tin.

The analysis of a micro-sample taken from the green alteration of the vegetation with Raman technique and/or XRD could confirm the nature of the secondary phases and the Composition of the original pigments.

Many areas of the porch showing blue green coloration have traces of High levels of copper to indicate that the process of degradation is also in these cases the formation of copper chlorides resulting from the interaction of chloride ions conveyed From the water with the azurite.

The Green alteration of the complexion of the statue S5 (St. Matthew), in the upper part of the Portico has a different composition and difficult to explain. In fact it is

The green of the complexion is that of the gap in the forehead have high tenors of Chromium and kaolin. The analyses therefore show that green is traceable to a Non-original pigment made from chromium and kaolin, due to an intervention Datable to the NINETEENTH century.

It is unclear why the intervention affects both the gap and the The complexion. Chromium-based Greens were also found in the gaps in the complexion

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Of the right hand of the Pantocrator. A stratigraphic analysis of the complexion in the areas of Green coloration of the S5 statue, the SEM and micro-Raman could clarify the Distribution and nature of the chromium-based pigment.

General description of the TNA activity

The MOLAB Laboratory of the Department of Chemistry of the University of Perugia (Centre of Excellence SMAArt) and the CNR-ISTM of Perugia (Institute of Science and Technology) carried out the non-invasive study of polychrome and the phases of alteration of the Pórtico de la Gloria. Were employed the following analytical techniques: Elementary X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis, Molecular analysis in mid-infrared reflectance (FTIR), molecular analysis in UV-vis fluorescence, colorimetric analysis, image analysis to the video microscope.

The statues and the specific areas to be analyzed were chosen in the first instance on the basis and Indications of the restorers responsible for the yard, and then proceed on the basis of the analytical results acquired at the moment, always taking into account the accessibility of the chosen areas and acquiring in total more than 500 measuring points.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? Very satisfied

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how:Conferences and Seminars, Publications.....

NOW – why:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

CIRUJANO, C., LABORDE, A., PRADO-VILAR, F. “La restauración del Pórtico de la Gloria en la Catedral de Santiago”, Patrimonio Cultural de España 6, Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte, 2012, PP. 183-196.

CORTÁZAR GARCÍA DE SALAZAR, M. y SÁNCHEZ LEDESMA, A. “Estudio de la secuencia de policromías y de la composición de los materiales empleados en las decoraciones del conjunto escultórico del Pórtico de la Gloria de la Catedral de Santiago de Compostela”, Revista Informes y Trabajos, 15, pp. 114-170. Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España, 2017.

Universidad de Perugia y C.N.R. Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche MOLAB investigaciones no destructivas sobre la policromía Programa Catedral 2010

The possible intervention of Michel Sittow in the execution of the altarpiece of the Luna Chapel in Toledo Cathedral – ARCHLAB 2017

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

1. **Retórica artística en el tardogótico castellano**, Olga Pérez Monzón, Matilde Miquel Juan, María Martín Gil, eds., Sílex Ediciones, Madrid, España, 2018. ISBN: 9788477379614

2. **Michel Sittow. Estonian Painter at the Courts of Renaissance Europe (Exh. Cat. National Gallery , Washington, DC, Jan.28-May 13, 2018)** by John Oliver Hand and Greta Koppel, eds. Washington DC: National Gallery ; New Haven: Yale University Press.128 pp, 90 illus. ISBN 978-0-300-23286-8.

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: María

surname: Martín Gil

institution: Spanish Cultural Heritage Institute

e-mail: maria.martingil@cultura.gob.es contact phone: + 34 91 550 45 38

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: The possible intervention of Michel Sittow in the execution of the altarpiece of the Luna Chapel in Toledo Cathedral.

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Project proposal acronym: SITTOW-LUNA.

Date of realization: 20-24 of February, 2017.

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Matthias Ulrich Weniger

Project leader institution: Bayerisches Nationalmuseum / Ludwig Maximilian Universität, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable)

Field of specialization of the user group: Curator / Lecturer

General description of the TNA activity

The activity was focused on accessing to the results of the funded research project: FORMACIÓN DEL PINTOR Y PRÁCTICA DE LA PINTURA EN ESPAÑA. (1350-1500). EL RETABLO DE ALVARO DE LUNA EN LA CAPILLA DE SANTIAGO DE LA CATEDRAL DE TOLEDO. (HAR2012- 32720). IPCE, UCM, UCLM and the Museo del Prado, participated actively in the project under the leadership of Matilde Miquel (UCM).and examined over the last years the large altarpiece in the Saint James chapel of the cathedral of Toledo with highly advanced analytical methods.

The altarpiece was commissioned on 21 December 1488 by María de Luna y Pimentel (ca. 1432-1502) for the chapel that contained the graves of her father don Álvaro de Luna (ca. 1390-1453) and of her mother Juana de Pimentel, who died in 1488. Before falling into disgrace, Álvaro de Luna had been the most powerful figure at the court of Isabel's father, King John II of Castile. The painters charged in the contract for the execution of the work were Sancho de Zamora and Juan de Segovia. The above mentioned project came to the conclusion that beside these two “Hispano-Flemish” masters, at least one further and blatantly more « Northern » artist must have been involved. It has tentatively proposed that this third artist might have been Michel Sittow. This view was shared by the user when both parties came together with the occasion of a symposium in Toledo and Madrid, in April 2016, and motivated the access. His contribution to the Toledo altarpiece is of pivotal importance for a better understanding of the early stages of the career of Michel Sittow who was to become the best paid artist in the court of Isabel la Católica.

The study of the X-ray and IRR analysis and not least of the excellent High Res photographs established by IPCE during the project was fundamental for understanding the complex relationship within the artists working together on the Luna altarpiece.

Major results of the access

The ARCHLAB visit meant a unique occasion to fully concentrate on the above mentioned questions during five very long and intensive days, without the heavy workload and the distractions of the usual routine at each of the participants working place.

The week was devoted mainly on looking together on the images and analysis elaborated by the IPCE on the Toledo altarpiece, and by the user on the other works by Sittow, and by comparing these data. The main interlocutor of the user in this was Carmen Vega Martín, a technician with admirable expertise in studying paintings with X-ray and infrared technology. These discussions were complimented by an exchange with the other specialists involved in the project, in particular with Matilde Miquel Juan, Olga Pérez Monzón, Tomás Antelo, as well as with Marisa Gómez González and Rocío Bruquetas Galán, who have done an important work analyzing the pigments used to paint the Toledo altarpiece.

The discussions with Carmen Vega and the user were extraordinarily detailed and marked by a remarkable openness on both sides to share all available documents and information, and to

advance as much as possibly in resolving the enigmas involved with the Toledo altarpiece.

As a result of these long discussions and of an openness and cooperation rarely found in the academic world, the results of the project “FORMACIÓN DEL PINTOR Y PRÁCTICA DE LA PINTURA EN LOS REINOS HISPANOS” establishing that Sittow indeed took part in the execution of the Toledo altarpiece could be confirmed. The appearance of the four central panels of the altarpiece, displaying saints Catharine and Magdalene as well as both Saint John, cannot be explained without a knowledge of his style.

However, based on the detailed results of the above project, there has also been consensus that one observes striking differences in the execution of these four panels, and that they were definitely not painted entirely by one single hand. This refers in particular to garments and brocades. The underdrawing does not seem to be homogeneous either. In addition, we also agreed that the painter of the outer four panels, the so-called Master of Miraflores, took up some of the innovations present in the inner panels.

Another interesting point in the results of the accessed project is that this by its turn implies that three or possibly even more artists seem to have worked together on the altarpiece at the same moment, and not one after the other. In addition, the central panels can not have been added at a later stage since the Master of Miraflores reacts already to Sittow.

This in turn evokes the question of the date of Sittow’s appearance in Spain. He is documented in Isabel’s service from 1492 onwards, while the contract of 1488 stipulated that the altarpiece should have been completed within a year. We know many cases in which the completion of an altarpiece took much longer than originally planned, but in this case there are no clear hints that the Toledo work was only executed after 1492. This leads to ask under which circumstances Sittow had come to Spain, and whether he was hired first by the Mendoza before entering the service of queen Isabel. María de Luna y Pimentel was married in 1460 to Íñigo López de Mendoza. Íñigo’s uncle was the “great cardinal” Pedro de Mendoza, head of Toledo cathedral and the most important counsellor of the queen, which means that both families were linked so closely that the distinction is only of limited relevance. Whatever the exact conditions of patronage, the altarpiece itself makes it clear that Sittow, once he appeared on the stage, was considered to be the most important artist involved in its execution. He was awarded the central panels, including those depicting both Saints John, the favourite saints of queen Isabel, and his innovations were adapted by the “Master of Miraflores”. Already the contract had asked for “foreign”, i.e. Netherlandish faces, and Sittow was much more able to fulfill these expectations than the two Hispano-Flemish masters.

The observations made on the Toledo altarpiece do not only raise our knowledge of cultural exchange between Spain and the Netherlands around 1490 to a new and unexpected level. They also alter our vision of the painter Sittow as well. When he contributed his share to the altarpiece, Sittow must have had come into touch already with the queen, since he quotes in his Toledo paintings art works in her possession. What is more, some features and some aspects of the painting technique that we tended to link with his later works are apparent already at that early stage, in the Toledo altarpiece.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

YES. The exchange as well as the discussions between the user and the IPCE on the exact amount of the cooperation of Sittow with the local artists will certainly continue.

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

YES – how: In 2018, the Estonian Art Museum in Sittow’s home town Tallinn and the National Gallery in Washington mounted the first monographic exhibition on Michel Sittow. In accordance with the IPCE, the user has included first results of the discussions had in Madrid in his contributions to the catalogue of that exhibition, mentioning ARCHLAB access, so that the important research done at the IPCE and the affiliated institutions will be present in that volume.

NOW – why:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

(See conclusions in Major results of the access)

HISTORIANS OF NETHERLANDISH ART REVIEWS

All Reviews Book Reviews Exhibition and Exhibition Catalogue Reviews Newsletter Archive

Michel Sittow. Estonian Painter at the Courts of Renaissance Europe. [Exh. cat. National Gallery of Art, Washington, DC, January 28 – May 13, 2018.]

By John Oliver Hand and Greta Koppel, eds.

Washington, DC: National Gallery of Art; New Haven: Yale University Press. 128 pp, 90 illus. ISBN 978-0-300-23286-8.

Review published July 2018

This recent Washington exhibition, jointly organized with the Art Museum of Estonia and its curator Greta Koppel, offers a fitting moment to pay tribute to John Hand, its long-time curator (since 1973) of early Northern Renaissance paintings at the National Gallery and a stalwart presence in both HNA and CODART. Hand has authored important catalogues of the Gallery’s permanent collection of both Netherlandish (1986; with Martha Wolff) and German pictures (1993) as well as the foundational monograph on Joos van Cleve (2002).

Retórica artística en el tardogótico castellano

Olga Pérez Monzón, Matilde Miquel Juan, María Martín Gil, eds.

Sílex Ediciones, Madrid, España, 2018.

ISBN: 9788477379614

Conservation and Revelation of the Ghent Altarpiece – ARCHLAB 2012

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The rediscovery of Jan van Eyck, ' King of Painters'

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Several press releases and conferences have been organised in the framework of the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece:

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PersberichtGhentAltarpiece_EN_V2.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PressRelease_KIK-IRPA_GhentAltarpiece_27June2013.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2014.06.20_Press_kit_Ghent_Altarpiece.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/12-10-2016_Press_Lam_Gods.pdf

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Persbericht%20Lam%20Gods%209%20nov%202017%20EN.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Dossier%20de%20presse%20Jan%20van%20Eyck%20en%20lign e%202011%20jan%202018.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2018.06.19%20Press%20kit%20Ghent%20Altarpiece%20EN.pdf>

The website [closetovaneyck www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be](http://www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be), launched in 2011 and regularly updated, is a pioneering example of open-access resources for technical art history and conservation. This has also been echoed in the press.

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Ghent%20Altarpiece%20-%20Web%20site%20-%20Press%20rel ease%20-%20July%207%202011%20-%20EN.pdf>

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/GhentAltarpiecewebsite_PressRelease.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The website “closer to van Eyck” (<http://closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be>) is financially supported by the

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Getty Foundation. It is a pioneering tool in the presentation of conservation-restoration process and a model for open access. The conservation is financed by the Flemish government (80%) and the Baillet-Latout Fund (20%). Research for conservation is carried out by KIK-IRPA in collaboration with the Universities of Ghent and Antwerp and has benefitted from sponsorship from the Gieskes-Strijbis Fund. Punctual analytical expertise have been provided by scientists from the Nicolaus Copernicus University (Toruń) and the National Gallery (Washington).

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Hélène

surname: Dubois

institution: KIK-IRPA

e-mail: helene.dubois@kikirpa.be contact phone: +

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: ARCHLAB “Van Eyck reconstructed”

Project proposal acronym:

Date of realization: May-June 2012

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Marie Postec

Project leader institution: ENSAV-La Cambre, Brussels

Other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable): Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage, Brussels

Field of specialization of the user group: conservators and art historians

General description of the TNA activity

This ARCHLAB project aimed to collate existing scientific imagery, laboratory analyses and conservation reports of paintings by Jan Van Eyck and followers in the participating institutions (National Gallery, C2RMF, Prado). The main questions were to gain more insight into the painting technique of Van Eyck and on the material condition of his paintings

This information participated in the preparation of the conservation project of the brothers van Eyck’s Ghent Altarpiece by the KIK-IRPA and of teaching material for the reconstruction of Early Netherlandish painting Techniques (Conservation training, ENSAV-La Cambre).

The conservation project of the Ghent Altarpiece (1432) is the most revealing campaigns carried out so far this century since it permitted the rediscovery of the original paint layers that had been hidden under overpaint since the middle of the sixteenth century. It has an enormous impact on the reevaluation of the Van Eyck’s artistic production which was an optical revolution at the time, and to increase knowledge of his materials and of degradation phenomena that affect the paintings.

The study of the technique enabled the elaboration of insightful and didactic teaching materials to supervise the reconstruction of Old Masters techniques by conservation students at ENSAV-La Cambre

Major results of the access

Teaching on historical painting techniques and contribution to research on the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece

Publications (selection):

Ute Stehr, Hélène Dubois, 'Über die Spaltung und die Restaurierungsgeschichte der sechs Flügel des Genter Altares in Berlin', in Stephan Kemperdick, Johannes Rößler (ed.), *Der Genter Altar der Brüder van Eyck. Geschichte und Würdigung*, Michael Imhof Verlag, Berlin, 2014, pp. 120-135.

Marie Postec, Hélène Dubois, Bart Devolder, Livia Depuydt, Nathalie Laquière, Françoise Rosier, Koen Jansens, Geert Van der Snickt, Jana Sanyova, Maximiliaan Martens and Peter Vandenabeele, 'Spectaculaire ontdekkingen op het Lam Gods van de gebroeders Van Eyck: de essentiële rol van de restaurateur', Marjan Buyle (ed.), *Achtste BRK-APROA/Onroerend Erfgoed colloquium: Innovatie in de conservatie-restauratie*, VIOE, Brussels, 12-13 November 2015, Brussels, 2016, pp.153-171.

A.van Grevenstein-Kruse, H. Dubois, 'The Ghent altarpiece revisited: 2012-2017', in C. Currie, B. Fransen, V. Henderiks, C. Stroo, D. Vanwijnsberghe (ed.), *Van Eyck Studies. Papers presented at the Eighteenth symposium for the Study of Underdrawing and Technology in Paintings*, Brussels, 19-21 September 2012, Leuven, Peeters, 2016, pp. 3-34

H. Dubois, J. Sanyova, D. Vanwijnsberghe 'Revenons à notre Mouton'. Paul Coremans, Erwin Panofsky, Martin Davies and the Mystic Lamb, in C. Currie, B. Fransen, V. Henderiks, C. Stroo, D. Vanwijnsberghe (ed.), *Van Eyck Studies, Papers presented at the Eighteenth symposium for the Study of Underdrawing and Technology in Paintings*, Brussels, 19-21 September 2012 Leuven, Peeters, 2016, pp. 67-76.

H. Dubois, 'Michiel Coxcie's copy as a formal reference of the material condition of the Ghent altarpiece in 1557' *Internationales Colloquium anlässlich der Ausstellung Der Genter Altar der Brüder van Eyck in Berlin 1820-1920: Der Genter Altar – Reproduktionen, Deutungen, Forschungskontroversen. The Ghent Altarpiece – Reproductions, Interpretations, Scholarly Debates*, Berlin, Gemäldegalerie, 13-14 February 2015.

H. Dubois, 'The Art of Conservation XV: The conservation history of the Ghent Altarpiece', in: *The Burlington Magazine*, September 2018, pp. 754-765.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? ...

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: author of publications, lectures in universities and conferences, conservation of the altarpiece

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

ARCHLAB is a particularly interesting TNA because it offers the opportunity to researchers to access non-published research material in a very efficient manner by providing direct access and discussing the context of this documentation with the colleagues on-site. The scientific community benefits from the improvement of the communication between research groups from different European countries, thereby stimulating collaborations. It gives the possibility to reprocess information that may have become dormant in archive by applying new analytical methods to old samples and documents.

The potential users are researchers in conservation, conservation scientists, art history, whether students, young or established professionals. They will influence the field by developing collaboration and research and disseminating through publications, presentations, research and conservation projects, teaching.

ARCHLAB gives also the financial and logistic support to research on heritage often runs on limited

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

budget. Since scientific research for conservation projects is rarely sufficiently funded, the TNA projects are a rare opportunity to gather information and stimulate collaborations to enhance the scientific support of conservation.

The potential users are art historians, conservators, conservation scientists and students (research mappers, master thesis and dissertations).

How to look inside a sealed Egyptian pottery using neutrons – FIXLAB 2013

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. **May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:**

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. **Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO**

7. **Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.**

8. **Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)**

name: Zsolt

surname: Kasztovszky

institution: Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences / Budapest Neutron Centre

e-mail: kasztovszky.zsolt@energia.mta.hu contact phone: +36-1-3922222 / 3143.....

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Investigation of a XVIIIth Dynasty Egyptian sealed Pottery by cold Neutron TOMOgraphy

Project proposal acronym: EP-NTOMO

Date of realization: 8-11. April 2013

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Emmanuel Abraham

Project leader institution: University of Bordeaux, Laboratoire Ondes et Matière d'Aquitaine, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) Museum of Aquitaine

Field of specialization of the user group: a physicist & a museum curator

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

General description of the TNA activity

The project was aimed to probe a sealed Egyptian pottery (15th c. B.C., Museum of Aquitaine, Bordeaux) at the Budapest Neutron Centre using the Neutron Induced Prompt Gamma Spectrometer (NIPS), equipped with “NORMA” neutron radiography and tomography system. Previous investigations (X-ray and Terahertz radiation) revealed the presence of an unidentified content inside the object. The main objectives of the present project are: (a) analysis of the jar itself using neutron tomography (presence of cracks, composition of the seal) and (b) analysis of the content using neutron tomography and Neutron Induced Prompt gamma Spectroscopy (NIPS).

Major results of the access

The main result was the precise identification of the cork stopper hidden by a clay cork. 3D neutron imaging clearly revealed that this stopper was made of a ball of linen or any other string-like organic material. This observation was not possible with both X-rays and THz radiation owing to insufficient spatial resolution and contrast. Neutron imaging also confirmed the presence of cracks in the wall of the pottery bottle, as already discovered with X-rays. 3D neutron imaging also provides some representations of the mobile content which is constituted of inhomogeneous dried materials. By semi-quantitative analysis of the (n, γ) spectra taken at NIPS, we concluded that the jar content is mainly composed of H, C, N, S and Cl elements, which supports the assumption about its organic nature. Without certitude, we can assume that this content could consist of germinated seeds of any other dried organic material.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

.....

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: The user and the team of instrument scientists have prepared a scientific paper and a conference presentation about the results of the experiments.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Our attention has been focused on an Eighteenth Dynasty Egyptian sealed pottery stored at the Museum of Aquitaine (Bordeaux, France). We pointed out that the main advantage of THz radiation is the possibility of rapid and rather cheap on site non-destructive and non-invasive diagnosis, even if it is limited by a millimeter spatial resolution. This first investigation brings out very interesting elements leading the curators to go further into the analysis with more complex and expensive experimental techniques. X-rays revealed the presence of many cracks and damages, thus giving more information for the curators about the conservation state of the pottery. X-rays also provide a clearer representation of the content and the presence of an internal cork with lighter density compared to clay. Finally, neutron imaging informed about the way the object has been closed by a double stopper (clay and probably a ball of linen or any other string-like organic material) and provided a more accurate representation of the mobile and heterogeneous content, probably constituted of germinated seeds. These partial conclusions emphasize the complementarity and specificity of THz, X-ray and neutron imaging that may be of a prime importance for historians and museum curators in order to enlarge the understanding of our cultural heritage.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 1: Photograph of the Egyptian pottery (Museum of Aquitaine, inv. nr 8608)

Fig. 2: Neutron Radiography at NIPS-NORMA station.

Fig 3: Neutron tomography at the NIPS-NORMA station. 3D representation of the cork

Reference: E. Abraham, M. Bessou, A. Ziéglé, M.-C. Hervé, L. Szentmiklósi, Zs. Kasztovszky, Z. Kis, M. Menu, Terahertz, X-ray and neutron computed tomography of an Eighteenth Dynasty Egyptian sealed pottery, *Appl. Phys. A* (2014) 963-972. DOI 10.1007/s00339-014-8779-3

Archaeometallurgical Investigation of the Chiaravalle Cross – FIXLAB 2016

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

other disciplines related to heritage science e.g. advances in understanding the materials and structure of an object contributing to historical research questions)

5. **May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:**

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. **Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO**

7. **Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.**

8. **Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)**

name: Zsolt

surname: Kasztovszky

institution: Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences / Budapest Neutron Centre

e-mail: kasztovszky.zsolt@energia.mta.hu contact phone: +36-1-3922222 / 3143

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Search of Fingerprints in Archaeometallurgy: elemental composition study of three gold fragments from an ancient Italian processional cross

Project proposal acronym: SOFIA

Date of realization: 11-15. April 2016

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Daniela Di Martino

Project leader institution: Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Dipartimento di Fisica, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) National Research Council

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

(CNR), Italy

Field of specialization of the user group: physicists

General description of the TNA activity

Aim of SOFIA is the study of a processional cross, coming from the abbey of Chiaravalle (close to Milan, Italy) and dated to the 13th century. The cross is of rather complex construction of rare beauty, being decorated by 985 gems and a fine gold filigree. During a recent restoration, some very small pieces of gold filigree were made available for scientific analyses. Our techniques of choice were XRF, PIXE and PGAA, in order to get information both from the surface and from the bulk of the samples. It was aimed to verify the use of amalgam technique (mix of Au and Hg) over a silver sample, and we would like to infer, from the possible presence of unusual minor/trace elements, indications on both the provenance of the metals used and the soldering technique, to help the restorers in their future work.

Major results of the access

The production and manufacturing techniques of metals involve expertise, and the study of ancient artifacts relies on interdisciplinary skills. Metalworking processes used in the production of jewelry masterpieces can, for example, give indications on the provenance of an ancient object of an unknown origin and the techniques used. In this regard, metallic samples from the Chiaravalle Cross (a beautiful processional cross with a complex structure, dating to the 13th century) have been studied, combining bulk and point measurements. Neutron-based experiments (like Prompt Gamma Activation Analysis and neutron diffraction) provide the bulk of the elemental and mineralogical composition, while particle induced X-ray emission analyses evidenced important details on its manufacturing techniques.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response? YES:
- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?
- YES – how: The users and the team of instrument scientists have prepared scientific papers and conference presentations about the results of the experiments.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The key aspect of our research was combining powerful non-destructive techniques in a deliberately interdisciplinary way. Many data were collected, with the main goal of deriving new insights into the provenance and manufacturing technique. We could confirm the use of the amalgam technique for the gilding of the filigree over a silver twisted thread and the use of copper in the soldering.

We stress that the combination of bulk and point measurements can be very powerful. By using point measurements on the filigree, we were able to better analyze the composite structure and discriminate between inner and surface regions, while by bulk PGAA analysis we could determine the exact composition of the nail specimens.

The study of a complex masterpiece like the Chiaravalle Cross has really benefited from the knowledge exchange among experts in archaeometry, materials science, geology, physics, chemistry, cultural heritage and art history. At the end, the results will foster the restoration work to be done in the future.

Figure 1. A picture of the artifact and of the investigated specimens: (a) Front of the Chiaravalle cross and (b) filigrees and nails specimens (photograph credit: Franco Blumer).

Reference: D Di Martino, E P Cippo, A Scherillo, Zs Kasztovszky, I Harsányi, I Kovács, Z Szőkefalvi-Nagy, R Cattaneo, G Gorini, An Archaeometallurgical Investigation on Metal Samples from the Chiaravalle Cross, *Heritage* 2019, 2, 836-847; doi:10.3390/heritage2010055

Non-invasive PGAA, PIXE and ToF-ND analyses on Hungarian Bronze Age defensive armour – FIXLAB 2012

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)

name: Zsolt

surname: Kasztovszky

institution: Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences / Budapest Neutron Centre

e-mail: kasztovszky.zsolt@energia.mta.hu

contact phone: +36-1-3922222 / 3143...

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Analyses of Hungarian Armour of the Bronze Age: Alloy Composition and Texture

Project proposal acronym: AHAB-ACT

Date of realization: 2012

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Marianne Mödlinger

Project leader institution: Dipartimento di Chimica e Chimica Industriale - DCCI

Università degli Studi di Genova, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable)

.....

Field of specialization of the user group: archaeologist

General description of the TNA activity

Non-invasive, archaeometric analyses on selected Hungarian Bronze Age defensive armour is presented here: three greaves, three helmets two shields as well as one vessel fragment were analysed with PIXE, PGAA and TOF-ND. The detected alloy elemental and phase composition as well as its intergranular or spatial concentration distribution reveals important insights into the alloys used and the manufacturing techniques applied c. 1200–950 BC, and allows to reconstruct the production techniques used during the Late Bronze Age.

Major results of the access

Marianne Mödlinger, Zsolt Kasztovszky, Zoltán Kis, Boglárka Maróti, Imre Kovács, Zoltán Szőkefalvi-Nagy, György Káli, Eszter Horváth, Zsombor Sánta, Ziad El Morr: Non-invasive PGAA, PIXE and ToF-ND analyses on Hungarian Bronze Age defensive armour, *Journal of Radioanalytical Nuclear Chemistry* 300 (2014), 787-799. DOI 10.1007/s10967-014-3064-7

From the total number of eight Bronze Age pieces of armour and one vessel fragment dated to c. 1300–1000 BC from modern-day Hungary, testing on the alloys used and manufacture techniques applied were carried out. The focus was only on alloying elements such as Cu, Sn and Pb, which could have been chosen intentionally by the Bronze Age craftsmen. The finds were analysed with PIXE, PGAA and TOF-ND. All objects analysed were made of binary CuSn or ternary CuSnPb alloys with an amount of 6.4–16.7 wt% Sn and up to c. 3 wt% Pb. The wires of the two greaves, as well as a rivet from the vessel were made of almost pure Cu. Since these parts of the armour have to be rather flexible, the usage of almost pure Cu comes as no surprise. Even though the single analytical methods show a certain variation according to their different sensitivities and nature (bulk vs. surface analyses). They clearly show that Pb was used as an alloying element in the objects dated to between 1050 and 950 BC. This has also been noted for the older vessel — for its period, this is not such a common choice of alloy. For the knobs of the helmets studied, the TOF-ND agreed with previously published metallographic analyses of knobs of similar helmets. The knobs from the helmets from two sites were directly cast on the cap using the lost-wax technique, as macroscopic studies and metallographic analyses of contemporary helmets of the same type indicate. From a purely archaeological point of view, the TOF-ND results on the two shield fragments are the most interesting: until now, it was assumed that the fragments belonged to one shield only. Instead, the TOF-ND results showed that the fragments belonged to two different shields. Since a total number of less than 95 Bronze Age shields is currently known, this result is particularly valuable for Bronze Age research.

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: Scientific publication (listed above)

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The main goal of our research was combining powerful non-destructive bulk and surface analysis techniques in a deliberately interdisciplinary way. Many data were collected, with the main goal of deriving new insights into the manufacturing technique of bronze age defensive armour from Hungary.

Based on our analysis it was possible to distinguish that the earlier objects (1300–1050) were made of binary CuSn alloy, while in the later period (1050–950) Pb was also added as an alloying element. Some parts (wires of the greaves, rivet of the vessel), however, were made of almost pure Cu, and since these parts of the armour have to be rather flexible, the usage of almost pure Cu comes as no surprise. For the knobs of the helmets studied, the TOF-ND agreed with previously published metallographic analyses of knobs of similar helmets. The knobs from the helmets from two sites were directly cast on the cap using the lost-wax technique. Furthermore, the TOF-ND results of two shield fragments had been supposed to belong to one shield proved that they belong to different objects. Since a total number of less than 95 Bronze Age shields is currently known, this result is particularly valuable for Bronze Age research.

The project improved the knowledge of development, manufacture and usage of the first metal defensive armour in the European Bronze Age, and as weapons design often applies the most advanced technologies a society has to offer, they can therefore be used as an indicator of the scientific, technical and sociocultural complexity of a society or culture

Fig. 1 Hungarian Bronze Age armour studied. 1 Hajdúböszörmény. 2 Mezőkövesd. 3 Nagytétény. 4 Lengyeltóti. 5 Rinyaszentkirály. 6 Várvölgy. 7 Keszőhidegkút. 8 Bodrogkeresztúr. 9 Jászkarajenő

Fig. 2 Radiography images of the knobs of the helmets from Hajdúböszörmény (right) and Mezőkövesd (left). Lighter areas of the radiography indicate higher neutron attenuation. The knobs are both c. 3.5 cm wide

Fig. 3 Traces of manufacture and use on greaves. Left Rinyaszentkirály, Hungary. The holes to fix the crack were punched from the inside to the outside (above). Scribed lines were applied on the inside of the greaves. These were used as guidance for the application of the actual, punched decoration (below). Right Lengyeltóti, Hungary. Crack with two rivet holes punched from the inside to the outside (above) and vice versa (below)

Meteoritic origin of mankind’s earliest iron artefacts – FIXLAB 2011

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The earliest known iron artefacts, a set of small beads dated to ca. 3300 BC, were unearthed in a predynastic cemetery in Lower Egypt. Predating the invention of bloomery smelting by nearly two millennia, the nature and origin of this iron material have remained a matter of dispute ever since the excavation in 1911. Our interdisciplinary investigation has provided unambiguous results about the meteoritic origin and the manufacture of three items and about their significance for the history of iron working development. The experimental study of the beads was performed by complementary neutron and proton beam techniques at the institutes of BNC-WIGNER.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

National Geographic

<https://news.nationalgeographic.com/news/2013/13/130822-ancient-egypt-beads-meteorites-iron-g-erzeh/>

Popular Science

<https://www.popsci.com/science/article/2013-08/confirmed-egyptian-jewelry-came-meteorites#page-2>

Science News

<http://www.sci-news.com/archaeology/science-egyptian-artifacts-meteoritic-iron-01323.html>

The Telegraph

<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/science/science-news/10252529/Ancient-Egyptians-made-jewellery-from-meteorites.html>

Times Live

<https://www.timeslive.co.za/news/sci-tech/2013-08-20-earliest-iron-artifacts-made-from-meteorite-archaeologists/>

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Los Angeles Times

<https://www.latimes.com/science/sciencenow/la-sci-sn-egyptian-beads-meteorite-20130820-story.html>

<https://www.livescience.com/38995-egyptian-beads-made-from-meteorites.html>

UCL News

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/news/2013/aug/earliest-known-iron-artefacts-come-outer-space>

Science Daily

<https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2013/08/130819202413.htm>

International Business Times

<https://www.ibtimes.co.uk/ancient-egypt-jewellery-meteorite-gerzeh-tomb-500234>

The Times of India

<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/home/science/Earliest-iron-artifacts-came-from-outer-space/articleshow/21939360.cms>

UPI

<https://www.upi.com/Some-of-worlds-earliest-iron-artifacts-came-from-outer-space/35871377035528/>

Collective Evolution

<https://www.collective-evolution.com/2017/01/24/archaeologists-discover-5000-year-old-egyptian-artifacts-that-came-from-space/>

News Punch

<https://newspunch.com/archaeologists-find-5000-year-old-egyptian-artifacts-that-came-from-space/>

ABC Science

<http://www.abc.net.au/science/articles/2013/08/20/3829786.htm>

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)

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contact phone: +36-1-3922222 / 3143...

TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Mankind's earliest iron – investigating the meteoritic beads from Gerzeh, 3,500 BC

Project proposal acronym: Petrie's iron beads

Date of realization: 09-16th December 2011

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Thilo Rehren

Project leader institution: UCL Institute of Archaeology, other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) University of Pierre and Marie Curie (France), Petrie Museum of Egyptian Archaeology (UK)

Field of specialization of the user group: archaeologist, geologist, historian

General description of the TNA activity

The main research goals were:

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

- To determine the nature of the iron from which these **earliest known iron beads manufactured by men** are made – can we demonstrate that they are meteoritic in origin, as has been speculated based on their early date?
- Specifically, to determine the crystal structure of the beads (presence of schreibersite Fe₃P crystals, grain size of remaining metallic iron)
- To determine their chemical composition (particularly full body composition of nickel, cobalt, germanium), and any other related information

Major results of the access

Thilo Rehren, Tamás Belgya, Albert Jambon, György Káli, Zolt Kasztovszky, Zoltán Kis, Imre Kovács, Boglárka Maróti, Marcos Martín-Torres, Gianluca Miniacif, Vincent C. Pigott, Miljana Radivojević, László Rosta, László Szentmiklósi & Zoltán Szőkefalvi-Nagy: 5,000 years old Egyptian iron beads made from hammered meteoritic iron. *Journal of Archaeological Sciences* **40** (2013), 4785-4792.

The earliest known iron artefacts are nine small beads securely dated to circa 3200 BC, from two burials in Gerzeh, northern Egypt. We show that these beads were made from meteoritic iron, and shaped by careful hammering the metal into thin sheets before rolling them into tubes. The study demonstrates the ability of neutron and X-ray methods to determine the nature of the material even after complete corrosion of the iron metal. The iron beads were strung into a necklace together with other exotic minerals such as lapis lazuli, gold and carnelian, revealing the status of meteoritic iron as a special material on a par with precious metal and gem stones. The results confirm that already in the fourth millennium BC metalworkers had mastered the smithing of meteoritic iron, an iron–nickel alloy much harder and more brittle than the more commonly worked copper.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

.....

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: article in scientific journal, interviews for popular media (listed above).....

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The non-invasive analysis of the earliest known iron artefacts is of wider significance as it demonstrates that metalworkers had already nearly two millennia of experience to hot-work meteoritic iron when iron smelting was introduced. This knowledge was essential for the development of iron smelting, which produced metal in a solid state process and hence depended on this ability in order to replace copper and bronze as the main utilitarian metals.

Fig. 4: Photographs of three of the originally nine iron beads from Gerzeh, Lower Egypt. From left UC10738, UC10739 and UC10740. © Petrie Museum of Egyptian Archaeology. Photo by Gianluca Miniaci.

Fig. 5: Neutron images of the three iron beads, in side view (left) and perpendicular (right). UC10740, UC10739 and UC10738 (from top).

Nondestructive methods applied to oriental swords for analysing high-carbon steels – FIXLAB 2013

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. **May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:**

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. **Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO**

7. **Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.**

8. **Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)**

name: Zsolt

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TNA Proposal Details

The title TNA proposal: Non-destructive structural and compositional analysis of swords and helmets by TOF-ND and PIXE techniques

Project proposal acronym: Hidden patterns

Date of realization: 2013

The title TNA proposal: Gamma-activation Nondestructive Analysis of Swords and Helmets

Project proposal acronym: GNASH

Date of realization: 2014

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

Information about the user:

Project leader name: Alan Williams

Project leader institution: The Wallace Collection, London , other institutions involved in using of the results (if applicable) Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto Sistemi Complessi; Hofjagd- und Rüstammer, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Vienna

Field of specialization of the user group: archaeometallurgist, conservator.

General description of the TNA activity

Various neutron techniques (PGAA, TOF-ND) and external milli-beam PIXE as complementary method were employed at the Budapest Nuclear Centre in an attempt to find the most useful method for analysing the high-carbon steels found in Oriental arms and armour, such as those in the Wallace Collection, London. Neutron diffraction was found to be useful in terms of identifying such steels and also indicating the presence of hidden patterns.

Major results of the access

David Edge, Alan Williams, Z. Kasztovszky, Zoltán Kis, Imre Kovács, László Rosta, Zoltán Szőkefalvi-Nagy, György Káli: Nondestructive methods of analysis applied to oriental swords, *Gladius* 35 (2015), 139–158.

The most useful techniques for the non-destructive analysis of swords seem to be, to some extent PIXE, but especially, ND. PIXE analysis on seven Indo-Persian blades was carried out. The trace elements found in some blades did not include vanadium, which has been claimed by some workers to be necessary for the formation of “Damascus” patterns. Perhaps other mechanisms are involved in their formation. Analysis of the gold used to inlay inscriptions showed that there was sometimes variation in its composition between blades. But if the gold alloy used in any one workshop or group of workshops was constant in composition (which seems likely) then we might have a potential method of identifying workshops in the Bactrian-Persian-Indian cultural area.

Six Indo-Persian blades were analysed by ND which has proved to be the most useful method of identifying high-carbon steels (such as are to be found in “Damascus” blades) but the detection of anisotropy in patterned blades has proved to be more complex. Some blades with clearly visible patterns show less anisotropy that might have been predicted. This could be due to forging methods which have led to a less asymmetrical distribution of carbides than expected. However, if this were to be found regularly, then this possible insight into different forging techniques could be extremely interesting.

Feedback from the user

- was the user enquired about the satisfaction from the results? If YES, what was the response?

- did the user participated in the dissemination of the results?

YES – how: scientific publication – reference above

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The analysis of plate armour is comparatively straightforward. A plate generally has an edge which can, after suitable preparation, be placed upon an inverted microscope and the microstructure investigated¹¹. Swords are more problematic, since a section (or at least a half-section) of a sword has to be observed in order to make any deductions about its manufacture. Attempts at investigation from the surface alone have had mixed success, so most results have had to be drawn from

The TNA activity related to „iconic” object or providing new results of common interest

excavated, or otherwise damaged swords.

Therefore, it became enormously necessary to have an entirely non-invasive technique for the analysis of swords, especially since The Wallace Collection, London, houses a highly important collection of Oriental (mostly Indo-Persian) arms and armour, including some 300 swords, as well as over 70 helmets, vambraces and shields, whose analysis presents quite difficult problems. The carbon content of Indian steels is unusually high by European standards, which has been one of the factors leading us to consider other techniques, such as neutron diffraction or gamma-activation. Accordingly, a series of experiments was planned and carried out at the Budapest Neutron Centre, Hungary. This was made possible by the transnational access program CHARISMA.

Fig. 6. Indian sword of 17th or 18th century – a broken blade of length 21 cm and hilt 21cm (12 cm width)

Fig. 7 Radiogram of the same specimen

Fig. 8 Indian kukri (knife) of 19th century

Fig. 9 Radiogram of the same specimen

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

Non-sampling analysis of painting layers by non-linear optical microscopy

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

New, non-invasive methodologies for the analysis of painting layers based on an advanced microscopy that uses ultrashort laser light pulses.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

Non-linear optical microscopy (NLOM) is a technique initially developed in the biomedical field to achieve high imaging quality in scattering environments such as cells and tissues. NLOM has reached the market while staying in the focus of further scientific innovations: the Nobel Prize in Chemistry was awarded in 2014 to E. Betzig, S. W. Hell and W. E. Moerner “for the development of super-resolved fluorescence microscopy”.

Various modalities of the technique (Multi-Photon Excited Fluorescence, Second and Third Harmonic Generation) are being developed, in the framework of the EU Project IPERION CH, for the accurate, non-invasive determination of the chemical nature, structure and thickness of multi-layered painting samples.

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? No

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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surname: Castillejo

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Objective

Develop a new methodology for non-sampling, non-invasive, in-depth analysis of painted artworks with micrometric resolution 3D capabilities.

General description of the instrument

The instrument is a laser scanning non-linear optical microscope where the excitation light is a laser delivering near-infrared, ultrashort pulses of femtosecond duration. The laser light is focused inside the substrate under study with a high numerical aperture objective lens. Non-linear optical signals, of Multi-Photon Excitation Fluorescence (MPEF), Second and Third Harmonic Generation (SHG and THG), are simultaneously generated in the focal volume of the examined object, each providing unique and complementary information concerning the chemical composition of the sample, the centrosymmetry/ organisation of its constituents and its structure (i. e., presence of multilayers). Those signals are detected either in transmission or in reflection modes, the latter being adequate for whole non-transparent cultural heritage objects, optically filtered and acquired using photomultipliers. Highly resolved 3D multimodal images are obtained by raster-scanning the laser over the object at different depths from the surface. The lateral and axial resolutions of the instrument are of the order of microns, while the penetration depth is typically up to 1 mm. Non-linear optical microscopy has been applied for the depth-resolved imaging of varnishes, lining glues, historical coatings, parchments, paints and corrosion layers on metal substrate

Unique features of the instrument

provide information on specific features (e.g. working parameters, construction) which makes it unique or especially designed for HS. What is the novelty of the design?

A non-linear optical microscope presents inherent 3D spatial resolution (superficial and in-depth) based on the quadratic or cubic dependence of signals on the intensity of the exciting laser beam. Laser wavelengths used in NLOM lie in the infrared region, ensuring significantly lower scattering and absorption from the investigated samples and thus increasing imaging depth. Generation of non-linear optical signals requires high peak laser power but the average power over the sample is low (of the order of mW), resulting in reduction of photothermal or photochemical unwanted effects. Due to the multimodal capability of such instrument, complementary information, such as the determination of different layers and their thickness, the surface topography or the concentration, shape and orientation of particles.

Unique methodologies

Non-linear optical microscopy (NLOM) is a technique initially developed in the field of biomedical optics that relies in ultrafast laser excitation to exploit several non-linear optical effects of materials. The common NLOM imaging modes of MPEF, SHG and THG provide non-destructive accurate determination of thickness within multi-layer samples and objects and of the composition as a function of depth. In imaging configurations, NLOM techniques are being incorporated as powerful diagnostic tools for cultural heritage studies, allowing surface mapping and profiling of multi-layer structures (e.g. coatings) using multimode operation schemes. Since absorption by most materials employed in artworks is low in the near-infrared, the use of laser light in this spectral region enables deeper optical penetration and makes feasible the examination of underlayers. The implementation

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

of THG, and especially SHG, signal acquisition in the reflection mode makes possible the study of non-transparent CH substrates. The lateral and axial resolutions of these techniques (diffraction-limited) are in the range of approx. 500 nm and approx. 2 μm respectively. The penetration depth is of the order of a few hundred μm for samples with high transparency in the NIR region.

In the framework of the EU Project IPERION CH, the modality of MPEF, as standalone or in combination with THG have been developed for the determination of thickness of transparent or partly transparent copper-phthalocyanine acrylic paint layers (results published in *Spectrochim. Acta A* 208 (2019) 262.) and for the assessment of modifications following laser removal of varnish (results published in *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 19 (2017) 22836.). Furthermore, an overview of the implementation of non-linear imaging contrast microscopy techniques (MPEF, SHG, polarization-SHG and THG), as diagnostic tools for cultural heritage studies has been published (*Insight - Non-Destructive Testing and Condition Monitoring*, DOI: 10.1784/insi.2018.60.12.XXX, DOI: 10.1784/insi.2018.60.12.XXX, in press).

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Non-linear optical microscopy techniques are non-invasive, do not require sampling and can be used to obtain 3D images (cross-sections), not only from substrates but also from whole cultural heritage (CH) objects. At present, these methods have been applied to a limited range of materials. The achievements here described allow extending the field of applications to the study of paintings which are complex substrates from the structural and compositional point of view. The advanced knowledge here obtained pave the way for development and validation of user-friendly workstations based on a suitably modified microscope with the capability of scanning and detecting very weak non-linear optical signals and a stable compact femtosecond laser source for in-situ applications in cultural heritage.

Non-Linear Optical Microscopy in painting analysis

Non-linear Optical Microscopy for studying paintings. Left: Determination of thickness of copper-phthalocyanine acrylic paints by Multi-Photon Excitation (adapted from *Spectrochim. Acta A* 208 (2019) 262-270.). Right: Assessment of modifications following laser removal of varnish (adapted from *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 19 (2017) 22836.).

Development of TLC/MU-ATR/SERS method

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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institution: UNIBO

e-mail:...S.PRATI@UNIBO.IT..... contact phone: +390544937153.....

Objective

The present research is focused on the setting up of an advanced analytical system for the detection of synthetic dyes.

The aim of this research is to propose for the first time a new TLC plate that allows the analysis of trace amounts of dyes present in mixture by means of the integrated use of enhanced Raman (SERS) and enhanced FTIR spectroscopy (Mu-ATR), obtaining complementary results.

General description of the instrument

The system is based on the combination of an innovative thin layer chromatography (TLC) plate coupled with enhanced infrared (MU-ATR, metal underlayer attenuated total reflection) and Surface Enhanced Raman (SERS) spectroscopy. In particular, a TLC plate made of silver iodide (AgI) applied onto a gold coated glass slide (AgI@Au) is proposed as an efficient stationary phase for the

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

separation of dyes mixtures. The separated dyes are then identified by means of both enhanced FTIR and SERS, performed directly on the same eluted spots. The use of a mid-IR transparent inorganic salt as stationary phase coupled with the underneath gold layer avoids spectral interferences, enhancing the signal obtained from ATR analyses. At the same time, SERS spectra can be recorded as the TLC plate may act as a SERS active substrate due to the photoreduction of AgI to metallic Ag caused by the exposure to the laser during the Raman analysis.

Unique features of the instrument

For the first time a new TLC plate that allows the analysis of trace amounts of dyes present in mixture by means of the integrated use of enhanced Raman (SERS) and enhanced FTIR spectroscopy (Mu-ATR), obtaining complementary results.

Unique methodologies

For the first time a new TLC plate that allows the analysis of trace amounts of dyes present in mixture by means of the integrated use of enhanced Raman (SERS) and enhanced FTIR spectroscopy (Mu-ATR), obtaining complementary results.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The characterization of organic dyes still represents a challenging task, because due to their high tinting strength, dyes are present in very low concentrations and are usually embedded into ultracomponent matrices (such as: paints, textiles, or inks). Nevertheless, their unambiguous and sensitive identification is of utmost importance for the characterisation istic samples for instance for provenance, dating and authentication studies.

The study has been published in *Analytica Chimica Acta*:

Sciutto, G., Prati, S., Bonacini, I., Litti, L., Meneghetti, M., & Mazzeo, R. (2017). A new integrated TLC/MU-ATR/SERS advanced approach for the identification of trace amounts of dyes in mixtures. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2017.08.020>

Gold substrate

AgI

μ Raman objective

Laser beam

ATR crystal

Gold substrate

AgI

AgI

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

NMR-MOUSE instrument

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Portable MRI inspects frescoes, paintings, violins and mummies

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

There has been a number of reports on the NMR-MOUSE on television over the years. The most prominent one features the study of Charlemagne's tibia in the three-part movie on the life of Charlemagne (see [movie](#) at [1:00](#) h):
<https://www.bing.com/videos/search?q=arte+karl+der+grosse&&view=detail&mid=4B188F967CFF90FB1FAC4B188F967CFF90FB1FAC&&FORM=VRDGAR>

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The NMR-MOUSE is a commercial product of Magritek holding and is being produced by Magritek GmbH in Aachen. Magritek GmbH is directed by Federico Casanova and Juan Perlo, who developed the instrument in the EU-ARTECH project. The company has expanded since and leads the world market in producing tabletop NMR spectrometers for chemical analysis.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Objective

A compact MRI instrument has been developed with which large objects can be inspected locally from one side with the superior soft-matter contrast of magnetic resonance imaging

General description of the instrument

The instrument is called NMR-MOUSE for MOBILE Universal Surface Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Explorer. It consists of a permanent magnet with a radio-frequency coil.

Unique features of the instrument

The NMR-MOUSE is essentially an MRI machine. But instead of having a large magnet where the object goes inside, the magnet is small, and the object is placed next to it. The pixels of the NMR-MOUSE are flat disks, 0.1 mm thin and 10 mm wide. They are defined by the sensitive measurement volume outside the sensor and are measured one by one.

Unique methodologies

Typically, the instrument is placed on a precision sliding table by which the sensitive volume is stepped out of the object so that the acquired pixels constitute a high-resolution depth profile that reports the stratigraphy and physical material properties of the object. Typical material properties are the moisture content, the wax content, or the elasticity of the material. These are the same parameters that give rise to the contrast in clinical magnetic resonance images. Like its clinical big brother, a measurement with the NMR-MOUSE is non-destructive.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

All non-metallic objects containing hydrogen can be studied non-destructively with the NMR-MOUSE. Important applications to heritage science concern the optimization of solvent-cleaning procedures for paintings, the efficiency of stone conservation treatments, the identification of undocumented conservation measures with bones, wood, plaster and stone, the determination of the content and flux direction of moisture inside walls, and the stratigraphic analysis of the plaster layers from frescoes which provide unique and novel insights into the craftsmanship and socio-economic conditions at the time of making.

The NMR-MOUSE scanning the depth of a wall from the Cathedral of St. Anthony in Padua in search of a hidden Giotto fresco. Copyright Bernhard Blümich.

Optimisation of portable Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry system DHSPI III

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

NDT structural Diagnosis: The DHSPI III hybrid geometry provides non contact high resolution defect detection with digital capturing ease. DHSPI detects in micrometer resolution all typical subsurface/bulk defects that impact on the surface. Hidden cracks and detachments, voids and weakened areas invisible to other advanced imaging tools become traceable from surface. Raw data manipulation algorithms offer multi-tasking tools usable to generate accurate **defect documentation topography**, defects with exact coordinates, surface morphology, 3D surface mapping. Post-processing tools are employed to most applications of DHSPI. Example: serve to generate a coded “signature” conducing to the verification of originality procedures, e.g. **Originality assessment** before and after travel.

Risk priority map: Defect topography map is direct visual qualitative result from pre-processing recording, while risk priority map is quantitative result after post-processing. The structural condition is prioritised according to the impact of defects on precious surface to carry out necessary remedial interventions. Additionally it is visualised the defect micro-structure in 2D and 3D. The defects or defected areas are located, sized in 1:1 scale and deformation is measured to be marked as μm per area (mm^2 , cm^2 related to the severity of defect impact on surface signifying the risk of permanent damage).

Preventive conservation: Monitoring environmental and microclimate impact of interior/exterior surfaces. Decorative artifacts, furniture, frescoes and wall paintings in historical buildings and monuments deteriorate constantly in response to the environment. DHSPI III can operate automatically in long term measurements to perform monitoring of surface reactions due to natural fluctuations of RH/T. Suits for on-field measurement requirements and can operate in moderate harsh out of laboratory conditions, e.g. Monuments and Churches environmental impact

Direct monitoring of materials, fragile surfaces are recorded in respond to natural climate conditions allowing to evaluate microclimate safety.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

http://popularizacija.ifs.hr/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/LaserLab_NL_07-2018_web.pdf

Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI) is a non-destructive optical technique which can be used to investigate deformation, deterioration and fracture mechanisms in cultural heritage objects. In the context of the European IPERION CH MOLAB project, Laserlab-Europe partner IESL-FORTH has developed DHSPI-II, a portable custom-made prototype, which has already been used to monitor wooden objects and to examine 17th century paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London. In DHSPI two coherent beams from the same laser form a holographic interferogram of the speckle patterns – spatial variations in the observed light intensity of the light reflected from a rough surface – on a CCD detector. A computer processes the phase changes in the reflected beam, which are caused by changes in the shape and position of the surface and the underlying material, revealing any changes in the surface as well as the internal structure. The laser beams employed in the DHSPI-II are highly divergent, allowing imaging of the whole or extended parts of the surface (full field). This also guarantees safety for the operator as well as the object, because in this power density regime the laser radiation does not interact with the surface. The technique enables detection of the location, shape and size of invisible defects, as well as their changes over time. As such, it allows monitoring of structural changes resulting from varying environmental and climatic conditions, conservation treatments, aging, and transportation or handling. The DHSPI-II instrument is a 15 kg light-weight portable system, comprising an optical head of 30x20 cm and a PC driven control unit. It has been developed at the holography laboratory of IESL-FORTH, and funded through several national and EU projects related to artworks diagnostics. In a preliminary preventive conservation experiment, DHSPI was employed to monitor in real time the response of complex materials and objects to fluctuations in relative humidity and temperature. Analysis has focused on the assessment of the dynamics of dimensional changes in cultural heritage objects made of hygroscopic materials. Oak and pine with sizes of 2 x 2 cm, and of varying thicknesses from 1 mm to 1 cm, were monitored while relative humidity was varied between 45% and 65% at different rates. The data of this work in progress suggests that wood sensors could be suitable for future assessment of environmental changes in collections. In addition, scaffold access between February and April 2018 enabled the recording of The Apotheosis of King James I and The Wise Rule of King James I, two ceiling paintings produced by Peter Paul Rubens and installed at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London in 1636. The assessment by the DHSPI-II instrument was part of a multidisciplinary effort to carry out a first ever full and systematic technical conservation survey, to determine how the paintings were created, how they have changed over the years, as well as to establish an accurate record of the present condition of the paintings to inform on approaches to future possible conservation interventions. Vivi Tornari A.Nevin, M. Andrianakis, V. Tornari, Towards understanding the impact of environmental changes on cultural heritage through the real time monitoring of dimensional change in wood sensors with Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry, to be published in Applied Surface Science List

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Objective

Holographic interferometry and thermography techniques in contactless non-destructive real-time direct-surface reflectance to record in full field changes in terms of a) surface optical displacement and b) its temperature gradient

General description of the instrument

Workstation development on optical table or in-situ integrating two separate systems for the interferometry and thermography measurements.

Unique features of the instrument

Contactless, non-destructive, real-time, direct-surface reflectance, full field.

Unique methodologies

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Enhanced diagnosis of subsurface damage provoking unknown sub and surface reactions can be provided by the complimentary study of DHSPI-SIRT. In general the effort to a combined use of the thermostructural information revealed data to diagnose unknown problems it is a challenge for the in situ applicability of portable systems and thus it is a problem of major importance if further hybrid instrumentation development is to be concerned and funded.

OCT instrument dedicated for examination of CH objects

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Objective

It was a need for a universal instrument of very high axial resolution and sensitivity capable of examination of a broad variety of CH objects with a convenient system of the annotation of examination spot for comparing with results obtained with other techniques

General description of the instrument

- Non-contact and non-invasive, utilising a short-wave IR radiation
- Permits imaging of cross-sectional views of transparent and semi-transparent sub-surface layers of the object
- Axial resolution in varnish: 2.1 μm , lateral resolution: ca 12 μm (optics dependent)
- Time of examination: 0.2 s / cross-section

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

- able to examine objects on an easel (mounted vertically) or on the table – mounted horizontally

Suitable for examination of easel paintings, historic and archaeological glass, ceramic, certain stones like jade, porcelain and faience, amber,

Unique features of the instrument

- Optimal axial resolution/penetration depth ratio
- HR live data preview due to utilisation of GPU technology
- Extensive video documentation system for localisation of examinations

Unique methodologies

- Localisation and determination of a state of preservation of varnish/glaze layers
- Measurements of thickness of these layers - if thicker than 5 μm
- Monitoring of varnish removal (chemically or by a laser)
- Examination of specific deterioration effects (e.g. lead soap formation and presence of protrusions)

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The instrument was broadly used for examination of objects during CHARISMA (e.a. “Adoration of the Magi” by Leonardo da Vinci and “The Landsdowne Virgin of the Yarnwinder” from the same studio, “La Muta” by Raphael, selected panels from “The Adoration of the Mystic Lamb” by Hubert and Jan van Eyck. “The Last Judgement” by Hans Memling. Then it had been included into MOLAB offer of IPERION CH and used for examination, e.a. of “The Vase with Sunflowers”, “View of the sea at Scheveningen”, and “Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen” by Vincent van Gogh, two ceiling paintings by Peter P. Rubens: “The Apotheosis of James I” and “The Wise Rule of King James I” from the Whitehall Banqueting House in London, art deco painted windows in Casa-Museu Doutor Anastácio Gonçalves in Lisbon, series of pastels by Wallerand Vaillant and historic violins in Violin Museum in Cremona.

OCT instrument at work at van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam during examination of „Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen” by Vincent van Gogh, from the left: prof. P. Targowski, Kathrin Pilz (VGM), May 2018, © P. Targowski

Exemplary OCT result from „ Congregation leaving the Reformed Church in Nuenen” by Vincent van Gogh; from the top: OCT cross-sectional view; IR photo with the position of a scan marked yellow; Annotation photos, © NCU

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

Neutron imaging driven prompt gamma-ray activation analysis (PGAA) at the NIPS-NORMA facility of the BNC

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The smart use of neutrons to provide localized elemental analysis of a bulky object in a non-invasive way.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

There is a YouTube series about the scientific activities at MTA EK, and one of them is dealing with the work related to Cultural Heritage Science at Nuclear Analysis and Radiography Department: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rkipBjVzw8w&list=PLYLO2ytittIFQmhEf11-fFIQ04MaS9Gg&index=17>

The Lendület/Momentum grant of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences (From bones, bronzes and sites to society: Multidisciplinary analysis of human mobility and social changes in Bronze Age Hungary (2500–1500 BC)) gives a possibility to examine the thousand years of the first half of the Bronze Age in several micro-regions of the Carpathian Basin that had played an outstanding role in prehistoric Europe for millennia due to its geographical location and to climatic factors. Based on the exchange of the eponymous material, bronze, distant regions linked up with each other, and for the first time in the history of humanity, social inequalities became institutionalized.

<http://mobilitas.ri.btk.mta.hu/?media=innovacio-a-bronzkori-regeszetben-avagy-mult-nelkul-nincs-jo-vo-2&lang=en>

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)

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Objective

The smart use of neutrons to provide localized elemental analysis of a bulky object in a non-invasive way.

General description of the instrument

The NIPS-NORMA facility is designed to integrate two non-destructive techniques (PGAA and NI) using guided cold neutrons.

Unique features of the instrument

At the NIPS-NORMA facility, a novel non-destructive procedure has been developed to determine the distribution of major elements and visualize internal parts of heterogeneous objects by combining position sensitive prompt-gamma activation analysis (PGAA) and neutron radiography/tomography (NI) into a unique facility.

Unique methodologies

The position-sensitive element analysis with prompt-gamma activation analysis (PGAA) and the imaging with neutron radiography/tomography (NR/NT) are integrated into a unique facility called NIPS-NORMA. The goal of such a combination of these methods is to save substantial beam time in the so-called NR/NT-driven PGAI (Prompt Gamma Activation Imaging) mode, in which the interesting regions are first visualized and located, and subsequently the time consuming prompt-gamma measurements are made only where it is really needed. If necessary, the quality of the images could be improved using the newly installed collimator changer, which provides the possibility to choose the suitable collimation ratio in the beam.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The NIPS-NORMA instrument is suitable for the non-destructive determination of bulk elemental composition of various samples, based on the detection of the characteristic prompt-gamma radiation induced by neutron capture into the atomic nucleus. The most of the major components and a few trace elements (e.g. B, Cl, Co, Cd, Hg, Sm and Gd) in rocks, minerals, ceramics, glass, metals and many inorganic materials can be determined. In addition, NIPS-NORMA station allows performing a position-sensitive elemental analysis of well-defined spots on larger objects (sculptures, vessels, etc. with up to the size of ca. 15 cm). Furthermore, it is possible to combine the 2D or 3D neutron imaging with local elemental analysis. At the moment, this technique is exclusively available at the BNC.

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

Fragments of a bronze dagger from the Füzesabony-Öregdomb settlement, dated to the 16th–15th century BC, i.e. Early or Middle Bronze Age were analyzed. Although neutron imaging is perfect to reveal the internal structure of the heterogeneous objects, with a spatial resolution far better than what neutron-based elemental analysis can ever offer, it cannot provide unambiguous evidence about the materials used, since, by chance, more than one material can have the same macroscopic attenuation property. An object's internal structure and its production technology can sometimes be understood only if a complementary element analysis technique, such as handheld X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (hhXRF), or position sensitive prompt-gamma activation analysis (PGAI) is involved, that can greatly improve the confidence of the conclusions. PGAI can outperform XRF when an altered layer is present on the surface either due to the corrosion processes during the burial, or due to surface treatment carried out in the museum for the purpose of restoration.

From the elemental analysis results, a clear difference between surface and bulk compositions was identified. The surface-related hhXRF data showed an alloy of about 70 wt% Cu and a variable Sn content (0.7–8 wt%), whereas bulk results measured by PGAI were 86 wt% Cu and 5.9 wt% Sn. These two major components do not sum up to 100%. Some lighter elements, e.g. Si, S and Fe were also present at 1% levels. The differences in elemental compositions found on the surface and in the bulk are attributed to soil contamination, or to near-surface corrosion, as well as to the concentration gradients caused by the fabrication. © 2018 Elsevier Ltd. All rights reserved.

L. Szentmiklósi, B. Maróti, Z. Kis, and Z. Kasztovszky, "Integration of neutron-based elemental analysis and imaging methods and applications to cultural heritage research," *J. Archaeol. Sci. Reports*, vol. 20, pp. 476–482, 2018.

Bimodal (neutron and X-ray) imaging at the RAD neutron facility of BNC

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The parallel use of a filtered neutron beam and X-rays in imaging for better selectivity in objects.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

There is a YouTube video about the scientific collaboration between the Hungarian National Museum and the MTA EK, showing a success story about the work related to a Late Bronze Age spearhead with wooden shaft:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2X8i9QA5p6E&list=PLYLO2tytittIFQmhEf11-fFIQ04MaS9Gg&index=3>

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details (sent by Katalin Bajnok)

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Objective

The parallel use of a filtered neutron beam and X-rays in imaging for better selectivity in objects.

New instrument developed or significantly improved or new methodology developed

General description of the instrument

The RAD station uses a horizontal beam that consist of a mixture of thermal and more energetic (epithermal and fast) neutrons, with the option of the mutual use of an X-ray source up to 200 kV tube voltage.

Unique features of the instrument

For HS objects, neutrons proved to be a useful probe, of which advantages could be better exploited at state-of-the-art facilities. Such facilities should combine the advantages of the filtered neutron beam, and the complementary feature of the neutron and X-ray imaging, providing a vivid tool for the investigation of HS problems.

Unique methodologies

Imaging as a non-destructive and non-invasive technique is rather powerful for the investigation of complex samples. Its objective is to look through and into objects made of a few varied materials, created by complex manufacturing processes and used for different purposes.

Because of the different reaction mechanisms of the thermal and epithermal (and fast) neutrons, and X-rays with matter, they can effectively be utilized for advanced imaging. If we could separate the different energy components using filters, we could achieve better contrast in our imaging system for the different materials.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The neutron beam at RAD is a radial beam where the beam port is facing to reactor core. There are two distinct aims to filter the white beam: a, to get rid of the more energetic part (epithermal and fast), and b, to use the most energetic part (fast) of it. In the first case, the sapphire crystal, which scatters out the energetic neutrons from the beam, makes it more thermal. This setup shields the system from the unnecessary burden of the higher energy neutrons. In the second case, a combination of a boron sheet and a lead column as a shielding against the lower energy neutrons, keeps just the higher energy ones. Such beam could effectively be used for the imaging of large (>10 cm) objects consisting of light and heavy materials (e.g. organic materials in metal structures) when using our polypropylene-based scintillation screen.

Another advantage of the application of beam-filters is that the induced activity of the objects can significantly be reduced that will eventually simplify the loan, storage and transportation process of the valuable museum objects.

The use of bimodal imaging (neutron and X-rays) makes sense for experiments with low contrast between the relevant features, where adding a second modality is beneficial to reduce ambiguity. Hydrogen-containing materials and several light elements (e.g. chlorine) will give high contrast, and many metals can easily be trans-illuminated by neutrons, while for X-rays, light elements (e.g. organic materials) have low contrast, and heavy elements (e.g. metals) are difficult to trans-illuminate. The joined evaluation of the two datasets will provide better base for distinction between different materials in the sample.

X-ray and neutron imaging of the full Kikinda bronze spearhead from the Hungarian National Museum, Department of Archaeology, Prehistoric Collection: (a) the X-ray radiography (b) the neutron radiography, (c) the neutron tomography and (d) a slice from the neutron tomography. The grayscale values of the radiographic images (a–b) are characteristic to the object's transmission, i.e. brighter spots mean more transmission. The grayscale values of the tomographic image (c) are characteristic to attenuation power of the object, i.e. brighter spots mean less transmission and, as a consequence, larger attenuation power. © 2018 Elsevier Ltd. All rights reserved.

J. G. Tarbay, B. Maróti, and Z. Kis, "Introducing the spear project: The tale of the Late Bronze Age spearhead with wooden shaft from the Marshland of Kikinda, Serbia," *J. Archaeol. Sci. Reports*, vol. 21, pp. 268–274, Oct. 2018.

New research methodology for commercial instrumentation

NMR-MOUSE

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Portable MRI inspects frescoes, paintings, violins and mummies

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The NMR-MOUSE is a commercial product of Magritek holding and is being produced by Magritek GmbH in Aachen. Magritek GmbH is directed by Federico Casanova and Juan Perlo, who developed the instrument in the EU-ARTECH project. The company has expanded since and leads the world market in producing tabletop NMR spectrometers for chemical analysis.

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Cleaning a painting while monitoring the solvent uptake by compact MRI with the NMR-MOUSE. Copyright Christian Rehorn.

G-PE electrochemical cell for in situ diagnostic of metallic cultural heritage

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry
- other – describe: Other industrial/research applications which need to measure carry out in-situ corrosion/protection measurements.

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Need to measure in-situ the degradation rate of a metallic sculpture, compare protective treatments or predict their failure? We have the tool for it, which will provide quantitative information on the corrosion process and protective systems for metallic heritage.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE
- other: national projects

comments:

The development of an electrochemical cell, specially tailored for in-situ application on cultural heritage, has been carried out under two Spanish nationally funded projects (CREMEL and CREMEL II). Under IPERION CH, the methodology using the cell has been tested and improved, demonstrating the utility for evaluation of the performance of different coatings over various typical heritage metals. Based on these developments, a new MOLAB facility, METAL.es (METAL Electrochemical Studies) has been created.

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Objective

The objective of this design is to provide a tool for in situ diagnostic of metallic cultural heritage (and protective properties of patinas, coatings or other treatments) by electrochemical techniques.

General description of the instrument or the procedure for which the methodology was developed

The G-PE cell is a solid electrolyte electrochemical cell, with a gelled electrolyte, specifically designed for in situ electrochemical measurements on metallic cultural heritage. This G-PE cell can be used with any commercial electrochemical measuring instrument.

Unique features of the methodology

Electrochemical techniques such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) give information on corrosion processes on metal objects, being a powerful tool for metal conservation. Traditional electrochemical cells consist of a vessel containing the electrolyte and electrodes, or a rigid container filled with a liquid electrolyte. None of these configurations are suitable to measure on the non-flat, leaning and/or irregular surface of a heritage object.

The G-PE cell consists of a plastic mould in which the reference and counter electrodes are fixed, which is filled with an aqueous electrolyte representing the corrosive environment, gelled with agar. The cell is inserted in a support fixed to an articulated arm that allows positioning on the surface to study.

The use of a gelled electrolyte cell adapts to the irregularity of the surface and allows measuring in-situ on the heritage asset on any position.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Protecting metallic cultural heritage from corrosion is a serious challenge for metal conservators. Limitation of time and resources and uncertainty on the effectiveness or duration of protective treatments are major issues in this enterprise. Electrochemical techniques such as Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy can provide an answer to these questions, and for these reasons are widely used in industry for corrosion studies and coatings evaluation. In the last decades its application to metallic cultural heritage conservation has raised some interest, though the difficulties to perform measures on the complex surface of monuments and objects has limited its use.

The G-PE cell provides a diagnostic tool that allows corrosion resistance evaluation of patinas and coatings, its evolution over time and helps to predict the failure of the protective coatings before active corrosion starts again. Having an adequate tool for in situ corrosion studies will facilitate research and improve the knowledge on corrosion and protection mechanisms in cultural heritage. The quantitative information obtained allows selecting the most efficient treatments and programming conservation interventions, saving resources and improving the preservation of unique heritage assets.

Electrochemical field measurements using the G-PE cell to assess the protective properties of Cor-Ten steel patinas.

Identification of highly aged organic residues in ancient wall paintings

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

Read the following definitions before going ahead

Academic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to academic advances, across and within disciplines, including significant advances in understanding, methods, theory and application (this could be scientific, but could also be in other disciplines related to heritage science eg advances in understanding the materials and structure of an object contributing to historical research questions)

Economic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to the economy. (e.g. the commercialisation of the instrument developed)

Societal impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to society, especially to preservation of CH – e.g. by introducing a new method of conservation, adopted by the community or commonly adopted new facts (knowledge) about the object of art

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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New research methodology for commercial instrumentation

Objective

To improve the analytical means in the investigation of organic binding media used in the ancient wall paintings

To identify possible degradation markers, such as carboxylates / oxalates, associated to the use of an original organic matter, deteriorated and thus hardly detectable.

General description of the instrument or the procedure for which the methodology was developed

Methodology components and respective information obtained:

Non invasive

- Diffuse reflectance in the Visible spectral range - > colour alteration
- FTIR total reflectance measurements -> screening of organic materials and degradation products on the paint surface

Micro destructive

- Micro ATR-FTIR mapping - > layer- resolved molecular investigation of organic materials and degradation products through the paint stratigraphy

Complementary separation techniques for the accurate identification of binder residues

- Evolved Gas Analysis- Mass Spectrometry (EGA-MS)
- Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS)

Unique features of the methodology

Integrated methodology developed for:

- examination of original painting techniques / binding media on ancient wall paintings or fragments.
- identification of highly aged organic residues.
- Investigation of deterioration mechanisms

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

An analytical approach was developed for studying the Interaction between organic compounds and metal ions, considering the entire system pigment-binder-lime ground in archaeological wall paintings.

- GC-MS analysis is accepted as the most accurate approach for the identification of organic binders, however, in highly aged samples,
 - proteins may show low solubility due to aggregation and cross-linking, challenging the GC-MS analysis.
 - when the protein is highly aggregated and cross-linked, the identification of the original binder is not possible by using EGA/MS analytical pyrolysis, but,
 - EGA/MS can be efficient in identifying egg (yolk or whole egg)-based binders in even extremely aged and degraded samples.
- Advanced methodological solutions combining analytical pyrolysis EGA/MS and GC-MS have been tested for the identification of degraded binders.
- The spatial distribution of degradation products in the paint layers as obtained with Micro ATR-FTIR mapping is crucial for their correlation with specific original constituent materials, pigments or media or their possible chemical reaction.

More info in:

Sotiropoulou, S., Scitutto, G., Lluveras Tenorio, A., Mazurek, J., Bonaduce, I., Prati, S., Mazzeo, R., Schilling, M., and Colombini, M.P., Advanced analytical investigation on degradation markers in wall paintings, *Microchemical Journal* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2018.03.007>

The methodology has been developed on a set of paint models designed to simulate ancient wall painting techniques. The models have been subjected to accelerated ageing.

FTIR – ATR mapping on a cross-section of sample WP1ii_3A_T5: a) spectrum extracted from the red ochre layer (Layer 1); b) spectrum extracted from the red lead layer (Layer 2); c) visible light microscopic image: white square indicates the region submitted to FTIR-ATR mapping analysis; d) false colour map of free fatty acids (peak area 1718 cm^{-1}); e) false colour map of calcium carboxylate (peak area 1576 cm^{-1}); f) false colour map of lead carboxylate (peak area 1563 cm^{-1}); g) false colour map of calcium oxalates (peak area 1320 cm^{-1}).

Software tool

Entropy repository software

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

Read the following definitions before going ahead

Academic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to academic advances, across and within disciplines, including significant advances in understanding, methods, theory and application (this could be scientific, but could also be in other disciplines related to heritage science eg advances in understanding the materials and structure of an object contributing to historical research questions)

Economic impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to the economy. (e.g. the commercialisation of the instrument developed)

Societal impact: the demonstrable contribution that the achievement makes to society, especially to preservation of CH – e.g. by introducing a new method of conservation, adopted by the community or commonly adopted new facts (knowledge) about the object of art

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

Software tool

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A software tool

Objective

Improving the accessibility of analytical data in heritage science, in accordance with the FAIR principles: making raw analytical data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable.

General description of the software package

Open source repository platform for storage, documentation, organization, presentation and sharing of heritage science analytical data.

Unique features of the software

Features:

- Open source, available on GitHub: <https://github.com/KIKIRPA/Entropy>
- Archival of analytical data and related metadata
- Organisation of data in libraries with access control
- Querying and interactive visualisation of the datasets
- Storage of data and metadata in an open, human-readable and archival-ready format
- On-the-fly conversion from/to proprietary file formats (through add-ons)
- Mass upload of existing data

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The Entropy repository provides researchers a unique tool to archive, document and share analytical datasets online, using the FAIR principles, and to create valuable scientific resources of data for the (heritage) science community.

During the IPERION CH project, a number of repository implementations of Entropy were made, showcasing datasets created during the project:

- Raman spectra from a MOLAB project
- Example synchrotron-imaging-XRF for FIXLAB
- OCT data from a MOLAB project

In addition, the possibility is being evaluated to use Entropy for a repository of the data generated in WP7.1a Diagnostic strategies for assessing the cleaning of paintings. All IPERION CH repositories are available on the internet: <https://entropydemo.kikirpa.be>

As an open source project, it is anticipated that Entropy will be used for other repositories in the future, not necessarily related to IPERION CH or E-RIHS. Since December 2018, an online repository of analytical data on synthetic organic pigments (<https://soprano.kikirpa.be>) was launched by SOPRANO, a network of researchers in European research institutions working on the analysis of these pigments and their use in authentication studies. Entropy forms the basis of the SOPRANO platform.

Screenshot of the demo MOLAB OCT repository
Showing the front page on which the repository is described, contact details and measurement points are listed.

Early Qur'an Illumination on Parchment (EQUIP)
MOLAB examination of the *Chester Beatty Islamic manuscript Is 1404* with Raman spectroscopy

List library

f13r_Rm_01
Raman 785nm

Analysis spot: f13r_Rm_01 | Colour: red | Result: cinnabar | Type: Raman 785nm

Raman Spectrum: Intensity (Arbitrary Units) vs Raman shift (cm⁻¹). The plot shows a prominent peak at approximately 300 cm⁻¹ and a smaller peak at approximately 350 cm⁻¹, with the intensity decreasing as the Raman shift increases.

License: The applicant of the TNA project has the copyright on this data. All use of the data outside the IPERION-CH context needs the written permission of the copyright owner.

Download: ASCII (.txt), JCAMPDX (.dx)

The complete Early Qur'an Illumination on Parchment (EQUIP) can be requested by email. By downloading this file you agree to the terms described in the license.

Sample		Instrument		Measurement	
Foil	f13r	Spectrometer	Rigaku Xantus-2	Timestamp	2018/03/14 13:29:57
Analysis spot	f13r_Rm_01	Detector	CCD	ID	ID_20180314132957
Colour	red				
X coordinate	0.39881911873817444				
Y coordinate	0.3257705569267273				

Parameters		Data processing		Result	
Source	785 nm	Baseline correction	no		cinnabar
Power	42 mW				
Integration time	300 ms				
Accumulations	20				

About IPERION-CH
[IPERION-CH \(main website\)](#)

Powered by Entropy
A repository tailored for analytical data

Developed by Wim Fremout
Supported by
IPERION-CH

Screenshot of the demo MOLAB Raman repository
Showing a Raman measurement in an interactive viewer with download options.

TBA..

High IF publication or series of publications

Optimisation of portable Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry system DHSPI III

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

NDT structural Diagnosis: The DHSPI III hybrid geometry provides non contact high resolution defect detection with digital capturing ease. DHSPI detects in micrometer resolution all typical subsurface/bulk defects that impact on the surface. Hidden cracks and detachments, voids and weakened areas invisible to other advanced imaging tools become traceable from surface. Raw data manipulation algorithms offer multi-tasking tools usable to generate accurate **defect documentation topography**, defects with exact coordinates, surface morphology , 3D surface mapping. Post-processing tools are employed to most applications of DHSPI . Example: serve to generate a coded “signature” conducting to the verification of originality procedures, e.g. **Originality assessment** before and after travel.

Risk priority map: Defect topography map is direct visual qualitative result from pre-processing recording, while risk priority map is quantitative result after post-processing. The structural condition is prioritised according to the impact of defects on precious surface to carry out necessary remedial interventions. Additionally it is visualised the defect micro-structure in 2D and 3D. The defects or defected areas are located, sized in 1:1 scale and deformation is measured to be marked as μm per area (mm^2 , cm^2 related to the severity of defect impact on surface signifying the risk of permanent damage.

Preventive conservation: Monitoring environmental and microclimate impact of interior/exterior surfaces. Decorative artifacts, furniture, frescoes and wall paintings in historical buildings and monuments deteriorate constantly in response to the environment. DHSPI III can operate automatically in long term measurements to perform monitoring of surface reactions due to natural fluctuations of RH/T. Suits for on-field measurement requirements and can operate in moderate harsh out of laboratory conditions, e.g. Monuments and Churches environmental impact

Direct monitoring of materials, fragile surfaces are recorded in respond to natural climate conditions allowing to evaluate microclimate safety.

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

http://popularizacija.ifs.hr/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/LaserLab_NL_07-2018_web.pdf

Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry (DHSPI) is a non-destructive optical technique which can be used to investigate deformation, deterioration and fracture mechanisms in cultural heritage objects. In the context of the European IPERION CH MOLAB project, Laserlab-Europe partner IESL-FORTH has developed DHSPI-II, a portable custom-made prototype, which has already been used to monitor wooden objects and to examine 17th century paintings by Peter Paul Rubens at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London. In DHSPI two coherent beams from the same laser form a holographic interferogram of the speckle patterns – spatial variations in the observed light intensity of the light reflected from a rough surface – on a CCD detector. A computer processes the phase changes in the reflected beam, which are caused by changes in the shape and position of the surface and the underlying material, revealing any changes in the surface as well as the internal structure. The laser beams employed in the DHSPI-II are highly divergent, allowing imaging of the whole or extended parts of the surface (full field). This also guarantees safety for the operator as well as the object, because in this power density regime the laser radiation does not interact with the surface. The technique enables detection of the location, shape and size of invisible defects, as well as their changes over time. As such, it allows monitoring of structural changes resulting from varying environmental and climatic conditions, conservation treatments, aging, and transportation or handling. The DHSPI-II instrument is a 15 kg light-weight portable system, comprising an optical head of 30x20 cm and a PC driven control unit. It has been developed at the holography laboratory of IESL-FORTH, and funded through several national and EU projects related to artworks diagnostics. In a preliminary preventive conservation experiment, DHSPI was employed to monitor in real time the response of complex materials and objects to fluctuations in relative humidity and temperature. Analysis has focused on the assessment of the dynamics of dimensional changes in cultural heritage objects made of hygroscopic materials. Oak and pine with sizes of 2 x 2 cm, and of varying thicknesses from 1 mm to 1 cm, were monitored while relative humidity was varied between 45% and 65% at different rates. The data of this work in progress suggests that wood sensors could be suitable for future assessment of environmental changes in collections. In addition, scaffold access between February and April 2018 enabled the recording of The Apotheosis of King James I and The Wise Rule of King James I, two ceiling paintings produced by Peter Paul Rubens and installed at the Whitehall Banqueting House in London in 1636. The assessment by the DHSPI-II instrument was part of a multidisciplinary effort to carry out a first ever full and systematic technical conservation survey, to determine how the paintings were created, how they have changed over the years, as well as to establish an accurate record of the present condition of the paintings to inform on approaches to future possible conservation interventions. Vivi Tornari A.Nevin, M. Andrianakis, V. Tornari, Towards understanding the impact of environmental changes on cultural heritage through the real time monitoring of dimensional change in wood sensors with Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry, to be published in Applied Surface Science List

High IF publication or series of publications

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Reference

Journals:

1. "On development of portable Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry system for remote-access monitoring and documentation in art conservation", Vivi Tornari, Strain 2018 DOI:10.1111/str.12288
2. "Digital holographic interferometry for cultural heritage structural diagnostics: A coherent and a low-coherence optical set-up for the study of a marquetry sample", Kosma K, Andrianakis M, Hatzigiannakis K, Tornari V., STRAIN. 2018; e12263. <https://doi.org/10.1111/str.12263>

Conferences

1. "**Portable Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry system and Infrared Thermography: A data combination strategy for Cultural Heritage research and applications**", **invited**, Vivi Tornari Michalis Andrianakis , Vincent Detalle, Didier Brissaud, Stephanie Duchêne and Witold Nowik, David Giovannacci , Antonina Ghaban, LACONA VII, Paris 10-15 September 2018
2. "Development of Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry for Cultural Heritage", **invited** , Vivi Tornari (invited), Shanghai, IcOPEN International Conference, April 2018

General description of the contents

Journals:

1. In the paper it is described the methodology used to develop a portable optical geometry and the relevant algorithm to perform holographic interferometry using speckle pattern recorded on digital medium for assisting conservators to proceed to structural diagnosis.
2. In the paper it is described the experimental geometry used to acquire low coherence compared to high coherence measurements using holographic speckle pattern interferometry. The idea is the basis to explore further the tuneable interferometry for low-cost thermostructural diagnosis.

The novelty of the communication

Journals:

- 1 Portable interferometry for Cultural heritage in movable and non-movable artworks
2. Hybrid tuneable interferometry

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

1. Digital Holographic Speckle Pattern Interferometry portable system is the only system for remote full field real time structural diagnosis and its potential plays an important contribution to modern investigation of non-invasive systems.
2. Experimentation on new optical geometries and combination of wavelengths in low coherence can provide new instruments in the near future

NMR-MOUSE**2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Portable MRI inspects frescoes, paintings, violins and mummies

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO**7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.**

The NMR-MOUSE is a commercial product of Magritek holding and is being produced by Magritek GmbH in Aachen. Magritek GmbH is directed by Federico Casanova and Juan Perlo, who developed the instrument in the EU-ARTECH project. The company has expanded since and leads the world market in producing tabletop NMR spectrometers for chemical analysis.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Reference

C. Rehorn, B. Blümich, "Cultural Heritage Studies with Mobile NMR", *Angewandte Chemie* **57**(25), pp. 7304-7412 (2018), DOI: 10.1002/anie.201713009, IF=12.102, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.201713009>, OA = N

High IF publication or series of publications

General description of the contents

This publication reviews how the NMR-MOUSE, the compact MRI sensor developed in this consortium, works and where it is being employed in heritage science.

The novelty of the communication

This is the first time that the NMR-MOUSE is described and its applications are summarized for the heritage science community. The publication is in a special issue of the most prominent European chemistry journal "Angewandte Chemie".

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

This manuscript summarizes the function of the NMR-MOUSE and the applications which are relevant to heritage science. Many different studies have been performed over more than 15 years, but only some of them are of value for routine analysis. Examples of these are presented in the mini-review. Angewandte Chemie is one of the prime Chemistry Journals worldwide. The fact that this manuscript was accepted in the special edition on Cultural Heritage underlines the recognition which the NMR-MOUSE is receiving in the heritage science community.

Accounts of Chemical Research: Special issue on Advanced Techniques in Art Conservation

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Reference

- Advanced Techniques in Art Conservation; B. Giovanni Brunetti, A. Sgamellotti; Acc. Chem. Res., 2010, 43 (6), pp 693–694; DOI: 10.1021/ar100072f
- In Situ Noninvasive Study works: The MOLAB Multitechnique Approach; C. Miliani, F. Rosi, B. Giovanni Brunetti, Antonio Sgamellotti; Acc. Chem. Res., 2010, 43 (6), pp 728–738; DOI: 10.1021/ar100010t
- Noninvasive Testing and Cultural Heritage by Mobile NMR; Bernhard Blümich, Federico Casanova, Juan Perlo, Federica Presciutti, Chiara Anselmi, Brenda Doherty; Acc. Chem. Res., 2010,

High IF publication or series of publications

43 (6), pp 761–770; DOI: 10.1021/ar900277h

- New Advances in the Application of FTIR Microscopy and Spectroscopy for the Characterization of Historic Materials; S. Prati, E. Joseph, G. Sciutto and R. Mazzeo; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 43 (6), pp 792–801; DOI: 10.1021/ar900274f
- Structural Examination of Easel Paintings with Optical Coherence Tomography; Piotr Targowski, Magdalena Iwanicka, Ludmiła Tymińska-Widmer, Marcin Sylwestrzak, Ewa A. Kwiatkowska; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 43 (6), pp 826–836; DOI: 10.1021/ar900195d
- Fluorescence Spectroscopy: A Powerful Technique for the Noninvasive Characterization work; Aldo Romani, Catia Clementi, Costanza Miliani, Gianna Favaro, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 43 (6), pp 837–846; DOI: 10.1021/ar900291y
- Scanning Multispectral IR Reflectography SMIRR: An Advanced Tool for Art Diagnostics; Claudia Daffara, Enrico Pampaloni, Luca Pezzati, Marco Barucci, Raffaella Fontana; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 43 (6), pp 847–856; DOI: 10.1021/ar900268t
- Immunodetection of Proteins in Ancient Paint Media; Laura Cartechini, Manuela Vagnini, Melissa Palmieri, Lucia Pitzurra, Tommaso Mello, Joy Mazurek, Giacomo Chiari; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, 43 (6), pp 867–876; DOI: 10.1021/ar900279d

General description of the contents

New noninvasive and microsampling analytical techniques more effectively guide the assessment and conservation of historical artifacts and works .

The novelty of the communication

Peer-review articles.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

High Impact factor ($IF_{2010} = 21.8$) ensures the high visibility of published articles.

Conservation and Revelation of the Ghent Altarpiece

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The rediscovery of Jan van Eyck, ' King of Painters'

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Several press releases and conferences have been organised in the framework of the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece:

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PersberichtGhentAltarpiece_EN_V2.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PressRelease_KIK-IRPA_GhentAltarpiece_27June2013.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2014.06.20_Press_kit_Ghent_Altarpiece.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/12-10-2016_Press_Lam_Gods.pdf

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Persbericht%20Lam%20Gods%209%20nov%202017%20EN.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Dossier%20de%20presse%20Jan%20van%20Eyck%20en%20lign e%202011%20jan%202018.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2018.06.19%20Press%20kit%20Ghent%20Altarpiece%20EN.pdf>

The website [closetovaneyck www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be](http://www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be), launched in 2011 and regularly updated, is a pioneering example of open-access resources for technical art history and conservation.

This has also been echoed in the press.

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Ghent%20Altarpiece%20-%20Web%20site%20-%20Press%20rel ease%20-%20July%207%202011%20-%20EN.pdf>

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/GhentAltarpiecewebsite_PressRelease.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The website “closer to van Eyck” (<http://closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be>) is financially supported by the

High IF publication or series of publications

Getty Foundation. It is a pioneering tool in the presentation of conservation-restoration process and a model for open access. The conservation is financed by the Flemish government (80%) and the Baillet-Latout Fund (20%). Research for conservation is carried out by KIK-IRPA in collaboration with the Universities of Ghent and Antwerp and has benefitted from sponsorship from the Gieskes-Strijbis Fund. Punctual analytical expertise have been provided by scientists from the Nicolaus Copernicus University (Toruń) and the National Gallery (Washington).

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Reference

G. Van der Snickt, H. Dubois, J. Sanyova, S. Legrand, A. Coudray, C. Glaude, M. Postec, P. Van Espen, and K. Janssens, 'Large-Area Elemental Imaging Reveals Van Eyck's Original Paint Layers on the Ghent Altarpiece (1432), Rescoping Its Conservation Treatment' *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 2017, 56 (17), pp. 4797–4801 (2017) IF=12.102; <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201702702>, OA = Y

General description of the contents

The interpretation of XRF scans of the Ghent altarpiece permitted to evaluate the condition of the original paint layers which were covered by opaque overpaint since the middle of the sixteenth century. It played a considerable role in the decision making towards the removal of the overpaint and reveal Van Eyck's paintings.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

MA-XRF scanning is one of the most innovative scientific imaging techniques in the field of CH. It is non-invasive, and combined by punctual analysis of paint samples in the laboratory, is leading to extraordinary revelations on artistic techniques and material alterations. It is extremely useful for conservation scientists, conservators and gives clear visual results which can be readily explained to the public.

Book (a chapter of the book)

Chemistry for restoration. Painting and restoration materials

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Reference

Mauro Matteini, Rocco Mazzeo, Arcangelo Moles, Chemistry for restoration. Painting and restoration materials, Nardini, 2016, 8840444505, 9788840444505

General description of the contents

This chemistry book dedicated to conservation and restoration aims at communicating and transferring to this field specifically addressed and targeted notions and concepts, without losing sight of a high scientific level.

Book (a chapter of the book)

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

We consider the production of a specific book addressing all general and applied issues of chemistry, the “alien” scientific discipline primarily involved in conservation, instrumental in collecting and organising the many experiences and advancements that during recent decades have often been accumulated in a disorganised manner. Of course this book is also useful in addressing educational and training needs. Today, schools of conservation and restoration are present all over the world. Young students who choose this type of professional activity should be trained, from the very beginning, within the typical interdisciplinary environment that characterizes the conservation of cultural heritage.

Analytical Chemistry for Cultural Heritage

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Reference

Rocco Mazzeo, Analytical Chemistry for Cultural Heritage., Springer, 2017, 978-3-319-52804-5

General description of the contents

The book is a collection of review articles, which provide a wide overview of very different analytical techniques applied to cultural heritage addressing a number of applications concerning archaeological materials, paintings and artwork. In every review article, an up-to-date reference list gives the reader the opportunity for further, more specialist reading.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The book collects the most advanced methods that can be used to study cultural objects and is addressed to established scientists and graduate students, and in general to those who are responsible

Book (a chapter of the book)

for research in the cultural heritage field

Scientific Examination for the Investigation of Paintings, A Handbook for Conservators-restorers

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Reference

D. Pinna; M. Galeotti, R.Mazzeo Scientific Examination for the Investigation of Paintings, A Handbook for Conservators-restorers, Centro Di, 2010, 8870384581224

General description of the contents

This volume, a friendly-consulting handbook, stems from professionals involved in the European project EU-ARTECH to address a particular need in the field of scientific analyses applied to cultural heritage conservation. The handbook is specifically addressed to conservator-restorers to illustrate the role played by scientific examinations in the investigation of panel and canvas paintings by explaining some analytical techniques - what they are and why they are used, what are their limits,

Book (a chapter of the book)

and what kind of effects/results they are expected to supply.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The book is organised with a problem solving approach in order to support restorers in the choice of the type of analytical investigation most useful for their needs.

A textbook about neutrons for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE
- other:

comments: The book “Neutron Methods for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage summarizes the 20 years long experiences of the Budapest Neutron Centre in the field

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

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Book (a chapter of the book)

Reference

- Zs. Kasztovszky, V. Szilágyi, K. T. Biró, J. Zöldföldi, M. I. Dias, A. Valera, E. Abraham, M. Bessou, F. LoCelso, V. Benfante, *Ceramics, Marbles and Stones in the Light of Neutrons: Characterization by Various Neutron Methods*, in: N. Kardjilov, G. Festa (Eds), *Neutron Methods for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2017, 89-140, ISBN 978-3-319-33161-4
- Z. Kis, L. Szentmiklósi, R. Schulze, E. Abraham, *Prompt Gamma Activation Imaging (PGAI)*, in: N. Kardjilov, G. Festa (Eds), *Neutron Methods for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2017, 303-320, ISBN 978-3-319-33161-4

General description of the contents

The book provides an extensive overview of the application of neutron characterization techniques in cultural heritage to a broad audience and will be of interest to both scientists and non-scientists in the field.

The first section of the book is dedicated to stories describing spectacular discoveries brought about by the use of neutron techniques in a range of applications. The second section covers the experimental techniques in appropriate detail: basic principles, limitations and fields of application.

The novelty of the book (the chapter)

Neutrons, due to their weak interactions with materials, provide a penetrating, but non-invasive probe of bulk properties. They allow the characterization of the composition and mechanical properties of materials, helping to answer questions related to the dating, the manufacturing process or the state of degradation effects. They allow detailed interrogation of the internal structures of objects that may be otherwise hidden from view.

In the chapter “Ceramics, Marbles and Stones in the Light of Neutrons”, we give examples of Cultural Heritage studies with the applications of neutron-based methods, performed at the Budapest Neutron Centre.

In the chapter “Prompt Gamma Activation Imaging (PGAI)” we give a description of a new methodology, developed at the Budapest Neutron Centre.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Archaeologists, palaeontologists, restaurateurs and conservators, historians and collectors will be fascinated by the wealth of information that can be obtained using neutron techniques, while material scientists and engineers will find details of the experimental techniques and materials properties that can be determined.

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Advanced Characterization Techniques, Diagnostic Tools and Evaluation Methods in Heritage Science

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Some of the most innovative analytical techniques for heritage science, as presented in the 1st IPERION CH Doctoral School, compiled in a single volume for reference of users and future heritage scientists.

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Emilio

surname: Cano

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e-mail: ecano@cenim.csic.es contact phone: +

Reference

David M. Bastidas and Emilio Cano (Eds.), *Advanced Characterization Techniques, Diagnostic Tools and Evaluation Methods in Heritage Science*, Springer, 2018, ISBN 978-3-319-75315-7 ISBN 978-3-319-75316-4 (eBook), 978-3-319-75316-4 (eBook), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75316-4>

General description of the contents

The book gives an overview of the fundamentals and applications of novel and advanced techniques for the study of cultural heritage assets, its conservation condition and the evaluation of different conservation treatments. This book compiles lectures from the 1st IPERION CH Doctoral Summer School on “Advanced Characterization Techniques, Diagnostic Tools and Evaluation Methods in Heritage Science”, held in Madrid from 12th to 15th July 2016.

The book chapters describe the use of electrochemical techniques in conservation science, with a particular focus on its application for on-site measurement; the capabilities of the nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) analysis by means of the innovative portable NMR mouse sensor in the assessment and preservation of soft heritage materials, such as wood, parchment, bone, and painted walls, or the application of optical coherence tomography (OCT) and its usefulness to obtain cross sections in a non-invasive way, the application of multispectral infrared reflectography for data collection from underlayers in paintings and other materials is presented, and its advantages over traditional wide-band reflectography are discussed; the capabilities of high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to UV–VIS diode array detector and tandem mass spectrometry detectors as quadrupole–time of flight (HPLC-DAD-QTOF) for the analysis of different organic components and a novel image analysis technique based on Fourier transform to precisely characterize, count threats and compare painting canvases.

The novelty of the book (the chapter)

The techniques and methodologies described in the book have been developed and/or improved by IPERION-CH partners, specifically for cultural heritage. Techniques described in chapters 3, 4 and 5 are already part of IPERION-CH/E-RIHS facilities, while the other techniques are being developed and evaluated to its future integration in E-RIHS services.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The relevance of the book is being the first time several innovative techniques, developed and offered through IPERION CH access services or considered for the future infrastructures, are presented in a single academic text. While detailed description of them and their capabilities had already been published in specialized scientific journals, this book present them in a single volume with an academic approach. This book aims to be useful both as reference for tentative users of these techniques (scientists, conservators, curators, etc.) and as training textbook for conservation scientists.

Contents

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Conservation and Revelation of the Ghent Altarpiece –

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The rediscovery of Jan van Eyck, 'King of Painters'

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Several press releases and conferences have been organised in the framework of the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece:

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PersberichtGhentAltarpiece_EN_V2.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PressRelease_KIK-IRPA_GhentAltarpiece_27June2013.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2014.06.20_Press_kit_Ghent_Altarpiece.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/12-10-2016_Press_Lam_Gods.pdf

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Persbericht%20Lam%20Gods%209%20nov%202017%20EN.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Dossier%20de%20presse%20Jan%20van%20Eyck%20en%20lign e%202011%20jan%202018.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2018.06.19%20Press%20kit%20Ghent%20Altarpiece%20EN.pdf>

The website [closetovaneyck www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be](http://www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be), launched in 2011 and regularly updated, is a pioneering example of open-access resources for technical art history and conservation.

This has also been echoed in the press.

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Ghent%20Altarpiece%20-%20Web%20site%20-%20Press%20rel ease%20-%20July%207%202011%20-%20EN.pdf>

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/GhentAltarpiecewebsite_PressRelease.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The website “closer to van Eyck” (<http://closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be>) is financially supported by the

Book (a chapter of the book)

Getty Foundation. It is a pioneering tool in the presentation of conservation-restoration process and a model for open access. The conservation is financed by the Flemish government (80%) and the Baillet-Latout Fund (20%). Research for conservation is carried out by KIK-IRPA in collaboration with the Universities of Ghent and Antwerp and has benefitted from sponsorship from the Gieskes-Strijbis Fund. Punctual analytical expertise have been provided by scientists from the Nicolaus Copernicus University (Toruń) and the National Gallery (Washington).

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Reference

C. Currie, B. Fransen, V. Henderiks, C. Stroo, D. Vanwijnsberghe (Eds.), *Van Eyck Studies. Papers presented at the Eighteenth symposium for the Study of Underdrawing and Technology in Paintings*, Brussels, 19-21 September 2012, Leuven, Peeters, 2016

Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium – Institut royal du Patrimoine artistique, *Restauration/Revelatie. De buitenluiken van het Lam Gods. Restauration/Révélation. Les volets extérieurs de l'Agneau mystique. Restoration/Revelation. The exterior wings of the Ghent Altarpiece*, Ghent (Provincial Culture Center Caermersklooster), 2017. ISBN: 9789074311960

General description of the contents

The Book “Van Eyck Studies” is the proceedings of a conference on the art of Hubert and Jan van Eyck took organized in Brussels by the KIK-IRPA and the Centre for the Study of the Flemish Primitives in collaboration with the Laboratoire d'étude des œuvres d'art par des méthodes scientifiques (Université catholique de Louvain-la-Neuve), and Illuminare - Centre for the Study of Medieval Art (Katholieke Universiteit Leuven) (19-21 September 2012).

The book sheds new light on complex topics such as attribution, iconography and painting technique. through thirty-seven papers presented at the symposium and

The book *Restauration/Revelation* gives a scientifically based, yet well accessible to the public of the research and conservation of the outer panels of the Ghent Altarpiece (2012-2016).

The novelty of the book (the chapter)

The books provide state-of-the-art knowledge on one of the most important artists of late medieval Western Europe painters and on the ongoing complex conservation of his greatest masterpiece.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

“Van Eyck Studies” is relevant for the conservation and scientific communities because it oversees the crucial historical material alterations, their impact on conservation and on art historical interpretations, It was a prerequisite for the conservation project.

The book “*Restauration/Revelation*” is very useful for the general public since it gives a clear and well-illustrated insight into the conservation of this very important masterpiece and into the research methodology involved. The societal relevance resides in the clear communication on this complex conservation project and its impact on the appearance of the altarpiece. Communication is

essential to avoid misunderstandings and disturbing public controversies.

Conference branded under one of CH projects

The workshop “The Painting Technique of Pietro Vannucci, called Il Perugino” with a dedicated publication

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release**
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)**
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

Did you know that Renaissance painters were used to mix lake pigments with powdered glass?

Detailed examinations of paint layers of Renaissance masters revealed that painters were used to mix uncolored powdered glass to red lakes and other pigments. This was done to give body to the brush strokes, to ensure transparency of the painted layer, and to reduce the drying time of siccative oil. The discovery emerged in a conference organised by the R.I. project LabS TECH (Laboratories on Science and Technology for the European Cultural Heritage), supported by the European Commission within the 5th FP. LabS TECH is a consortium which joins together European institutions developing research on science applied to the study and conservation works.

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. **May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:**

- academic**
- economic
- societal**

6. **Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links**

After the conference, organised within the networking activities of Eu-ARTECH, a book of proceedings was published fully dedicated to the execution techniques of Pietro Vannucci called il Perugino (see below).

Interest in the workshop was manifested by the *Soprintendenza ai Beni A.P.P.S.A.D dell’Umbria* (Italian Ministry of Cultural Heritage), such that its results were presented in the technical section of the great exhibition on “Perugino, il divin pittore”, held at the Galleria Nazionale dell’Umbria (February 25th-September 5th, 2004). The exhibition registered more than 200.000 visitors.

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

An outstanding demonstration of the usefulness of cooperation among European research institutions within the networking activities of LabS TECH.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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Conference details:

Name of the conference: **Workshop “The Painting Technique of Pietro Vannucci, called Il Perugino”**

Location: **Perugia, Conference Room of the Galleria Nazionale dell’Umbria**

Daily dates: **April 14th–15th 2003**

Organiser: **LabS TECH Infrastructure Cooperation Network (B.G.Brunetti Coordinator)**

Branded under project: **LabS-TECH.**

Number of participants: **around 80**

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:

Book entitled: The Painting Technique of Pietro Vannucci called Il Perugino, Proceedings of the LabS TECH Workshop. B.G. Brunetti, C. Seccaroni and A. Sgamellotti Eds.. Quaderni di Kermes, Nardini Editore, Firenze, 2004.

General description of the subject:

At the moment of the conference, several scientific studies on Perugino’s paintings had been carried out in several laboratories in Europe and extended new information was available. However, most results were not published.

The workshop was organised within LabS TECH with the objectives:

- (a) to increase and stimulate cooperation and exchange of data among European laboratories;
- (b) to show how cooperation among European institution can be fruitful, reconstructing as much as possible the painting technique of the great Master, via integration of data obtained by different laboratories;
- (c) to offer conservator-restorers new knowledge on technical practices of Renaissance painters.

The results presented by contributors were outstanding and even surprising, because showed unexpected recurrent instances in the use of materials that were not previously considered as part of the traditional painter’s palette of the 1500s. For example, Perugino’s consistent use of finely ground uncoloured powdered glass mixed into the red lakes in oil paintings was an absolute new discovery. In particular, the use of glass mixed to red lakes was found to be recurrent in Perugino’s oil paintings beginning in 1490, as confirmed by the results separately obtained by the Scientific Department of the National Gallery of London, by the French laboratories of C2RMF in Paris, and through the non-destructive XRF studies carried out by ENEA (partly in cooperation with University of Perugia and CNR-ISTM) on about 60 paintings executed by Perugino throughout his career.

It also emerged that the use of powdered glass was not limited to lake pigments. Some evidence of

Conference branded under one of CH projects

the presence of uncoloured powdered glass was also found in other pigments or primings, as reported by the National Gallery and confirmed by the *Soprintendenza* of Bologna. Other than the use in lakes, where the powdered glass may also be present to add body and transparency to the paint film, it seemed likely that it was used as a siccativo for the oil.

Another interesting new finding concerned the use of finely-ground metal powder, or the use of ground minerals with a metallic lustre, to achieve specific effects in grey tones. In relation to the altarpiece of the *Certosa di Pavia* in the National Gallery, the presence of tin-rich bronze filings, a specific alloy that may well have been white or grey in colour was found; to date, this use is unique and has not been found in any other easel painting from the period. This tin-rich bronze powder could be placed in the same category of pigments as metallic bismuth, stibnite, and galena, which were in use by Perugino's contemporaries and, in the case of stibnite, by Perugino himself.

Relation to the CH projects:

The LabS TECH Network was the official organiser of the event. Main intent was to show participants, stakeholders, policy makers and public how exchange of knowledge, best practices and data among research institutions can be profitable to achieve better results in heritage studies and conservation.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The workshop was attended by scientists, conservators, and art-historians, belonging to the LabS TECH institutions, such as INSTM (*Consorzio per la Scienza e Tecnologia dei Materiali*), C2RMF (*Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France*), NGL (National Gallery of London), and OPD (*Opificio delle Pietre Dure*), as well as to other prestigious institutions, such as the *Musei Vaticani*, the *Soprintendenza ai Beni A.P.P.S.A.D. dell'Umbria*, the *Unita' tecnico-scientifica "Materiali e Nuove Tecnologie"* of ENEA, the *Istituto Nazionale di Ottica Applicata*, INOA, the *Soprintendenza di Bologna*, the Centre SMAArt of the University of Perugia, and the *Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Molecolari, ISTM, of CNR*.

The outcome of the conference opened up new horizons in technical art history. In fact, it early appeared that almost all the newly identified aspects of the Perugino's painting technique were valid also for many of his contemporaries.

The results of the conference were presented to the public through a series of technical panels at the great exhibition "Perugino, il Divin Pittore" dedicated to Pietro Vannucci, held at the National Gallery of Umbria from February 28th to September 5th, 2004. The exhibition registered more than 200.000 visitors!.

A related book

Reference

B. Brunetti, C. Seccaroni and A. Sgamellotti Eds., *The Painting Technique of Pietro Vannucci, called Il Perugino*, Proceedings of the LabS-TECH Workshop held in Perugia on 13-14 April 2003, Firenze, Editore Nardini, 2004.

General description of the contents

The book contains a series of 10 papers all dedicated to the execution techniques of Perugino in panel paintings exhibited at the National Gallery of London, at the Palais du Louvre and other French collections, at the Galleria Nazionale dell'Umbria, at the Pinacoteca of Bologna and of Citta' di Castello, as well as the mural paintings of the Sistine Chapel in Vatican. Among the

various original contributions, results can be mentioned regarding: (a) a study of the preparation of gesso layers and *imprimitura*, with the identification of specific tools (as a slice with teeth of variable depth and width) for scraping and rasping possible unevenness or roughness in the gesso surface; (b) the identification of tin-rich bronze filings to give grey or light grey hues in paint layers or a specific brown ochre with an anomalous content of zinc impurities that, being used by the master only in the last years of his career, can be exploited for *ante-* or *post-quem* dating; (c) underdrawings characterized by frequent and substantial pentimenti, indicating the painter's care and accuracy in achieving the best compositional and pictorial results, a fact that contrast with the Vasari's substantially negative historical portrait of Perugino; (d) the study of the Sistine Chapel showing that Perugino, more than the other painters of the group in the 1480s, used complementary colours in fresco technique before the final application of some other pigments very frequently applied in tempera or in oil.

The book content was of great relevance for academicians (technical art history) and for restorers, who learned important new details on use of materials by Renaissance painters.

The novelty of the book

New important aspects of the Perugino painting technique were highlighted. The use of glass powder mixed to red lakes or of grinded metals or alloys, such as bronze, were never reported before and shed new light not only on Perugino way of painting but, more generally, on the techniques of the Florentine painters of the end 1400 and beginning 1500.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

At the time of publication of the book, materials such as powdered glass, metal filings, or grounded minerals having a lustre, were not reported or were rarely mentioned in the literature regarding the Renaissance painting techniques. In particular, it was reported that Perugino mixed glass powder to red lakes starting from 1490 onward, a detail that can be used for dating of paintings. In the book it was shown that these materials were used not only by Perugino, but also by other painters, contemporary to him (see the results of National Gallery, C2RMF, and ENEA). The identification of all these materials in Florentine easel paintings of the 1500s greatly helped in better understanding how information on the properties and use of materials as glass, minerals and metals was circulated among artists during the Renaissance, showing a continual osmosis of knowledge among painters, glass manufacturers, ceramists and foundrymen.

For all these reasons the book is an important witness of the great usefulness of exchange and cooperation among research institutions in Europe, a mandatory pathway towards the achievement of high-level results, otherwise impossible or hard to be achieved.

The 'Raphael's Painting Technique: Working Practices before Rome' with a publication

2. **Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience**

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. **Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –**

4. **Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:**

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH**
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. **May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:**

- academic**
- economic
- societal**

6. **Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO**

7. **Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.**

A conference within the networking activities of the EU-ARTECH project. A workshop organized at the National Gallery in London on 11th November 2004

8. **Person to be contacted for details**

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surname: **Spring**

institution: **The National Gallery of London**

e-mail: **marika.spring@ng-london.ac.uk** contact phone: +

A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: **Raphael's Painting Technique: Working Practices before Rome**

Location: **The National Gallery of London.**

Daily dates: **11th November 2004**

Organiser: **The National Gallery of London**

Conference branded under one of CH projects

Branded under project: **EU-ARTECH**

Number of participants: **around 200**

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:

A book of Proceedings was published. See the voice: **A book.**

General description of the subject:

The workshop coincided with the great exhibition entitled: 'Raphael: From Urbino to Rome' (London, 20th October 2004- 16th January 2005) and attracted around 200 participants among the international community of conservators, heritage scientists, curators, scholars, and students. The audience heard 11 presentations by eminent authorities from Italy, France, Britain and the United States, belonging to institutions internal and external to the EU-ARTECH consortium.

Several papers combined discussion of painting materials and techniques with aspects of the conservation needs and treatments of paintings, as notably for the Raphael's famous *Madonna del Cardellino* in the Galleria degli Uffizi. The wide-ranging technical survey of C2RMF on Raphael's paintings in French museums included new results centred on infra-red and radiographic investigations. Contributions from the Opificio delle Pietre Dure (OPD) and CNR-INOA continued the theme of design and evolution of Raphael's compositions relying on digital infra-red multispectral scanning of paintings and other imaging techniques. Many of the works dealt with materials in the paint layers through non-invasive in situ analysis with portable XRF and micro-Raman spectroscopy, including the MOLAB equipment. Presentations by the National Gallery included recent re-evaluation of the underdrawings in Raphael's early pictures in the collection of London, new discoveries on Raphael's materials and their relationship to other sixteenth-century pictures and an account of the painting technique of Raphael's *Madonna of the Pinks*. The development of Raphael's later painting practice was examined in papers on the *Alba Madonna*, now in Washington, *Santa Cecilia* from Bologna and the *Baglioni altarpiece* in Rome.

The use of finely ground colourless manganese-containing glass, reported for the first time at the previous Perugia workshop (Perugia, 2003), was found in virtually all the examinations, confirming that Raphael and many artists of the period added powdered glass to their paint (in lakes and other contexts), most likely as a siccativ. One of the studies from the National Gallery showed that in Italy it was already used by Raphael's father, Giovanni Santi and by Justus of Ghent who was working in Urbino in the same period. Other examples from the Netherlands, Germany and France, were presented. In paintings from Northern Europe the use of powdered glass was extended back as far as 1432, since it is present in the famous Jan van Eyck's *Arnolfini Portrait*. Interestingly, painters appeared to have used local glass, reflected in differences in the composition that can be determined by elemental analysis. For this reason, it was concluded that this feature could be taken as indication of geographical origin of a painting, in much the same way that a chalk ground in Renaissance paintings is usually an indication of a Northern European origin, while gesso is typical of the Mediterranean area.

Ground bismuth metal powder was found in several paintings by Raphael. Through the close cooperation of the contributors both before and after the workshop, we know that other painters of the period also used bismuth, as well as other similar materials which can be used as dark grey pigments such as stibnite and galena. Each institution had discovered only a few occurrences of these materials, making it difficult to determine why they were used, but when placed together it seems clear that the artists were experimenting with novel grey pigments at this time, most probably through exchange of materials with other crafts such as glass making and pottery.

Relation to the CH projects:

The opportunity to collect together and discuss the data dispersed among the institutions involved in the Eu-ARTECH network, or having contact with it, proved particularly valuable. It was immediately clear that the methodologies and interpretation of results had benefited from the close cooperation

of the institutions.

Another important aspect was that the organization of events like this one, in proximity of great exhibition, provided a formidable opportunity for dissemination of results from MOLAB examinations, i.e. the access to mobile equipment, offered for the first time to European researchers within EU-ARTECH.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The workshop was attended by around 200 people, including scientists, conservators and curators, internal and external to the EU-ARTECH consortium, belonging to: 15 public institutions, such as Conservation Departments or Studios of United Kingdom, Italy, Finland, Germany, Portugal, USA; 7 Universities of different countries such as Sweden, United Kingdom, Netherland, Italy; 3 specialised European Journals (The Burlington Magazine, UK; Il Giornale dell'Arte, IT; Kermes, IT); several SME's (21 private restorers were present). The event was very successful for the following reasons:

- (a) the opportunity to collect together and discuss the data dispersed among European (and global) heritage institutions was demonstrated to be extremely effective in enhancing the quality of research, with the achievement of results otherwise impossible;
- (b) a stronger interdisciplinary interaction of heritage scientists with conservators, restorers, and curators was finally achieved, together with the promotion of exchange of skills and methodologies among institutions;
- (c) the use of the most advanced investigation techniques was diffused among users of different disciplines (from art to science) and the access program of EU-ARTECH demonstrated to be an effective profitable opportunity for all heritage professionals;
- (d) the newly acquired knowledge represented a substantial step ahead in technical art history, not only concerning the Raphael working practice, but also that of his contemporaries.

The results of the workshop were presented in the book entitled **Raphael's Painting Technique: Working Practices before Rome, published by Nardini Editore Firenze**

Programme of the conference

9.00-10.00am Registration

Morning session
Chair; Ashok Roy

10.00-10.05am **Welcome**

10.05-10.35 *Raphael's paintings in French museums: some new results from recent technical investigations*

Bruno Mottin, Elisabeth Martin, Eric Laval (Centre de Recherche et de Restauration des Musées de France, Paris)

10.35-11.05 *Raphael's 'Madonna del Cardellino': The Conservation Project*

Marco Ciatti and Patrizia Riitano (Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Florence)

11.05-11.35 **Coffee**

11.35-12.05 *Design, Raphael before 1509: technical examination of some paintings in*

Conference branded under one of CH projects

	<i>central Italy</i> Claudio Seccaroni, P. Moioli (ENEA, Rome) B. Brunetti, C. Ricci, F. Rosi, I. Borgia (Centre SMAArt University of Perugia), C. Miliani, Sgamellotti (CNR-ISTM University of Perugia)
12.05-12.35	<i>Design, Elaboration and Technique in Raphael's Underdrawing</i> Roberto Bellucci and Cecilia Frosinini (Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Florence)
12.35-12.50	<i>Optical analyses of Raphael's paintings</i> Luca Pezzati, R. Fontana, M.C. Gambino, M. Materazzi, E. Pampaloni and P. Poggi
12.50-2.15 pm	Lunch
<u>Afternoon Session</u> <u>Chair; Carol Plazzotta</u>	
2.15-3.00	<i>Recent Research on the Early Paintings by Raphael in the National Gallery, London:</i> - <i>Study of the paintings by infrared reflectography</i> Rachel Billinge (National Gallery, London) - <i>Raphael's materials: some new discoveries and their context within early sixteenth-century painting</i> Marika Spring (National Gallery, London)
-	<i>The re-emergence of The Madonna of the Pinks</i> Ashok Roy (National Gallery, London)
3.00-3.30	<i>The study of Raphael's early paintings: re-analysis of cross-sections in the scientific laboratory of the Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Florence</i> Giancarlo Lanterna, C. Lalli (Opificio delle Pietre Dure, Florence), B. Brunetti (Centre SMAArt University of Perugia), C. Miliani, A. Sgamellotti (CNR-ISTM, University of Perugia)
3.30-4.00	Tea
4.00-4.30	<i>Raphael's 'Alba Madonna'</i> Barbara Berrie (National Gallery, Washington)
4.30-4.45	<i>Raphael's 'Saint Cecilia' in Bologna: New Data on the Genesis and the Materials</i> Claudio Seccaroni (ENEA, Rome), Ilaria Borgia (University of Perugia), Diego Cauzzi (Soprintendenza P.S.A.D di Bologna), Bruno Radicati (CNR-IFAC, Florence)
4.45-5.15	Questions and Close

“3D Imaging in Cultural Heritage” Conference at the British Museum, 2017

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

A conference on 3D Imaging in Cultural Heritage, funded by IPERION CH, was held at the British Museum on the 9-10 November 2017. The conference brought together experts in a variety of 3D imaging techniques, and demonstrated the myriad ways in which they are now implemented in archaeological and cultural heritage research, education, public engagement and accessibility

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Daniel

surname: O’Flynn

institution: The British Museum

e-mail: doflynn@britishmuseum.org contact phone: + +44 207 323 8980

A conference

Fill-in if you organised or co-organised a conference branded under one of CH projects.

Conference details:

Name of the conference: 3D Imaging in Cultural Heritage

Location: The British Museum

Daily dates: 9-10 November 2017

Organiser: Daniel O'Flynn

Branded under project: IPERION CH, D "WP9. NA2 –Task 9.1 Knowledge exchange activities Cooperation and networking"

Number of participants: 250 (approx.)

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue: N/A

General description of the subject:

A conference on 3D Imaging in Cultural Heritage, funded by IPERION CH, was held at the British Museum on the 9-10 November 2017. The conference brought together experts in a variety of 3D imaging techniques, and demonstrated the myriad ways in which they are now implemented in archaeological and cultural heritage research, education, public engagement and accessibility

Relation to the CH projects:

The project was related to IPERION CH WP9. NA2 –Task 9.1 Knowledge exchange activities Cooperation and networking. The IPERION CH logo was used throughout the conference media (e.g. programme, list of abstracts, cover slide for conference). The conference consisted of 43 presentations (unknown how many directly related to IPERION CH)

specify, how the conference was related to the CH projects (e.g. presentation of results of a WP, financed by the project, preparation phase etc.), how the project's brand was exposed? Estimate, how many presentations were directly related to the project?

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

One of the key benefits of the conference was the bringing together of an audience of highly varied disciplines, including archaeologists, art historians, physicists, engineers, software developers and visual media producers. This gave the opportunity for attendees to see the different perspectives of the presenters, as well as to discover new advances in technology, and how they are being applied across the broad spectrum of cultural heritage. This diversity was reflected in the conference programme, with talks given by (for example), university lecturers, curators (from regional and national museums) and experimental scientists. Companies were present in the conference foyer area demonstrating the display and use of 3D models (Sketchfab), 3D implementation in the British Museum (Soluis Heritage), and new 3D imaging equipment (Cyreal)

The three keynote talks delivered at the conference reflected high profile uses of 3D imaging technology: Michael Scott (Professor of Classics and Ancient History, University of Warwick) discussed how laser scanning was used to uncover secrets of historic cities, as he presented in the BBC TV programmes "Italy's Invisible Cities" and "Ancient Invisible Cities". Daniel Antoine (Curator of Physical Anthropology, The British Museum) spoke about the use of X-ray CT scanning in exploring the ancient lives of Egyptian mummies, and the use of the scans in a permanent gallery in the Museum, as well as in a high profile exhibition at the Museum and subsequent touring exhibitions across the world. Alex Ball (Head of Imaging and Analysis, Natural History Museum) discussed the challenges of 3D imaging of material over a wide range of sizes and resolutions, and the correlation of different methods – applied across material from the Natural History Museum as well as material from other museums and research institutions.

The conference was actively discussed on Twitter throughout, using the hashtag #IPBM3D.

IAEA technical meeting on developing strategies for safe analysis of paintings and paint materials

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Ineke

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e-mail: i.joosten@cultureelerfgoed.nl. contact phone: +31611455626

A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: IAEA technical meeting on developing strategies for safe analysis of paintings and paint materials

Location: Ateliergebouw, Amsterdam

Daily dates: 27-30 June 2017

Organiser: Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands, IPANEMA, Rijksmuseum and IAEA

Branded under project: IPERION CH

Number of participants: 45

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue: No proceedings were published.....

General description of the subject:

Paintings are an important part of our world cultural heritage. Analytical techniques using intense photon, electron and ion beams produced by particle accelerators, synchrotrons, microscopes and other sources are increasingly being applied for their study. Whole paintings are scanned using X-ray methods at synchrotrons and in laboratory environments. Electron, Raman, X-ray and ion beam microscopies are widely applied to study both lateral and cross sections of paint samples to learn more about their complex composition, to construct painting biographies and to inform on degradation mechanisms. Analytical investigations are based on photon, electron and ion interactions with the material. Such material under irradiation, visible or non-visible, might induce visible or non-visible alterations during analysis which can be also permanent or temporary. The effects of irradiation depend both on the investigated materials and the experimental conditions. All these need to be taken into account as e.g. changes of local colour, structural, chemical, morphological can influence the analytical results. The consequences of the analyses in terms of radiation effects are insufficiently known. Radiation effects have been investigated for a long time in materials from life sciences to semiconductors. However, the main focus of such studies has been on pure materials and not on heterogeneous, complex and multi-layered systems like paintings. Several recent works have shown that interactions between pigments and binding media are likely to influence significantly material behaviour under irradiation. More specific, "pure" pigments are already complex mixtures containing traces phases, substitution elements and structural defects, which behaviour will deviate from standard chemicals. Therefore, to understand the radiation effects on paintings has utmost importance in order to minimize any possible alteration.

The meeting confirmed that the study of these samples with these techniques is broad and popular, providing valuable information. It was also confirmed the complexity of these samples from the point of view of composition material (generally a mix inorganic and organic materials), which will react to radiation in different ways, pointing out the wide modification mechanism involved. The reports presented a number of studies performed in the laboratories and museums equipped with particle accelerators, photon sources and laser beams. Special attention was paid to experimental conditions that can induce damage or alteration of the sample due to irradiation conditions. Discussions, first in the frame of working groups and then by the participants, about the need of a history radiation passport of the objects/samples was performed. It is necessary to collect this information to monitor the effects (immediate or future) of radiation in future, and also to limit the radiation exposure and avoid duplication of measurements. repetitive in their integrity. Very related with this topic, another working group was focused on damage prevention wizard, in an attempt to reduce the modifications induced in some materials, especially in the organics, as binders. Finally, other working group was dedicated to define a Round robin exercise where, jointly with the participants, were identified potential pigments and dyes (in mock-ups forms, aged mock-ups or real samples) to be studied. It was also discussion the need to diffuse and discuss these induced modifications at conferences and addressed to a broader public through international organizations, such as ICOM, ICCROM and UNESCO, and to link these concerns with the radiation effects in materials community.

Relation to the CH projects:

The conference was the direct result of WP6.4 *Safe boundaries for analysis of heritage materials*

Conference branded under one of CH projects

under intense radiation sources and a successful collaboration with the IAEA. Results from this workpackage were presented and many partners were involved. Around 11 presentations were related to the project.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The technical meeting was attended by 45 people from 10 different countries including scientists and conservators internal and external the IPERION CH consortium, belonging to: universities of different countries such as Portugal, the Netherlands and Italy, public institutions such as Conservation departments or studios from Germany, Croatia and the Netherlands, large scale facilities from Brazil, France, Hungary, Italy, Jordan and the United States of America. The meeting resulted in the development of a special pamphlet on SAFE EXAMINATION OF HERITAGE MATERIALS. Another result was the funding of a NICAS seed money project Irradiation Passport for Art.

Provide the programme of the conference

8 :30 – 9 :00	Registration
9 :00 – 9 :15	Opening addresses Robert van Langh , Netherlands Institute for Conservation, Art and Science (NICAS) Susan Lammers , Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands (RCE)
9 :15 – 9 :30	Hilde de Clercq International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property (ICCROM)
9 :30 – 9 :45	Loic Bertrand , Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage (IPERION CH) and European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science: a new way of approaching Heritage Science (E-RIHS)
9:45 – 10:00	Aliz Simon , International Atomic Agency (IAEA) Overview of the IAEA activities for Cultural Heritage Objectives and expected outcomes of the Technical Meeting Introduction of the Participants, Election of the Rapporteurs
10 :00 -10 :10	Mathieu Thoury , IPANEMA Report on previous activities
10 :10 – 10 :20	Ineke Joosten , RCE Theme of the meeting
10 :20 – 10 :50	Coffee break
SESSION 1A: IMPACT ON PURE ORGANIC PAINT	
10:50 – 11:30	Paul Jonkergouw , Radboud University, NI
11:30 – 11:50	Zita Szikszai , ATOMKI, HU Systematic investigation on ion beam effects on painted and unpainted parchment
11:50 – 12:10	Branka Mihaljevic , Radiation Chemistry and Dosimetry Laboratory (RCDL), CR Gamma irradiation of selected fungi on linen textile
12:10 – 12:30	Han Neevel , RCE, NL A study of the light degradation of some ink-related dyes on paper using μ -fading
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch Buffet
SESSION 2A: METHODOLOGIES	
13:30 – 14:10	Samual Webb , Stanford Synchrotron Radiation Lightsource (SSRL), SLAC National Laboratory, USA Characterization of X-ray Induced Beam Damage of Pigments
14:10 – 14:30	Raul Freitas , LNLS, BR Mitigating Radiation Damage on the Nanoscale – a Case for the Next Generation of Synchrotron Sources
14:30 – 14:50	Franco Zanini , Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste, IT Risk vs. danger perception in the analysis of cultural heritage

Conference branded under one of CH projects

14:50 – 15:10	Lambert van Eyck , Delft University of Technology, NL Neutrons Imaging: A gently probe to study the interior objects
15:10 – 15:40	Coffee break
SESSION 2B: METHODOLOGIES	
15:40 – 16:20	Sunil Sabharwal , IAEA, ORG – video conference Voluntary irradiation for treatment
16:20 – 16:40	Salvatore Siano , Istituto di Fisica Applicata “N. Carrara” – Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche IT Efficient and Thermally Controlled System for Safe Raman Spectroscopy
16:40 – 17:00	Annelies van Loon , Rijksmuseum, Mauritshuis, Delft University of Technology, NL Macro X-ray fluorescence (MA-XRF) scanning in the Rijksmuseum in-situ, considerations regarding safety
17:00 – 18:00	Visit the Rijksmuseum Eregerij
18:30	Drinks

Netherlands Institute for Conservation + Art + Science +

IAEA technical meeting on developing strategies for safe analysis of paintings and paint materials

27 - 30 June 2017

Location:
Rijksmuseum,
Amsterdam,
the Netherlands

TOPICS

- › irradiation effects during the analysis of easel and panel paintings, as well as dyed textiles
- › dose calculation tools for the irradiation of irregular and heterogeneous materials
- › irradiation effects and their mechanism
- › current practices in radiation analysis of heritage items
- › monitoring radiation-induced modifications: real-time and long-term
- › identify model samples and opportunities for a Round robin exercise to compare analytical results on damage formation from various techniques
- › outline a Damage Prevention Wizard (flow diagrams and atlas) and an Irradiation History Passport for heritage objects which are analysed

Further information: iaea.org | nicas-research.nl

Contacts: Aliz.simon@iaea.org | Ineke.joosten@cultureelerfgoed.nl | k.keune@rijksmuseum.nl | loic.bertrand@synchrotron-soleil.fr

Announcement of the technical meeting

Conference 'New Strategies for diagnostics of conservation treatments'

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

A two day conference on 'New strategies for diagnostics of conservation treatments' in Amsterdam with 166 attendees

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

It was a free conference open for everybody interested. It was interdisciplinary: stone, metals and paintings. In the morning the sessions were combined. In the afternoon parallel session. As an attendee you could choose where to participate. During lunch there was time for discussions, networking and there were posters about the techniques. Attendees could talk to the people behind the poster/technique.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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surname: Maarten

institution: University of Amsterdam

e-mail: m.r.vanbommel@uva.nl contact phone: + 31625534931

A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: New strategies for diagnostics of conservation treatments

Location: Amsterdam, the Netherlands

Daily dates: 7, 8 February 2019

Organiser: The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands

Branded under project: WP7 IPERION-CH

Number of participants: 166

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue: digital abstract book

General description of the subject:

Organized by The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands and sponsored by IPERION CH, the conference on 'New Diagnostic strategies for assessing the cleaning in conservation treatments', took place 7-8 February 2019 in Amsterdam. The conference was the result of IPERION CH activities in the work-package 7: 'New strategies for the diagnostics of conservation treatment'. It presented the results obtained within the different working groups in this work-package.

Relation to the CH projects:

The project aimed to develop sophisticated, primarily non-invasive analytical research strategies to guide the conservator in the assessment and evaluation of the cleaning of paintings, coatings of metal objects and consolidation of stone. This conference discussed practical aspects of application, potential and limitations of the techniques in addition to results of cleaning experiments on several case study's and mock-ups.

It was a free of charge one and a half day conference with parallel sessions on the cleaning of paintings, the coating of metal and the consolidation of stone. The presentations on the first day (see program) were all directly related to the project. The case studies, techniques and general strategy were presented. There were pitches on OCT, MA-XRF, IRR, FT-IR, Micro-drilling, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, drop wettability test, NMR_MOUSE, Terahertz time-domain reflectometry system and Micro-profilometry. Also, invited speakers gave lectures on these new methods of conservation used in practice (case-study) and their view on the use of these new techniques in the future .

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

IPERION-CH conference was an attempt to make conservators and scientists in the heritage field familiar with these relatively new 'high tech' devices. In the long term it is expected that the information obtained from this range of instrumentation will contribute to a better understanding of the consequences of current cleaning procedures and materials on paintings, metals and stone. The knowledge gained by this research and presented at the symposium will help improve the access of future users of the MOLAB infrastructure.

The IPERION CH conference was open to everybody working or studying in the field of conservation, restoration, science and conservation science and interested in new strategies for diagnostics of cleaning.

There is no website and there are no post-prints. Every participant received an abstract book beforehand. The conference was presented through the website of the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands and the IPERION website.

<https://cultureelerfgoed.nl/agenda/new-strategies-for-diagnostics-of-conservation-treatments>

Provide the programme of the conference

February 7, 2019

Aula, University of Amsterdam

Singel 411, Amsterdam

09:00 Registration and coffee

10:00 Maarten van Bommel, Welcome and general introduction

10:20 Klaas-Jan van den Berg, Research approach to monitor the removal of varnishes and over-paints

Monica Galeotti, Research approach to monitor the application of coatings on metal objects

Jadwiga Łukaszewicz, Research approach to monitor the consolidation methods of stone

11:20 Discussion

11:45 Poster pitches

12:30 Lunch and poster presentation

14:00 Parallel sessions

Cleaning of Paintings (Aula)

Coatings of Metals (Doelenzaal)

Consolidation of Stone (Belle van Zuylenzaal)

17:00 Drinks

February 8, 2019

University of Amsterdam

Oudemanhuispoort 4-6

room D1.09

08:30 Coffee

09:00 Coating of metal plenary session

Monica Galeotti, summary of the parallel session

Stefania Agnoletti, Case study: Facing a huge conservation project: the three bronze doors of the Baptistery of Florence

Tonny Beentjes, future perspectives in metal conservation

10:00 Consolidation of stone session

Jadwiga Łukaszewicz, summary of the parallel session

Conference branded under one of CH projects

Andreas Furche, Case study: Surface analyses and cleaning of blackened Italian marble sculptures burnt during the Second World War from the collection of the Bode-Museum in Berlin

David Giovannacci, Future perspective: On the relevance of non-destructive methods for measuring water content in masonry

11:00 Cleaning of paintings session

Klaas-Jan van den Berg, summary of the parallel session

Bronwyn Ormsby, Case study, The conservation of modern and contemporary art: collaborative cleaning research – methodologies, materials and progress

Aviva Burnstock, future perspectives

12:00 Concluding remarks and closure

Klaas Jan van den Berg of The Cultural Heritage Agency talking at the symposium. Copyright: The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands. Photo by: Melissa Daugherty

The conference in the Aula of the University of Amsterdam. Copyright: The Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands. Photo by: Melissa Daugherty

2nd Conference on Neutron Imaging and Neutron Methods in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (NINMACH) 2017

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Merging heritage and neutron science communities

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Iperionides – Newsletter of IPERION CH

<http://www.iperionch.eu/did-you-miss-it/>

International NR Newsletter – International Society for Neutron Radiology

http://www.isnr.de/images/nr_newsletter/NR13.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

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surname: Szentmiklósi

institution: MTA Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences / Budapest Neutron Centre (BNC)

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A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: 2nd Conference on Neutron Imaging and Neutron Methods in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (NINMACH) 2017

Location: Budapest, Hungary

Daily dates: 11-13 October, 2017

Organiser: Budapest Neutron Centre (MTA Centre for Energy Research, MTA Wigner Research Centre for Physics), chairman: László Szentmiklósi

Branded under project: IPERION CH

Number of participants: 70

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:

László Szentmiklósi, Katalin Bajnok, Zsolt Kasztovszky, Adél Len (eds.), Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Neutron Imaging and Neutron Methods in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (NINMACH), Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports – Special Issue

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-archaeological-science-reports/special-issue/10MPRBGBFSH>

General description of the subject:

The three-days-long meeting, organized by the Budapest Neutron Centre in cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), took place in the landmark building of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences at the river banks of Danube.

Sessions were devoted to present studies from Neutron imaging, Neutron activation analysis and Prompt gamma activation analysis as well as Neutron scattering. The technical background was highlighted in sessions called Facilities, techniques and data processing and Multi-technique approach and complementary techniques. The four keynote speakers represented the state-of-the-art of neutron imaging (Dr. Eberhard Lehmann, Dr. Burkhard Schillinger) and the interdisciplinary (Prof. Thilo Rehren) and multi-technique approach (Dr. Thomas Calligaro) of heritage science. Two of the five invited talks were focussing on archaeological interpretation (Dr. Katalin T. Biró, Dr. Friedrich Wagner), one on conservation application of historical buildings (Dr. Francesca Sciarretta) while the two others on instrumental approaches (Dr. László Szentmiklósi, Dr. Nikolay Kardjilov). The dense program of the conference included 27 oral presentations and 20 posters. In addition, a workshop by the Volume Graphics, supplier of high-end data visualization software, was also part of the program. The most represented topic was neutron imaging with three sessions, in total 9 lectures.

This meeting was attended by 66 participant representing a wide range of disciplines (physics, chemistry, geology, archaeology, conservation science, engineering) and nationalities (Argentina, Australia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Switzerland, UK, USA)

Relation to the CH projects:

The mission of the NINMACH conference series is to bring together neutron scientists, archaeologists and conservators, by creating a stimulating environment to exchange ideas and to promote this interdisciplinary research field. The scope of the conference was strongly connected to WP4 of the IPERION CH project, as results of the transnational access programme were presented, forming ca. the ¼ of the total presentations in the programme.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The mission of the NINMACH conference series is to address neutron scientists, as well as archaeologists and conservators, by creating a stimulating environment to exchange ideas and to make a bridge between them. In 2017, the Hungarian neutron and cultural heritage communities received the honour to organize the second NINMACH. The three-days-long meeting took place in the landmark building of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, right next to the famous UNESCO world heritage river banks in Budapest, Hungary. The event was organized by the Budapest Neutron Centre (BNC), the consortium of Centre for Energy Research and Wigner Research Centre for Physics, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, in cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). This meeting was a successful one with 62 registered participants representing a wide range of disciplines (physics, chemistry, geology, archaeology, conservation science, engineering) and nationalities (Argentina, Australia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Switzerland, UK, USA). Peer-reviewed proceedings will be published in a special issue of *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*.

Conference programme

Wednesday, 11th October

12:00-13:30		Registration
13:30-13:45		Opening Ceremony
13:45-14:30	K-01	Using neutron imaging data for deeper understanding of cultural heritage objects – experiences from 15 years of collaborations <i>Eberhard Lehmann</i> (PSI)
14:30-15:50		Session I – Imaging 1. Chair: Burkhard Schillinger
14:30-14:50	O-01	A pulsed neutron transmission method for metal cultural heritage research <i>Yoshiaki Kiyonagi</i> (Nagoya University)
14:50-15:10	O-02	Neutron imaging study of ‘pattern-welded’ swords from the Viking Age <i>Anna Fedrigo</i> (STFC, ISIS Neutron Source)
15:10-15:30	O-03	Study of ancient metallic artefacts by using neutron imaging techniques, Ramanspectroscopy and SEM-EDS <i>Myriam Krieg</i> (Site et Musée Romains Avenches SMRA)
15:30-15:50	O-04	The neutron imaging study of cultural heritage items from Tver treasure <i>Kuanysh Nazarov</i> (Joint Institute for Nuclear Research)
15:50-16:10		Coffee break
16:10-18:00		Session II – Multi-technique approach and complementary methods 1. Chair: Thilo Rehren
16:10-16:40	I-01	Stone artefacts and Neutrons - Case studies from Hungary <i>Katalin T. Biró</i> (Hungarian National Museum)
16:40-17:00	O-05	Non-destructive determination of the manufacturing methods of ancient Indian blades and modern replicas through advanced applications of neutron tomography and neutron diffraction <i>Francesco Grazzi</i> (Consiglio Nazionale Ricerche)
17:00-17:20	O-06	Pre-historic funerary votive assemblages – stone vases provenancing using nondestructive neutron techniques <i>M. Isabel Prudêncio</i> (Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares, Campus Tecnológico e Nuclear, Instituto Superior Técnico)
17:20-17:40	O-07	What is inside in the bronze weapons and tools? Archaeometallurgical Characterization of Late Bronze Age Metal Artefacts by Neutron Methods <i>Gábor János Tarbay</i> (Hungarian National Museum, Archaeological Department, Prehistoric Collection)
17:40-18:00	O-08	A multi-technique investigation of the incuse coinage of Magna Graecia <i>Filomena Salvemini</i> (ACNS-ANSTO, Sydney)
18:00-21:00		Poster session & Welcome cocktail hosted by Mirrotron

Thursday, 12th October

09:00-09:45	K-02	Science and Technology for Archaeology and Cultural Heritage <i>Thilo Rehren</i> (The Cyprus Institute)
09:45-10:55		Session III – Imaging 2. Chair: Eberhard Lehmann
09:45-10:15	I-02	Neutron imaging and PGAI methods applied to water absorption measurement on historic construction materials: first results and potentiality <i>Francesca Sciarretta</i> (Department of Design and Planning in Complex Environments, Università Iuav di Venezia)
10:15-10:35	O-09	Neutron tomography data fusion for visualization of South- and Southeast Asian bronzes <i>Sara Creange</i> (Rijksmuseum)
10:35-10:55	O-10	Recent uses of neutron imaging for the study of cultural heritage objects in Argentina <i>Julio Marin</i> (Centro Atómico Bariloche, CNEA, Av. Ezequiel Bustillo 9500, Bariloche, Argentina)
10:55-11:15		Coffee break
11:15-13:05		Session IV – PGAA & NAA Chair: Heather Chen-Mayer
11:15-11:45	I-03	PGAI-NT, an integrated approach of element analysis and imaging, and its applications to cultural heritage samples <i>László Szentmiklósi</i> (Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences)
11:45-12:05	O-11	Minimizing Sample Sizes while Achieving Accurate Elemental Concentrations in Neutron Activation Analysis of Precious Pottery <i>Sheldon Landsberger</i> (University of Texas)
12:05-12:25	O-12	Preliminary petrological and geochemical results of the possible source locations of HPmetaophiolitic polished stone artefacts <i>Benjámín Váczi</i> (ELTE Department of Petrology and Geochemistry)
12:25-12:45	O-13	Archaeometry at the PGAA facility of the MLZ <i>Christian Stieghorst</i> (Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (MLZ), Technical University of Munich)
12:45-13:05	O-14	Quantitative chlorine analysis of archaeological iron objects by PGA Analysis <i>Britta Schmutzler</i> (State Academy of Art and Design Stuttgart)
13:05-14:30		Lunch break
14:30-16:00		Session V – Imaging III Chair: Winfried Kockelmann
14:30-15:00	I-04	Neutron phase-contrast imaging for revealing armourers' marks <i>Nikolay Kardjilov</i> (Helmholtz-Zentrum-Berlin)
15:00-15:20	O-15	Neutron imaging as tool for investigations on historical musical instruments

15:20-15:40	O-16	<i>Eberhard Lehmann</i> (Paul Scherrer Institut) Searching for “the needle in the haystack”: reconstructing the brain and vascular system of the mammalian forerunners
15:40-16:00	O-17	<i>Burkhard Schillinger</i> (Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (FRM II)) Crystallographic characterization on different types of structure (Tsukurikomi) of Japanese swords using pulsed neutron imaging and diffraction methods <i>Kenichi Oikawa</i> (Japan Atomic Energy Agency)
16:00-16:20		Coffee break
16:20-17:40		Session VI – Facilities, techniques and data processing Chair: Nikolay Kardjilov
16:20-16:40	O-18	The neutron imaging beamline in Delft and future plans <i>Lambert van Eijck</i> (TU Delft Appl. Sci. dep. RadiationSciTech)
16:40-17:00	O-19	PGA-Imaging and Neutron Tomography at MLZ's PGAA-facility (FRM-II). A position-sensitive spectroscopy-visualization method with neutrons <i>Eschly Jan Kluge</i> (Institute of Nuclear Physics, University of Cologne) <i>Christian Stieghorst</i> (Maier-Leibnitz Center, Technical University Munich)
17:00-17:20	O-20	Neutron imaging options with fission and thermal neutrons at the NECTAR facility <i>Malgorzata Makowska</i> (Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (MLZ), FRM II, Lichtenbergstr. 1 85748 Garching, Germany; Bavarian Research Institute of Experimental Geochemistry and Geophysics (BGI), University of Bayreuth, Germany)
17:20-17:40	O-21	Neutrons and complementary methods for Cultural Heritage research at the Budapest Neutron Centre <i>László Rosta</i> (Wigner Research Centre for Physics)
17:40-18:20		Workshop (Volume Graphics) Chair: László Szentmiklósi
20:00		Conference dinner (<i>Márványenyasszony Restaurant</i>)

Friday, 13th October

09:00-09:45	K-03	Neutron Imaging Methods for Cultural Heritage at the ANTARES facility <i>Burkhard Schillinger</i> (Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum (FRM II))
09:45-10:55		Session VII – Neutron Scattering Chair: Francesco Grazi
09:45-10:15	I-05	The Metallurgical Texture of gold artefacts from the Bronze Age Rampart of Bernstorf (Bavaria) Studied by Neutron Diffraction <i>Friedrich Wagner</i> (Technical University of Munich)

10:15-10:35	O-22	IMAT: A new neutron imaging and diffraction beamline at ISIS <i>Winfried Kockelmann</i> (STFC-Rutherford Appleton Laboratory)
10:35-10:55	O-23	Neutron diffraction for cultural heritage studies:the Italian Neutron Experimental Station INES@ISIS <i>Antonella Scherillo</i> (STFC – ISIS, UK)
10:55-11:15		Coffee break
11:15-13:05		Session VIII – Multi-technique approach and complementary methods 2. Chair: Katalin T. Biró
11:15-11:35	O-24	Neutron and laboratory x-ray characterization of excavated Napoleonic artefacts from the Berezina Battlefield in Belarus <i>Jérôme Beaucour</i> (Institut Laue Langevin)
11:35-11:55	O-25	Investigation of a Simulated Chinese Jade Dagger by Neutron Radiography and Prompt Gamma Activation Analysis <i>Heather Chen-Mayer</i> (NIST)
11:55-12:15	O-26	Investigating beads from Chalcolithic funerary cremation contexts of Perdigões, Portugal <i>M. Isabel Dias</i> (Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares, Campus Tecnológico e Nuclear, Instituto Superior Técnico)
12:15-12:35	O-27	Multi-technique archaeometallurgical investigations of metal objects from the Marche Region, Italy <i>Massimo Rogante</i> (Rogante Engineering Office)
12:35-13:20	K-04	Chemical imaging of paintings: X-rays and ions as complementary probes to neutrons <i>Thomas Calligaro</i> (Centre de recherche et de restauration des musées de France C2RMF)
13:20-13:30		Closing ceremony
13:30-14:30		Lunch break
14:30-18:00		Optional visit to the Budapest Neutron Centre or to the Hungarian National Museum

NINMACH

BUDAPEST 2017

Conference branded under one of CH projects

Conference branded under one of CH projects

“Theory and Practice in Conservation - a tribute to Cesari Brandi” – 2006

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Putting researchers in contact and reuniting in books themed new knowledge

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: JOSE.....

surname: ...DELGADO-RODRIGUES.....

institution: ...LNEC.....

e-mail: delgado@lnec.pt..... contact phone: +

Conference details:

Name of the conference: Theory and Practice in Conservation - a tribute to Cesari Brandi”

Location: Lisbon

Daily dates: 2006

Organiser: LNEC

Branded under project: EU-ARTECH

Number of participants:

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:

General description of the subject:

a 574 pps. book of proceedings printed in paper with 59 invited lectures and papers.

Relation to the CH projects:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

“Stone Consolidation in Cultural Heritage research and practice” – 2008.

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

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- economic
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name: JOSE.....

surname: ...DELGADO-RODRIGUES.....

institution: ...LNEC.....

e-mail: delgado@lneec.pt..... contact phone: +

Conference details:

Name of the conference: Stone Consolidation in Cultural Heritage research and practice

Location: Lisbon

Daily dates: 2008, May

Organiser: LNEC

Branded under project: Eu-Artech

Number of participants:

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:

Conference branded under one of CH projects

General description of the subject:

published a 462 pps. book of proceedings printed in paper with 47 invited lectures and papers.

Relation to the CH projects:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

New techniques for the non-invasive investigation of the surface and subsurface structure of heritage objects

3. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

4. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

5. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

6. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

7. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

8. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

9. Person to be contacted for details

name: Piotr

surname: Targowski

institution: N. Copernicus University

e-mail:ptarg@fizyka.umk.pl. contact phone: + 48 56 611 3206

Conference details:

Name of the conference: New techniques for the non-invasive investigation of the surface and subsurface structure of heritage objects

Location: Toruń

Daily dates: 25-26 June 2013

Organiser: The National Gallery, UK and Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland

Branded under project: CHARISMA

Number of participants: 81

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue: Book

General description of the subject:

In recent years there have been significant advances in the techniques available for the non-invasive investigation of the surface and sub-surface structure of cultural heritage objects, including those being developed within WP9 of CHARISMA. This two-day workshop was held in Toruń (Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, NCU). It was an opportunity to disseminate more widely the advances in this area being made within the project, and also to bring together in a networking event experts from outside CHARISMA, through a series of invited presentations, to give an overview of both new emerging techniques that are in development and those that are already available more widely. The workshop was jointly organised by the Scientific Department at the National Gallery, London and the Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun. This workshop gave a general overview of current research on many different non-invasive techniques, and was complementary to the two-day training workshop immediately following it, which in contrast focussed on OCT, allowing participants to learn about one technique in more depth.

Relation to the CH projects:

The workshop was planned as Task 3.3b within the activities of Work Package 3 “Scientific excellence”, Task 3.3 “Oriented-topic events”. WP3 aims to share new knowledge and to improve awareness and understanding of innovative methodologies and current analytical instrumentation across the multidisciplinary field of science applied to cultural heritage.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The workshop was very successful in achieving its aim of providing an overview of current developments in the field of non-invasive instrumentation for the examination of cultural heritage objects. The longer format of the talks allowed the speakers to give a fuller description of the characteristics and basic principles of each technique, and also to discuss a variety of applications, to give the audience – the potential future users – insight into how each instrument functions and for which applications it can give good results. This approach is particularly valuable since it gives a realistic and practical view of where each technique can be used most effectively, and also some idea of what might become available in the near future. The high number of questions for the speakers and lively discussions were a very evident manifestation of the appreciation and interest of the participants in the workshop. The event formed a valuable opportunity to showcase instrumentation being developed in CHARISMA, and at the same time bring together a wider group of experts in this field to present the latest advances to conservators and conservation scientists, potential users of the new techniques in the future.

Programme of the conference

Monday 24 June 2013: Welcome reception – Collegium Maximum, Pl. Rapackiego 1

Tuesday 25 June 2013

Location: Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Chopina Street 12/18, Toruń, Poland

9:30 Opening remarks

Session chair: Bruno Brunetti, CHARISMA project coordinator, University of Perugia

10:00 *A systematic non-invasive optical investigation of wall paintings at a UNESCO world heritage site*

Haida Liang,¹ Andrei Lucian,¹ Chi Shing Cheung,¹ Bo Min Su²

¹School of Science & Technology, Nottingham Trent University, UK. ²Dunhuang Academy, Gansu Province, China

10:45 coffee break

11:15 *Thermal quasi reflectography: current research and potential applications*

Claudia Daffara,¹ Dario Ambrosini,² Luca Pezzati³

¹Dept. of Computer Science, University of Verona, Italy. ²DIIE, University of L'Aquila, Italy. ³INO-CNR, National Institute of Optics, Florence, Italy.

12:00 *Of MOUSE and Men: Single-sided NMR in Cultural Heritage*

Tyler Meldrum

Institut für Technische und Makromolekulare Chemie, RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

12:45 lunch (provided on-site)

Session chair: Heinz-Eberhard Mahnke, Freie Universität Berlin

14:15 *A CHARISMA round robin; comparison of non-invasive analyses and documentation methods for integration of results from multiple techniques on a single painting*

Marika Spring¹ and Haida Liang²

¹Scientific Department, National Gallery, London, UK. ²School of Science & Technology, Nottingham Trent University, UK.

15:00 *Laser tools in Cultural Heritage Science and Conservation; non-invasive analysis and management of cleaning interventions*

Paraskevi Pouli

Institute of Electronic Structure and Lasers (IESL), Foundation for Research and Technology–Hellas (FORTH), Heraklion, Crete, Greece.

15:45 coffee break

16:15 *Mid-infrared hyperspectral imaging of painting materials*

Costanza Miliani,^{1,2} Francesca Rosi,^{1,2} Roland Harig,³ René Braun,³ Diego Sali,⁴ Alessia Daveri,⁵ Brunetto G. Brunetti,^{1,2} Antonio Sgamellotti^{1,2}

¹ CNR-ISTM c/o Chemistry Department, University of Perugia, Italy. ² SMAArt, Chemistry Department, University of Perugia, Italy. ³ Bruker Optik GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany. ⁴ Bruker Italia S.r.l. uni personale, Milan, Italy. ⁵ Associazione laboratorio di Diagnostica per i Beni Culturali, Spoleto, Perugia, Italy.

17:00 *On site research on 'The Beanery' by Edward Kienholz with portable Fibre Optics Raman Spectroscopy'*

Suzan de Groot,¹ Anna Laganà,² and Sandra Weerdenburg³

¹ Conservation scientist, Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands (RCE), Amsterdam, The Netherlands. ² Freelance Modern Materials Conservator, ³ Conservator of Modern Objects / Head of Conservation, Stedelijk Museum Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

Conference branded under one of CH projects

17:30 END OF THE SESSION

Wednesday 26 June 2013

Location: Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Chopina Street 12/18, Toruń, Poland

Session chair: Suzan de Groot, Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands (RCE)

9:30 *Photoluminescence of painting materials*

Costanza Miliani

CNR-ISTM c/o Chemistry Department, University of Perugia, Italy.

10:15 *Multiphoton microscopy: an efficient and promising tool for in situ study of historical artifacts*

Gaël Latour,^{1*} Jean-Philippe Echard,² Marie Didier,² Marie-Claire Schanne-Klein¹

¹ Laboratory for Optics and Biosciences (LOB), Ecole Polytechnique, CNRS, INSERM, Palaiseau, France. ² Laboratoire de recherche et de restauration, Musée de la musique, Cité de la musique, Paris, France. * Currently at Laboratoire Imagerie et Modélisation en Neurobiologie et Cancérologie, Université Paris Sud, CNRS, Orsay, France

11:00 coffee break

11:30 *Short poster talks*

Time-averaged digital speckle pattern interferometry for investigation objects surfaces

Leszek Krzemien and Michal Lukomski

Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków, Poland

Analysis of Ancient Paper Structure in Transmitted Light by Application of Different Microscopic Techniques. Examples from the Collection of the Kornik Library of the Polish Academy of Science.

Tomasz Koziolec

Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland

Preliminary physicochemical studies on a shield handle originating from the Przeworsk culture cemetery located in Czersk

Ewelina Miśta and Paweł Kalbarczyk

National Centre for Nuclear Research, Swierk, Poland

12:30 lunch (provided on-site)

Session chair: Costanza Miliani, University of Perugia

14:00 *Fusion of tomographic documentation objects based on electromagnetic radiation in the near and mid infrared area of the spectrum and ultrasonic microscopy. Application to Byzantine icons from Cyprus*

Georgios Karagiannis

ORMYLIA Foundation Diagnostic Centre, Greece

14:45 *Accelerators and X-rays in cultural heritage studies*

Heinz-Eberhard Mahnke

Fachbereich Physik and Excellence Cluster TOPOI, Freie Universität Berlin, Germany

15:30 coffee break

16:00 *Optical coherence tomography for vulnerability assessment of sandstone in-situ*

Elizabeth Bemand and Haida Liang

School of Science & Technology, Nottingham Trent University, UK

16.25 *Macroscopic X-ray fluorescence analysis, a method for non-invasive imaging of painted works . Comparison with other methods and some case studies.*

Koen Janssens,¹ Mathias Alfeld,¹ Geert van der Snickt,¹ Joris Dik²

¹ University of Antwerp, Belgium. ² Delft University of Technology, Netherlands

17:10 Final remarks

17:20 END OF THE SESSION

The training course on application of Optical Coherence Tomography

3. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

4. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

5. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

6. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

7. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

8. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

9. Person to be contacted for details

name: Piotr

surname: Targowski

institution: N. Copernicus University

e-mail:ptarg@fizyka.umk.pl. contact phone: + 48 56 611 3206

Conference details:

Name of the conference: The training course on application of Optical Coherence Tomography

Location: Toruń

Daily dates: 27-28 June 2013

Organiser: Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland

Branded under project: CHARISMA

Number of participants: 46

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue: Book of Abstracts, M. Spring, P. Targowski Eds, NCU Press 2013, ISBN: 978-83-231-9031-8

General description of the subject:

The training course on application of Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to structural analysis has been co-organised by NCU and National Gallery London. It has been held in Toruń (Centre for Quantum Optic – Institute of Physics, NCU) from 27th to 28th June 2013 with 44 participants. The course has been structured as lectures and hands-on sessions. This two-day training event was dedicated to traditional and innovative applications of OCT to the examination of cultural heritage objects. During the first day the physical background and a review of the state-of-the-art of OCT was presented together with the most advanced applications to examination of cultural heritage objects. A second day was mostly devoted to practical training with utilisation of the OCT instrument built for the CHARISMA project and a commercial system from Thorlabs. The course was immediately preceded by the meeting “New techniques for the non-invasive investigation of the surface and subsurface structure of heritage objects” also organized under CHARISMA. For technical reasons both events had a combined “Book of Abstracts” and a joint website.

Relation to the CH projects:

The training on Spectroscopic Techniques has been planned within the activities of Work Package 3 “Scientific excellence”, task 3.1 “Sharing of resources and oriented-training on advanced instrumentation”.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The lectures were devoted to fundamentals of the technique and the applications in conservation science. The subject oriented approach has been chosen for presentations of applications – separate lectures have been presented for examinations of easel paintings, Chinese glaze, faience, historic wood, historic glass and reverse painting of glass. In addition certain technical aspects like comparison with other techniques, use of parallel processing for real time data processing, and a LIBS-OCT technique have been presented.

Hands-on training was performed in two groups of trainees with use of two instruments: a home-made SdOCT instrument developed in NCU for Charisma project and SdOCT microscope from Thorlabs. Participants could compare images and acquisition protocols of both instruments and learn how to identify specific structural details of objects examined. The training was focused on examination of paintings (dr M. Iwanicka), jade and porcelain (dr Mei-Li Yang) and stained glass (dr. M. Walczak, prof. P. Targowski).

Provide the programme of the conference

Thursday 27 June 2013

Location: Institute of Physics, Centre for Quantum Optics, Nicolaus Copernicus University
Toruń, Grudziądzka Street 5, Toruń, Poland

9:00 Opening remarks

Session chair: Mei-Li Yang

9:15 *Introduction to the OCT technique*

Piotr Targowski

Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland

10:00 *High resolution Fourier domain optical coherence tomography for resolving thin layers in painted works*

Chi Shing Cheung, Haida Liang

Nottingham Trent University, UK

10:20 *Application of Optical Coherence Tomography to the examination of varnish layers on the Ghent altarpiece*

Hélène Dubois

KIK IRPA - Royal Institute For Cultural Heritage, Brussels, Belgium

10:40 coffee break

Session chair: Claudia Daffara

11:10 *Next Generation OCT for Art Conservation, Art History & Archaeology*

Haida Liang¹, Chi Shing Cheung¹, Masaki Tokurakawa², Jae M.O. Daniel², W. Andrew Clarkson², Marika Spring³, Dawid Thickett⁴

¹School of Science & Technology, Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham, UK, ²Optoelectronics Research Centre, University of Southampton, Highfield, UK, ³Scientific Department, National Gallery, London, UK, ⁴English Heritage, London, UK

11:55 *Laser ablation monitoring with OCT*

Paraskevi Pouli¹, Kristalia Melessanaki¹, Magdalena Iwanicka², Łukasz Ćwikliński³, Piotr Targowski³

¹Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas, Heraklion, Crete, Greece; ²Institute for the Study, Restoration and Conservation of Cultural Heritage, N. Copernicus University, Torun, Poland; ³Institute of Physics, N. Copernicus University, Torun, Poland

12:15 *Ultra-high resolution, full-field, time domain OCT in the visible range and multi-spectral camera. Cross-checking and complementarity of the images*

Mady Elias

Evry University, France

13:00 lunch (provided on-site)

Session chair: Mady Elias

14:30 *Using Optical Coherence Tomography to Examine the Structure of Ancient Chinese Glaze and Jade*

Mei-Li Yang

National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan

15:15 *Combined LIBS/OCT technique for examination of paintings*

Ewa A. Kaszewska¹, Marcin Sylwestrzak¹, Jan Marczak², Wojciech Skrzeczanowski², Magdalena Iwanicka³, Elżbieta Szmit-Naud³, Demetrios

Anglos^{4,5}, and Piotr Targowski¹

¹Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland; ²Institute of Optoelectronics, Military University of Technology, Warsaw, Poland; ³Institute for the Study, Restoration and Conservation of Cultural Heritage, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland; ⁴Institute of Electronic Structure & Laser, Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas, Heraklion, Crete, Greece; ⁵Department of Chemistry, University of Crete, Heraklion, Crete, Greece

15:35 *From confocal microscopy to confocal OCT*

Raffaella Fontana¹, Marco Barucci¹, Enrico Pampaloni¹, Luca Pezzati¹, Claudia Daffara²

¹INO-CNR, Istituto Nazionale di Ottica, Firenze, Italy; ²Università degli Studi di Verona, Verona, Italy

15:55 coffee break

Session chair: Haida Liang

16:25 *Assessing the potential of OCT for the non-invasive examination of varnish layers; a survey of paintings in the National Gallery London*

Marika Spring¹ and Haida Liang²

¹The National Gallery, London, UK; ²School of Science & Technology, Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham, UK

17:10 *Tracing of past restorations of ‘Madonna dei Fusi’ by Leonardo da Vinci (school)*

Magdalena Iwanicka¹, B.J. Rouba¹, P. Targowski², M. Sylwestrzak², Ewa A. Kaszewska², Cecilia Frosinini³

¹Institute for the Study, Restoration and Conservation of Cultural Heritage, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland; ²Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland; ³Opificio delle Pietre Dure e Laboratori di Restauro, Firenze, Italy;

17:30 *Sweep Source Optical Coherence Tomography (SS-OCT) for the examination of dry and waterlogged “heritage” wood*

Dimitris Tsipotas¹, Alexandros Diamantoudis²

¹Technological Educational Institute of Larisa, Greece; ²University Ecclesiastical Academy of Thessaloniki, Greece

17:50 *Parallel processing of OCT data for monitoring of restoration procedures*

Marcin Sylwestrzak, Ewa A. Kaszewska, Magdalena Iwanicka, Łukasz Ćwikliński, Piotr Targowski

Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Torun, Poland

18:10 END OF THE SESSION

Friday 28 June 2013

Location: Institute of Physics, Centre for Quantum Optics, Nicolaus Copernicus University
Toruń, Grudziądzka Street 5, Toruń, Poland

Session chair: Marika Spring

9:00 *Examination of structure and properties of historic glass with OCT*

Piotr Targowski¹, Paweł Karaszkievicz², Bogumiła J. Rouba³, Dariusz Markowski³, Ludmiła Tymińska-Widmer³, Magdalena Iwanicka³, Ewa A. Kaszewska¹, Marcin Sylwestrzak¹

¹Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland; ²Academy of Fine Arts, Kraków, Poland; ³Institute for the Study, Restoration and Conservation of Cultural Heritage, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland

9:20 *Examination of reverse painting on glass (Hinterglasmalerei) with OCT*

Magdalena Iwanicka¹, Ludmiła Tymińska-Widmer¹, Bogumiła J. Rouba¹, Ewa A. Kaszewska², Marcin Sylwestrzak², and Piotr Targowski²

Conference branded under one of CH projects

¹Institute for the Study, Restoration and Conservation of Cultural Heritage, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland; ²Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland

9:40	<i>Introduction to NCU OCT instruments</i> Tomasz Bajraszewski, Łukasz Ćwikliński, Iwona Gorczyńska, Michalina Góra, Ewa A. Kaszewska, Marcin Sylwestrzak, Maciej Szkulmowski, Anna Szkulmowska, Piotr Targowski Institute of Physics, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Toruń, Poland
10:00	<i>Introduction to Thorlabs OCT instruments</i> Martin Krah Thorlabs, Germany
10:20	coffee break
10:50	hands-on training
13:00	lunch (provided on-site)
14:30	hands-on training
16:00	Final remarks
16:10	END OF THE SESSION

GlazeArt2018 – International Conference Glazed Ceramics in Cultural Heritage

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry
- other – describe:

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Addressing, not the materiality of heritage assets but rather their immaterial side: VALUES

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Joao.....

surname: ...MIMOSO.....

institution: ...LNEC.....

e-mail: jmimoso@lnec.pt..... contact phone: +

Conference branded under one of CH projects

A book (a chapter of the book)

Reference

Pereira, S., Menezes, M. & Rodrigues, J. editors, GlazeArt2018 International Conference “Glazed Ceramics in Cultural Heritage”, Book of Proceedings, LNEC, Lisbon, 2018 ISBN 978-972-49-2301-7

General description of the contents

Deals with studies on glazed ceramics as cultural heritage. The book of Proceedings is printed on paper in full colour. Contents are 43 extended abstracts over 87 pps. annexed a digital book of Proceedings with full papers over a full papers over 457 pages.

The novelty of the book (the chapter)

Each collection of texts on glazed ceramics as cultural heritage is very unusual.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Full Book + Conference details will be sent (the book as pdf file) to the Coordination Office

GlazeArt2018

International Conference
Glazed Ceramics in Cultural Heritage

A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: **GlazeArt2018- International Conference Glazed Ceramics in Cultural Heritage**

Location: Lisbon, PT

Daily dates: 29-30 Oct 2018

Organiser: LNEC

Branded under project: IPERION CH.

Number of participants: 96

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:
.....above..

General description of the subject:

Relation to the CH projects:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Programme of the conference:

http://glazeart2018.lnec.pt/GlazArch2018_programa_v6.pdf

Intangibility Matters – International Conference on the values of tangible heritage (IMaTTe 2017)

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

Addressing, not the materiality of heritage assets but rather their immaterial side: VALUES

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: MARLUCI.....

surname: ...MENEZES.....

institution: ...LNEC.....

e-mail: marluci@lnec.pt..... contact phone: +

A book (a chapter of the book)

Reference

Menezes, M., Costa, D. & Rodrigues, J. editors Intangibility Matters- International conference on the values of tangible heritage (IMaTTe 2017) Book of Proceedings, LNEC, Lisbon, 2017 ISBN 978-972-49-2295-9

General description of the contents

Deals with values associated to material heritage (the immaterial side of materiality). The book of Proceedings is printed on paper in full colour. Contents are 42 full papers over 417 pages.

The novelty of the book (the chapter)

The immaterial side of materiality is not often addressed.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Full Book + Conference details were sent (the book as pdf file) to the Coordination Office

A conference

Conference details:

Name of the conference: Intangibility Matters- International conference on the values of tangible heritage

Location: Lisbon, PT

Daily dates: 2017, may

Organiser: LNEC

Branded under project: IPERION CH.

Number of participants: 96

How the proceedings were published? Provide bibliographic data of the book or journal issue:
.....above..

Conference branded under one of CH projects

General description of the subject: Intangibility Matters, the IPERION CH international conference on the values of tangible heritage – IMaTTe 2017, aims at offering a discussion forum for scientists and other professionals working on the Cultural Heritage field about the intangible aspects of tangible cultural heritage assets.

Relation to the CH projects:

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

Programme of the conference :

<http://imatte2017.lnec.pt/programme.html>

Conservation and Revelation of the Ghent Altarpiece

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

The rediscovery of Jan van Eyck, 'King of Painters'

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Several press releases and conferences have been organised in the framework of the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece:

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PersberichtGhentAltarpiece_EN_V2.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/PressRelease_KIK-IRPA_GhentAltarpiece_27June2013.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2014.06.20_Press_kit_Ghent_Altarpiece.pdf

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/12-10-2016_Press_Lam_Gods.pdf

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Persbericht%20Lam%20Gods%209%20nov%202017%20EN.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Dossier%20de%20presse%20Jan%20van%20Eyck%20en%20lign e%2011%20jan%202018.pdf>

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/2018.06.19%20Press%20kit%20Ghent%20Altarpiece%20EN.pdf>

The website [closetovaneyck www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be](http://www.closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be), launched in 2011 and regularly updated, is a pioneering example of open-access resources for technical art history and conservation. This has also been echoed in the press.

<http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/Ghent%20Altarpiece%20-%20Web%20site%20-%20Press%20rel ease%20-%20July%207%202011%20-%20EN.pdf>

http://www.kikirpa.be/uploads/files/GhentAltarpiecewebsite_PressRelease.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

The website "closer to van Eyck" (<http://closetovaneyck.kikirpa.be>) is financially supported by the

Conference branded under one of CH projects

Getty Foundation. It is a pioneering tool in the presentation of conservation-restoration process and a model for open access. The conservation is financed by the Flemish government (80%) and the Baillet-Latout Fund (20%). Research for conservation is carried out by KIK-IRPA in collaboration with the Universities of Ghent and Antwerp and has benefitted from sponsorship from the Gieskes-Strijbis Fund. Punctual analytical expertise have been provided by scientists from the Nicolaus Copernicus University (Toruń) and the National Gallery (Washington).

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Hélène

surname: Dubois

institution: KIK-IRPA

e-mail: helene.dubois@kikirpa.be contact phone: +

Conference details:

Name of the conference: Ghent Altarpiece 2nd International Study Day

Location: Ghent University Aula Academica

Daily dates: 11 September 2018

Organiser: KIK-IRPA and Universiteit Gent

Branded under project: IPERION

Number of participants: 350

How the proceedings were published? The proceedings will be published in the form of a book, in 2019

General description of the subject:

The conference gave an overview of the interdisciplinary research and the results of the first phase of the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece (2012-2016)

Relation to the CH projects:

The proceedings of the conference are financed by IPERION. The research and conservation interdisciplinary research on the conservation of the Ghent Altarpiece: approach and methodology, material history, artistic techniques, issues of presentation and communication.

The 7 of the 9 presentations all have benefitted from CHARISMA and IPERION contribution, whether directly or indirectly.

IPERION is clearly referred to in the credentials.

Importance

The conference gathered presentations on fundamental and innovative interdisciplinary research on the conservation, technical and scientific study of the Ghent Altarpiece. The participants comprised CH professionals of all disciplines involved: Art Historians, Conservation Scientists, conservators as well as students of C/R and Art History and members of the general public. Most participants were Belgians, but scholars and scientists from other European countries and from the United States were also attending.

The conference was certainly interesting for the general public who is curious about the conservation campaign, which is carried out in public view in the museum of Fine Arts in Ghent. Several guides of

cultural associations also attended and transmit this information to the public during visits at the conservation studio. The impressive results of the conservation, which would not have been possible without academic and scientific research, is very attractive to the local public and through tourism; it has therefore an important economical and societal impact

Provide the programme of the conference

GHENT ALTARPIECE 2 nd INTERNATIONAL STUDY DAY	
	<p>11 SEPTEMBER 2018 GHENT Aula Academica (to be confirmed) Voldersstraat 9</p>
9.30 - 9.40	<p>Introduction Hilde De Clercq (KIK-IRPA) and Maximiliaan Martens (UGent)</p>
9.40 - 10.00	<p>Material History in the 15th and 16th centuries Hélène Dubois (UGent, KIK-IRPA)</p>
10.00 - 10.20	<p>The Conservation Treatment Livia Depuydt, Bart Devolder, Hélène Dubois, Nathalie Laquière, Claire Mehagnoul, Laure Mortiaux, Marie Postec, Françoise Rosier, Griet Steyaert, Jean-Albert Glatigny, Anne-Sophie Augustyniak (KIK-IRPA)</p>
10.20 - 10.40	<p>The Paint Analysis Jana Sanjova, Cédric Glaude, Steven Saverwyns (KIK-IRPA); Koen Janssens, Geert Van der Snick (Universiteit Antwerpen); Peter Vandenaebelle (UGent), Alexia Coudray (KIK-IRPA)</p>
10.40 - 11.00	<p>The Creative Process: From (Under)Drawing to the Final Touch in Paint Griet Steyaert, Marie Postec (KIK-IRPA)</p>
11.00 - 11.30	<p>Break</p>
11.30 - 11.50	<p>The Quatrain and Other Inscriptions Susan Jones, Anne-Sophie Augustyniak, Hélène Dubois (KIK-IRPA)</p>
11.50 - 12.10	<p>Imagining the Original Display Bart Franssen, Jean-Albert Glatigny (KIK-IRPA)</p>
12.10 - 12.20	<p>Van Eyck Research in Open Access Christina Currie, Bart Franssen, Susan Jones (KIK-IRPA)</p>
12.20 - 12.30	<p>Closer to Van Eyck Ron Spronk (Queen's University, Kingston and Radboud Universiteit, Nijmegen), Christina Currie (KIK-IRPA), Ann Doooms (VUB), Bart Franssen (KIK-IRPA)</p>
12.30 - 12.50	<p>Second Phase : An introduction Hélène Dubois</p>
12.50 - 13.00	<p>Questions Jørgen Wadum (CATS at SMK)</p>
13.00 - 13.10	<p>Closing Remarks Cyril Stoo (KIK-IRPA)</p>
13.10 - 14.00	<p>Free time for lunch</p>

International conference “Tempera painting between 1800 and 1950 – Experiments and innovations from the Nazarene movement to abstract art”, 15-17 March 2018, Munich (JRA WP 9)

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? IF YES, provide the description and available links

Postprints available as print version published by Archetype Publications Ltd and as free open access download:

http://www.doernerinstitut.de/tempera_2018/downloads/Tempera_Painting_1800_1950_128dpi.pdf

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Heike

surname: Stege

institution: Doerner Institut, Bavarian State Painting Collections, Munich

e-mail: Heike.Stege@doernerinstitut.pinakothek.de contact phone: +

Conference details:

Name of the conference: Tempera painting between 1800 and 1950 – Experiments and innovations from the Nazarene movement to abstract art

Location: Munich

Daily dates: 15-17 March 2018

Organiser: The Doerner Institut of the Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen

Branded under project: IPERION

Number of participants: 270

How the proceedings were published? The proceedings will be published in the form of a book, in 2018

General description of the subject:

International conference “Tempera painting between 1800 and 1950 – Experiments and innovations from the Nazarene movement to abstract art”

Relation to the CH projects:

Funding by the EU IPERION CH project allowed the publication of a richly illustrated postprint volume by Archetype Publications now available either in print form or as free and open access download via the website of the Doerner Institut.

Importance

From the 15 to 17 March 2018, Munich and its ‘Kunstareal’ was the location for three days of exchange and experiment on ‘Tempera Painting between 1800 and 1950’. The Doerner Institut of the Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen hosted this international conference with over 270 participants from 22 countries, which took place in close cooperation with the Academy of Fine Arts, Munich, and the Technical University Munich, Chair of Conservation-Restoration, Art Technology and Conservation Science, as well as museum partners Villa Stuck and the Lenbachhaus. Munich has a long history as a hotspot for artists and scholars interested in painting techniques. All the above-mentioned institutions share an unbroken tradition of theoretical and practical engagement with art-technological questions reaching back into the 19th and early 20th century. Prominent painting technicians including Ernst Berger and Max Doerner researched and taught in this field, and chemists such as Alexander Eibner studied the properties and durability of artists’ materials. This milieu inspired influential artists including Franz von Lenbach and Franz von Stuck as well as members of ‘Der Blaue Reiter’ to experiment with new materials and techniques. In this period, ‘tempera’ and experiments on new binding media systems were among the most debated and complex topics of painting techniques. For about 10 years, intense academic research and exchange on this fascinating history of tempera painting has been ongoing among numerous institutions and independent scholars, both in Germany and elsewhere. However, good research always leads to more questions and we felt that this was the moment to share the manifold views and research activities among a broader, international audience, bringing together scholars from the fields of conservation, technical art history, science and art history. The two days of lectures covered a broad range of questions such as: What were the artists trying to achieve? Which materials did they use and how did they prepare and apply them? How can we examine and understand their techniques? In addition to theoretical disputes, the conference offered a day dedicated to practical workshops

Conference branded under one of CH projects

and guided gallery tours allowing participants to gain hands-on experience of the making of paints and their application as well as a splendid opportunity to study works of tempera painting preserved in Munich museums. Funding by the EU IPERION CH project allowed the publication of a richly illustrated postprint volume by Archetype Publications now available either in print form or as free and open access download via the website of the Doerner Institut. These texts explore the revival of tempera painting between 1800 and 1950 from the perspectives of art history, technical art history, conservation and scientific analysis. General papers give an overview on topics such as the historical background of tempera painting, its terminologies, commercial production and the reconstruction of historical recipes, fundamentals of rheology, binding medium analyses and its interpretation. Moreover, particular papers focus on the work of Christina Herringham, Frances Hodgkins, Paul Klee, Hermann Prell, John Roddam Spencer Stanhope, Joseph Southall, Edward Steichen and Ossawa Tanner. The book thus gives new insights into what artists were trying to achieve, the materials they used and how they prepared and applied them.

Cover of the conference postprints. © Archetype Ltd.

Summary of a given TNA activity (e.g. statistics)

TNA activities of the Budapest Neutron Centre

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

8. Person to be contacted for details

name: Zsolt

surname: Kasztovszky

institution: Centre for Energy Research, Hungarian Academy of Sciences / Budapest Neutron Centre

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contact phone: + 36-1-3922222 / 3143

Indicate the appropriate TNA:

- MOLAB
- FIXLAB
- ARCHLAB

dates the summary covers: 2015.05.01-2019.09.30.

Summary of a given TNA activity (e.g. statistics)

General description of the summary

The success of the TNA provided by the Budapest Neutron Centre during the IPERION-CH project is demonstrated here. The increasing number of the access days requested by European users show the demand for multi-instrumental approach in Heritage Science.

Importance (about 1/2 page, 11 pt)

The Budapest Neutron Centre is one of the four FIXLAB trans-national access providers in the former CHARISMA FP7 and in the presently running IPERION-CH H2020 projects. Budapest Neutron Centre (BNC), a consortium of MTA Centre for Energy Research and Wigner Research Centre for Physics, offers access to a broad range of instruments applicable to non-destructive characterization of Cultural Heritage objects, utilizing the neutrons produced by the Budapest Research Reactor. The applied analytical and scattering methods can reveal the element composition and structure of even complex Cultural Heritage objects made of stones, ceramics, metals and glass. The analytical and structural information can be combined with 2D or 3D images obtained using neutrons of various energies or X-ray radiation. The up-to-date features of the instruments are available at www.bnc.hu. In the beamtime applications, typically, a combination of complementary analytical methods is chosen by the users. With the joint interpretation of elemental and structural data, or correlating surface and bulk concentration data, one can reveal much more details of the objects in a completely non-destructive way. This approach towards research problems in heritage science become more and more attractive for the experts of this interdisciplinary field.

Despite the almost one-year long reactor shut down, we received beam time applications for twice of the experimental days originally foreseen in the project.

Other

Itinerant course on stone conservation

2. Target of the story – mark ALL applicable audience

- press (media) release
- science community
- CH community (e.g. restorers, curators, prospective TNA users, etc.)
- European Commission
- business and industry

3. Tentative punch line (i.e. your story in a tweet or a Facebook post) –

A new concept in training for the conservation of CH

4. Indicate the CH projects within which it was developed – mark ALL applicable projects:

- LabS-TECH
- Eu-ARTECH
- CHARISMA
- IPERION CH
- ARIADNE

5. May this success story be considered as innovation? Specify its impact:

- academic
- economic
- societal

6. Has this success story generated already any public release (e.g. in press, TV etc.)? NO

7. Any additional information which may be important for the presentation of the success story, not included in the relevant questionnaire below.

Under the framework of the EU project CHARISMA an itinerant course on stone conservation was designed and implemented in different countries. The innovation was that the same basic program was implemented in several countries with local lecturers and adapted to local specificities (e.g. sorts of stone, decay risks, ...). The first venue took place in Lisbon, Portugal; the second in Torun, Poland; the third in both Brussels and Amsterdam. A fourth venue took place in Brazil, then without founding through the Framework Programs.

The course addressed subjects ranging from stone materials to conservation methods and products, from the preparatory steps to the implementation phases of conservation interventions, and aimed at providing the students with modern concepts and updated knowledge on the most relevant aspects of this discipline.

In Lisbon the students were housed together at LNEC offering an opportunity for knowing each other, exchanging views and preparing the presentations given at the close of the course.

The teachers came from different CHARISMA partners and included additional external invited lecturers.

Other

8. Person to be contacted for details

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surname: DELGADO-RODRIGUES

institution: LNEC

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